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INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

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Summary

This document reports on an identification of new incentives for soil health business models. Short term investments in soil health can deliver long term results in food security and value chain. Farmers and land managers can face barriers to change practices, such as perceived risk, access to finance or initial costs. Reviews of successful farmer-owned urban areas businesses, farmer, and forestry linkages point to the importance of new incentives development for: 1- market linkages for healthy soil new value chain development of safety food and services, 2- internal and bridging innovative ways of blending finance streams and policy measures, and 3- creating a soil health business models to reduce production costs and costs as a result of using a differentiated approach in food production systems.

To identify the new incentives and to evaluate the impact of the business model was applied two steps:

1. New incentives' gap analysis based on five building blocks of the Business Model Canvas (BMC);
2. Multicriteria Analysis - BOCR analysis. The structure of MCA-BOCR analysis (Benefits, Opportunities, Costs and Risks) is suitable for achieving the identification of the new incentives. Short term investments that share risks and costs or provide innovative finance options are covered by the Risks and Costs block in the BOCR analysis. Through the elements of these four blocks and through ANP it is covered all the factors that influence the choice of an appropriate new incentive.

As a result, a typology of all incentives related to the five building blocks of the Business Model Canvas (BMC) can be derived. Each incentive is related to two of the building blocks. This relation is direct and represents how implementing any of the incentives affects each element of the BMC. Regarding the relationship with the BMC building blocks, the results from the first step shows that *Revenue and costs* is the building block that is covered by most of the incentives included here (17 of them are related to this block). Secondly, *Key activities* is the block covered in 13 of the incentives. The other three elements, *Customer value proposition*, *Channels and partnerships* and *Key resources*, are almost equally covered by the investigated NOVASOIL project case studies. Regarding the categories of incentives that were chosen in all case studies, the most preferred one is for Subsidies (1.5 Code), which is included in ten of the incentives.

Analysis in the second step shows the following in terms of the three promoted business models in WP 2:

- **Business models under Payment per ES**

The results for the case studies *Payment per ES* show that the most covered elements of the BMC in the case studies are *Revenue and costs* and *Key resources*, followed by *Channels and partnerships* and *Key activities*.

Regarding the category of incentives, under the *Payment per ES* business model, are included the following categories:

- 1.3 Taxes/charges
- 1.12 Corporate social responsibility
- 1.5 Subsidies
- 1.8 Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)
- 1.10 Impact funds
- 2.1 Green bonds
- 2.3 Conservation concessions
- 2.4 Direct Payment for Ecosystem Services

Of those mentioned above, the category which appear the most is *1.5 Subsidies*, which is chosen in four of the suggested new incentives from the case studies.

- **Business models under Value chain**

The results show that the most covered element of the BMC in the case studies under *Value Chain* is *Key resources*. The other elements of the BMC are almost evenly covered by all case studies.

Regarding the category of incentives are included the following categories:

- 1.5 Subsidies
- 2.1 Green bonds
- 1.8 Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)
- 1.10 Impact funds
- 1.9 Offsets
- 2.2 Voluntary farm set-asides
- 2.3 Conservation concessions
- 2.6 Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)

The category which appears to be the most preferred one is *2.6 Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)*, which is chosen in two of the suggested new incentives from the case studies.

- **Business models under Carbon credits**

The results show that the most covered element of the BMC in the case studies under *Carbon credits* is *Revenue and costs*.

Regarding the category of incentives are included the following categories:

- 1.1 Prohibition of use
- 1.5 Subsidies
- 1.10 Impact funds

1 Introduction

1.1 Context of WP 3 objectives

The objective of the task T 3.2: Identification of new incentives soil health business models is to investigate the opportunities and gaps of new incentives and to build a digital hub of knowledge (preliminary version reported in D3.2).

The focus of this report is on investigation of the opportunities that new incentives could give taking into consideration the soil health business models.

The identification of new incentives is connected to the implementation of innovative soil health technologies for production safe food production.

1.2 Connection with the other WPs

The report presents analysis based on opportunities and gaps of the new incentives for business models defined by the NOVASOIL partners in WP 2. Healthy soils are not only important for the food system, but they are also providing various other ecosystem services. Three business models were analysed in WP2 to explore new incentives for soil health: *public payments for ecosystem services*, *value chain integration*, and *carbon markets*. The promoted business models were included into analysis of new incentives for soil health business models.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the document

Deliverable D 3.4 *Report on new incentives soil health business models* aims to prioritize the defined new incentives for soil health business models, which are part of T 3.2.

The purpose of the report is to assess the new incentives and find their importance for soil health business model development. The analysis is made on two steps:

- First, identification of the new incentives that affect the characteristics of the business models that the current ones don't.
- Second, assessment of the new incentives using MCA-BOCR to find their importance.

The first step of analysis was made on the following 12 NOVASOIL Case studies (CSs), while the MCA-BOCR analysis for only 10 of them (without the last two):

1. BG: Integrated production in the vineyards with vinery and rural tourism;
2. DE 1: CO2-Land;
3. IT1: Producers' association "Sandy district";
4. IT 2: Multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas;
5. IT 3: CiRAA LTEs on conventional and organic agriculture;
6. SP 1: Integrated Production, Periurban park;
7. SP 2: Organic wine production – value chain from grapes cultivation to marketing;
8. EE: Production of quality seeds;
9. LV 1: Crop production and animal farming - Alley cropping system;
10. LV 2: Crop production and animal farming - Digital showcase;
11. UK: Crop production;
12. DE 2: AgoraNatura.

1.4 Process of development

The process of the construction methodology for identification of new incentives started at the beginning of July 2023.

In September it was prepared instruction that was coordinated with the partners from EVENOR. At the beginning of October (7 October 2023) the instruction for identification of new incentives was sent to all partners. Also, the partners were invited for discussion to a technical meeting on 16 October 2023. Based on the feedback received during the technical meeting, on 01 November 2023 it was sent a final version of the instruction. After that, it was held additional technical meeting on 13 November 2023 with the partners to clarify some details in the process of new incentives data collection.

The NBU team supported the partners during the data collection answering all the questions and concerns of the partners. The original new incentives for soil health business model's questionnaire were developed for 3 incentives. Additionally, it was prepared questionnaire only for 2 incentives.

The results from collecting and analyzing the data are summarized in table 1.

Table 1 results from collecting and analyzing the data from case studies

Case study	New incentives delivered	MCDM questionnaire delivered	Entering the data in software	Final analysis
BG: Integrated production in the	yes	yes	yes	yes

vineyards with vinery and rural tourism				
DE 1: "CO2-Land"	yes	yes	yes	yes
IT1: Producers' association "sandy district"	yes	yes	yes	yes
IT 2: multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas	yes	yes	yes	yes
IT 3: CiRAA LTEs on conventional and organic agriculture	yes	yes	yes	yes
SP 1: Integrated Production, Periurban park	yes	yes	yes	yes
SP 2: Organic wine production – value chain from grapes cultivation to marketing	yes	yes	yes	yes
EE: production of quality seeds	yes	yes	yes	yes
LV 1: Crop production and animal farming - Alley cropping system	yes	yes	yes	yes
LV 2: Crop production and animal farming - Digital showcase	yes	yes	yes	yes
UK: Crop production	yes	-	-	-
DE 2: AgoraNatura	no new incentives	-	-	-

2 Methodology

WP3 investigate the opportunities and gaps of new incentives for redirection of financial streams and policy support measures for provision of innovative soil health technologies for producing safe food. Short term investments that share risks and costs or provide innovative finance options would help overcome those barriers, leading to long term returns.

As it was mentioned earlier, the analysis of the new incentives was performed on two steps:

First step, it was identified the new incentives that could affect characteristics of the business model that the current incentives don't.

Second step, assessment of the new incentives using MCA-BOCR to find their importance for soil health business model development.

The structure of MCA - BOCR analysis (Benefits, Opportunities, Costs and Risks) is suitable for achieving the goals. The goals of this analysis includes the study of opportunities, which are considered to consist in two parts - Benefits and Opportunities. Short term investments that share risks and costs or provide innovative finance options are covered by the Risks and Costs block in the BOCR analysis. For every block in BOCR is created a separate network where ANP is applied. Through the elements of these four blocks and through ANP all the factors that influence the choice of an appropriate new incentives. In terms of sustainability, it is necessary to consider the incentives in Economic, Technological, Social, Political point of view. For this reason, it is relied on Economic, Technological, Social and Political as control criteria in BOCR analysis.

Within the BOCR analysis, the analysis goes through four levels of the networks (four phases). Within each block, evaluation of the influence of the elements on the new incentives is the first level of analysis ([phase 1](#)). The elements are grouped in clusters which is the second level of analysis. Control criteria are the second level of the analysis ([phase 2](#)). This second level corresponds to the generalized factors: 1- market linkages for healthy soil new value chain development of safety food and services, 2- internal and bridging innovative ways of blending finance streams and policy measures, and 3- creating a soil health business models to reduce production costs and costs as a result of using a differentiated approach in food production systems. The clusters are grouped in control criteria, which corresponds to the third level of the analysis ([phase 3](#)). Finally the forth level of the analysis is related with evaluation of the four blocks – Benefits, Opportunities, Costs and Risk, according the strategic criteria ([phase 4](#)).

Thanks to the network built in this way, it is possible to trace the influence of each cluster and its elements on the choice of each new incentive. Also, it was analyzed the aggregate influence of all elements and corresponding clusters, control, and strategic criteria on the choice of incentive.

2.1. Identifying new incentives for soil health business model development

For the purposes of the analysis, we are using the definition for new incentive as follows: any incentives which are new for the specific case study and business model, and which are different from the ones implemented until now. Additionally the new incentives need to cover the gaps if there are in the BMC structure.

The source for finding new incentives in the form of opportunities is based on three main groups:

- The Common Agricultural Policy: 2023-2027 – review of planned incentives;
- Other policies;
- FAO classification (presented in table 2).

Table 2 is based on the typology of incentives prepared in the previous task 3.1. Here, the typology of incentives is related with the five building blocks of the Business Model Canvas (BMC). Each incentive is related to two of the building blocks (table 2, the cells in green colour). These relations were discussed and agreed during the technical meeting at 13-th of November 2023. They are direct and represents how implementing any of the incentives affects each element of the BMC.

Table 2 Typology of incentives and their relation to the BMC blocks

Category of incentives		Business Model Canvas building blocks				
		Customer value proposition	Channels and partnerships	Revenue and cost	Key resources	Key activities
Policy-driven	1.1 Prohibition of use					
	1.2 Property use rights					
	1.3 Taxes/charges					
	1.4 Mandatory farm set-asides					
	1.5 Subsidies					
	1.6 Conservation easements					
	1.7 Permits and quotas					
	1.8 Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)					
	1.9 Offsets					
	1.10 Impact funds					
	1.11 Responsible sourcing of agriculture products and services					
	1.12 Corporate social responsibility					
	1.13 Others (<i>incentives not included in previous categories</i>)					
	2.1 Green bonds					

Category of incentives		Business Model Canvas building blocks				
		Customer value preposition	Channels and partnerships	Revenue and cost	Key resources	Key activities
Voluntary	2.2 Voluntary farm set-asides					
	2.3 Conservation concessions					
	2.4 Direct Payment for Ecosystem Services					
	2.5 Rewards for Ecosystem Services					
	2.6 Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)					
	2.7 Others (<i>incentives not included in previous categories</i>)					

Source: Adapted to Table 2 in Deliverable 3.1

Identifying new incentives for the provision of soil health activities is based on assessing **current gaps** of incentives (Table 3). Each of the proposed incentives in the NOVASOIL business case models are assessed whether they meet the five building blocks of the BMC following the identified direct relations from Table 2.

Table 3 Relation of incentives with the five building blocks of the business model

Incentives	Category of incentives	Period before 2023	Period 2023-2027	Business Model Canvas building blocks				
				Customer value preposition	Channels and partnerships	Revenue and cost	Key resources	Key activities
Incentive 1	1.11	x						
Incentive 2	2.1		x					
Incentive 3	2.2		x					
Incentive 4	2.3		x					

Source: The authors

In the first column of Table 3 are the proposed current (period before 2023) and new incentives (period after 2023-2027) within the business models. The second column (Category of incentives) is the link between Table 2 and Table 3. Here, each of the proposed incentives in the first column should be referred to the category of incentives in Table 2. After identifying the relation between the incentives and the five building blocks of the BMC (which are already given in Table 2), the gaps will be revealed. Gaps are those building blocks which are **not covered** by the current incentives.

The next step is proposing new incentives, that are within the category of incentives in Table 2, and which will fill the missing building blocks. Columns 2 and 3 represent the period in which the incentive has been introduced.

Each partner identified the potential incentives corresponding to their business model. The NOVASOIL partners organized focus group which includes relevant stakeholders. In this format it was discussed and proposed the new incentives based on stakeholder's feedback. When discussing the new incentives, if their number is more than three, it was necessary to make a **ranking** of the incentives in order to select **only the most important three**. Each one of the participants voted three times for the proposed new incentives, and those three with the highest count was selected. The identified new incentives that filling the gaps in the five building blocks is used for the assessment in the second step of the analysis.

2.2. Multicriteria analysis - BOCR

2.2.1. Theoretical background on MCA – ANP/AHP methodology

The analytic hierarchy process (AHP) and the analytic network process (ANP) were introduced by Thomas Saaty (Saaty, 1997, 1980, 2000, 2001, 2005). AHP uses relativity in measuring both tangible and intangible criteria. It allows us to construct hierarchies with several levels including criteria that expands in lower and lower levels, until it reaches the sub-criteria (a top-down approach). According to Saaty (2006) the ANP is “a generalization of the AHP, with the basic structure is an influence network of clusters and nodes contained within the clusters”. This approach enables us to connect one criteria/sub-criteria from a cluster to another cluster and to take into consideration its influence. This is the reason for this approach to be named “network” because it reveals the interdependencies within the elements of the network.

One reason of substituting AHP with ANP is that certain research problems pose the need of involving the interdependence between clusters (both elements in the same cluster or another cluster), where the hierarchy is a “linear top down structure” (Saaty and Vargas, 2006). AHP method has been criticized by some researchers regarding the rank reversal which doesn't correspond to the multi-attribute utility theory (Leung and Cao, 2001). Therefore, the later proposal of the ANP as an extension of AHP takes into consideration the dependencies between the elements in the clusters.

ANP being an extension to the AHP is perceived as a tool for more complex problems where we seek to reveal the interconnections within the elements. Saaty (2005) suggests that when there is an independence between the elements in the hierarchy we should use AHP. In contrast, the ANP was proposed as a solution to address the issue of dependence among alternatives or criteria (Saaty, 2005).

Both AHP and ANP can be used as methods to prioritize one alternative over the others based on judgment of stakeholders, where the final goal is to choose the most appropriate one. Using BOCR analysis with both AHP and ANP models has been used as a valuable method in many research areas, including evaluation of product design (Chan et. al, 2013), municipal solid

waste management (Contreras et al., 2008, Brent, Rogers, Ramabitsa-Siimane, & Rohwer, 2007), modelling green initiatives (Sarmiento and Vargas-Berrones, 2018, Guo, Zhou, Li, & Xie, 2015), green energy production (Hussain et al., 2018), transportation (Bottero et al., 2011), and others.

With regards to studies in the agricultural field, BOCR-ANP has been used to assess financial tools for inclusion of farmers (Megantara and Priantina, 2020), choosing between the most sustainable crop production (Strada, 2009), sustainable floriculture (Çürük and Alptekin, 2022), agroforestry (Lovric et al., 2018), and others.

In connection with soil problems research is relatively scarce at the moment. Several studies have adopted ANP method relating to soil erosion. Nekhay et al. (2009) apply ANP method to evaluate soil erosion risks. Another study from 2018 (Sajedi-Hosseini et al., 2018) used Fuzzy Analytical Network Process (FANP) which allows not only to reveal interdependencies but direct and indirect relationships. This study is the first to apply FANP in soil erosion studies.

An interesting study compares the use of AHP and ANP with regards to ecosystem services from farming area (Jorge-Garcia and Estruch-Guitart). One of the conclusions is that compared with AHP, which does not consider relationships between elements, ANP is more efficient method when analyzing intangible assists, as it is the case with different ecosystem services.

The usefulness of BOCR-ANP method is that it deals with multi-criteria problems, especially when monetary calculations are difficult or not applicable. When we work with qualitative data the use of criteria to evaluate more than one competing alternatives is required. Using this method, we are able to determine what is the relative importance of the criteria we have chosen by using pairwise comparisons. The decision to adopt a soil health incentive has on hand ecological, economic and social considerations, but on the other hand all of these should be considered through the complexities of the BOCR sub-network.

Decision-making often faces complexity in choosing the most appropriate management option no matter the area of research field. Economic outcome is not the only factor which is measured when choosing the best option. It is certainly the easily computable in quantitative aspect, however qualitative criteria should be also taken into consideration. The BOCR tool is a multiple criteria decision-making method (MCDM) – its core idea is to help researchers in solving multi-attribute problems. In its essence, the BOCR method is using ANP (analytic network process)/AHP (analytic hierarchy process) in comparing several alternatives within four separate hierarchies: Benefits hierarchy (B), and similar Opportunities hierarchy (O), Costs hierarchy (C) and Risk hierarchy (R), in order to solve complex decision-making problems.

When performing ANP method it is important to define what is the main objective (goal) and then which are the clusters that influence the decision on what alternative to choose. The research problem that we have is structured

into a network of four blocks – benefits, opportunities, costs and risks. This is basically the main structure of the model. After that, the pairwise comparison takes place. Here we have two levels – the clusters and the nodes. Finally, we use Saaty’s 9-point scale to compare elements in each level. With the benefits and opportunities sub-network we ask the question “what presents the greater benefit/opportunity” and with the costs and risks – “what represent the highest cost or risk”.

In our study, the use of BOCR – ANP provides us with a more structural approach which enable us to prioritize new incentives for improving soil health business models, considering the respective benefits, opportunities, costs, and risks.

2.2.2. BOCR framework for analysing new incentives in NOVASOIL case studies

In the following methodology, it will be outlined the structure of the BOCR analysis for the purposes of analyzing the impact of the elements on the new incentives and to rank the importance of the new incentives for soil health business models. Figure 1 shows the general structure of the BOCR analysis. At the top is the goal of the analysis: Assessing new incentives and finding their importance for soil health business model development. At the next stage, the four blocks are shown: *Benefits, Opportunities, Costs, Risks*. Each of the four blocks represents a separate ANP network that is estimated independently. In order to unify the analysis of the four networks, control criteria are chosen that are the same for each of the blocks. These control criteria are: *Economic, Social, Technological and Political*. The result of the assessment of the four networks associated with the individual BOCR blocks is a ranking of the incentives within each network. The final stage of the analysis is the weighting of the four blocks and results from them. The weighting is done using the strategic criteria.

Figure 1. Structure of the BOCR analysis

Detailed and summarized structure of the BOCR analysis and elements used in the model are described and shown in table 4. According to the methodology in each case study are evaluated 2 or 3 new incentives which are placed on the top of the table. Additionally, (at the bottom of the table 4) for each case study are selected 3 or 4 (out of 10 CAP objectives) strategic criteria.

Table 4 Contain of the BOCR analysis

Alternatives	New incentive 1 New incentive 2 New incentive 3		
BOCR	Control criteria	Clusters	Elements/nodes in the cluster
Benefits	Economic	Market linkages	Producing safe food, GAPs, GMPs, Long chain
		Cost saving	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Technological	Resources	Knowledge of latest technologies,

			Immediately available
	Social	Contribution across local and national communities	Informational campaigns, Knowledge hubs
	Political	Innovative financing	Better access to finance, Soil health financial measures, Improvement productivity, Efficiency improvement
Opportunities	Economic	Market linkages	Long term results in food security, Food demand
		Cost saving	Long term return, Initial costs, Sustainable crop production
	Technological	Soil restoration	Fertilization, Soil remediation, Sustainable soil management
	Social	Sustainable soil use	Climate change, Biodiversity preservation, Soil quality, Regulation of water cycle
Costs	Economic	Market linkages	Developing nature-positive production, Costs for information campaigns, Increased marketing expenditure
		Cost saving	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Technological	Investments in better technologies for healthy soil	Precision agriculture, Cover crops, Crop rotation,

			Increasing short term investments,
Risks	Economic	Market linkages	Barriers to change practices for health practices, Perceived risk, Access to finance, Initial costs
		Cost saving	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations, Increasing variable costs, Increasing initial costs
	Political	Innovative financing	Decreasing liquidity, Increasing the long term assets, Income decrease
Strategic criteria	Strategic criteria 1 Strategic criteria 2 Strategic criteria 3		

2.3.1 Phases of the BOCR analysis

BOCR analysis evaluates the new incentives on four phases presented in figure 2.

BOCR	Control criteria	Clusters	Elements	Strategic criteria	Incentives
Benefits	Economic	Market linkages	Ex. Producing safe food	← Phase 1 →	→
		Cost saving	Ex. Gross margin increasing		
	Technological	Resources	Ex. Knowledge of latest technologies	← Phase 2 →	→
	Social	Contribution across loc. and nat. commun.	Ex. Knowledge hubs		
Political	Innovative financing	Ex. Better access to finance		← Phase 4 →	
Opportunities	Economic	Market linkages	Ex. Food demand	Strategic criteria 1 Strategic criteria 2 Strategic criteria 3	Incentive 1 Incentive 2 Incentive 3
		Cost saving	Ex. Sustainable crop production		
	Technological	Sustainable soil health use	Ex. Fertilization		
	Social	Soil restoration	Ex. Climate change		
Costs	Economic	Market linkages	Ex. Developing nature-positive production		
		Cost saving	Ex. Gross margin increasing		
	Technological	Investments in better technologies for healthy soil	Ex. Precision agriculture		
Risk	Economic	Market linkages	Ex. Perceived risk		
		Cost saving	Ex. Increasing variable costs		
	Political	Innovative financing	Ex. Decreasing liquidity		

Figure 2 Phases of BOCR analysis

Phase 1: Evaluation of the influence of the elements on the new incentives.

Phase 1 is the lowest level of evaluation. At this level, the influence of the individual elements on the new incentives is determined. The evaluation is done by comparing each pair of incentives against each element. The scores are then combined to rank the new incentives.

Phase 2: Influence of control criteria on the new incentives

Phase 2 makes a ranking of the incentives according the control criteria, after weights of the different clusters are made.

Phase 3: Determining the control criteria weights and their influence on new incentives

Phase 3 determines the weights of the control criteria and prioritizes the new incentives for each of the benefits, opportunities, costs and risks networks separately.

Phase 4: Strategic criteria weighting and final result

Phase 4 uses the strategic criteria for weighing the blocks benefits, opportunities, costs and risks and outputting the final ranking of the new incentives.

2.3.2 Structure of the network under Benefits block

Economic, Technological, Social and Political control criteria were identified for the Benefits block of the model. The goal of the network under Benefits is assessing new incentives and finding their importance for soil health business model.

Figure 3. BOCR structure under Benefits block

Under **Economic** benefits, there are two clusters: *Market linkages* and *Cost saving*. These clusters include different elements (nodes):

The **Cost saving** cluster consist from *Gross margin increasing*, *Higher retail price*, *Better product quality*, *Decreasing variable costs*.

The **Market linkages** cluster consist of *Producing safe food*, *GAPs*, *GMPs*, *Long chain*.

Within the BOCR, it is important to set the direction of the relationship. These connections can be seen in the figure.

Figure 4. Structure and direction under Benefits block, Economic control criteria

Under **Technological** benefits, there is one cluster: *Resources*.

The **Resources** cluster consist from *Knowledge of latest technologies* and *Immediately available elements*.

Figure 5. Structure and direction under Benefits block, Technological control criteria

Under **Social** benefits, there is one cluster: *Contribution across local and national communities*.

The **Contribution across local and national communities** cluster consist from: *Informational campaigns* and *Knowledge hubs* elements.

Figure 6. Structure and direction under Benefits block, Social control criteria

Under **Political** benefits, there is one cluster: *Innovative financing* (fig 7).

The **Innovative financing** cluster consist from *Better access to finance*, *Soil health financial measures*, *Improvement productivity* and *Efficiency improvement* elements.

Figure 7. Structure and direction under Benefits block, Political control criteria

2.3.3 Structure of the network under Opportunities block

Economic, Technological and Social control criteria were identified for the Opportunities block of the model. The goal of the network under Opportunities is assessing new incentives and finding their importance for soil health business model.

Figure 8. BOCR structure under Opportunities block

Under **Economic** opportunities, there are two clusters: *Market linkages* and *Cost saving*. These clusters include different elements (nodes):

The **Cost saving** cluster consist from *Initial costs*, *Long term return* and *Sustainable crop production*.

The **Market linkages** cluster consist from *Food demand* and *Long term results in food security*.

The direction of the relationship can be seen on the figure.

Figure 9. Structure and direction under Opportunities block, Economic control criteria

Under **Social** opportunities, there is one cluster: *Sustainable soil use*.

The **Sustainable soil use** cluster consist from: *Climate change*, *Biodiversity preservation*, *Soil quality* and *Regulation of water cycle*.

Figure 10. Structure and direction under Opportunities block, Social control criteria

Under **Technological** opportunities, there is one cluster: *Soil restoration*.

The **Soil restoration** cluster consist from: *Fertilization*, *Soil remediation* and *Sustainable soil management*.

Figure 11. Structure and direction under Opportunities block, Technological control criteria

2.3.4 Structure of the network under Costs block

Economic and Technological control criteria were identified for the Costs block of the model. The goal of the network under Costs is assessing new incentives and finding their importance for soil health business model.

Figure 12. BOCR structure under Costs block

Under **Economic** costs, there are two clusters: *Market linkages* and *Cost saving*. These clusters include different elements (nodes):

The **Cost saving** cluster consist from *Gross margin increasing*, *Higher retail price*, *Better product quality* and *Decreasing variable costs*.

The **Market linkages** cluster consist from *Developing nature-positive production*, *Costs for information campaigns* and *Increased marketing expenditure*.

The direction of the relationship can be seen on the figure.

Figure 13. Structure and direction under Costs block, Economic control criteria

Under **Technological** opportunities, there is one cluster: *Investments in better technologies for healthy soil*.

The **Investments in better technologies for healthy soil** cluster consist from: *Precision agriculture, Cover crops, Crop rotation and Increasing short term investments.*

Figure 14. Structure and direction under Costs block, Technological control criteria

2.3.5 Structure of the network under Risks block

Economic and Political control criteria were identified for the Risks block of the model. The goal of the network under Risks is assessing new incentives and finding their importance for soil health business model.

Figure 15. BOCR structure under Risks block

Under **Economic** risks, there are two clusters: *Market linkages* and *Cost saving*. These clusters include different elements (nodes):

The **Cost saving** cluster consist from *Increasing expenditures for soil health operations, Increasing variable costs and Increasing initial costs.*

The **Market linkages** cluster consist from *Barriers to change practices for health practices, Perceived risk, Access to finance and Initial costs.*

The direction of the relationships is visualized on the figure.

Figure 16. Structure and direction under Risks block, Economic control criteria

Under **Political** risks, there is one cluster: *Innovative financing*.

The **Innovative financing** cluster consist from *Decreasing liquidity*, *Increasing the long term assets*, *Income decrease*.

Figure 17. Structure and direction under Risks block, Political control criteria

2.3.6 Strategic criteria

Each partner and each case study, depending on the business model orientation, define the strategic criteria. The strategic criteria corresponds to the 10 CAP objectives - 1. To ensure a fair income for farmers; 2. To increase competitiveness; 3. To improve the position of farmers in the food chain; 4. Climate change action; 5. Environmental care; 6. To preserve landscapes and biodiversity; 7. To support generational renewal; 8. Vibrant rural areas; 9. To protect food and health quality; 10. Fostering knowledge and innovation (the 10 objectives that underpin CAP 2023-2027). For every case study business model, the number of strategic criteria could be from 1 to 10.

3. Analysis of the new incentives by case study

3.1 Spain: Integrated production case study

The first case study of Spain is related with the *Integrated production and Value chain* business model. With the integrated production program, sustainable agriculture in Andalusia has been promoted. The statistics offered by the regional government show that participation in this measure has been increasing over the past few years. Specifically, in the olive grove sector, there is a lot of competition. Recent research works highlighted the increase of soil organic carbon due to crop/land management. From the point of view of the promoted business models in WP 2 this model is Value chain.

The new incentives are:

1. Green bonds;
2. Local funds;
3. Conservation concessions.

Phase 1: Evaluation of the influence of the elements on the new incentives

The analysis will begin with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Cost saving*. Based on the stakeholder ratings, *Better Product Production* holds the highest importance for *Green Bonds* with a significant score of 0.7695, indicating a strong emphasis on product quality within this incentive. *Decreasing Variable Costs* prioritizes *Conservation Concessions* with a score of 0.4545, suggesting a focus on cost reduction as a priority within this incentive. *Increasing Gross Margin* ranks highest the *Local Funds* with a score of 0.6337, indicating a focus on maximizing profit margins through this particular incentive. *Higher Retail Price*, equally influences across all incentives, maintains a consistent consideration with a score of 0.3333, indicating a shared approach to retail pricing regardless of the incentive.

Table 5 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1.Green bonds	0.7695	0.1985	0.1919	0.3333

2.Local funds	0.1040	0.3468	0.6337	0.3333
3.Conservation concessions	0.1265	0.4545	0.1743	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

The analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Market linkages*. For the element *GAPs*, the highest influence is observed in the context of the incentives *Green bonds* and *Conservation concessions*, scoring 0.4737. Similarly, for the element *GMPs* (Good Manufacturing Practices), the incentives *Ass Green bonds* and *Conservation concessions* exhibits the highest priority, scoring 0.4737. *Long Chain* sees its highest importance in *Local funds*, with a score of 0.8182. Finally, *Producing Safe Food* demonstrates the highest influence once again in *Green bonds* and *Conservation concessions*, scoring 0.4737. This consistent trend underscores the significant impact of assistance provided under European quality schemes across various elements of food production.

Table 6 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	GAPs	GMPs	Long chain	Producing safe food
1.Green bonds	0.4737	0.4737	0.0909	0.4737
2.Local funds	0.0526	0.0526	0.8182	0.0526
3.Conservation concessions	0.4737	0.4737	0.0909	0.4737

Source: Own calculations

For the control cluster *Political* in *Benefits* the influence of the elements *Better access to finance*, *Efficiency improvement* and *Soil health financial measures* has highest influence over the incentives *Green bonds* and *Conservation concessions* with a weight of 0.4737. The element *Improvement productivity* has highest importance for *Conservation concessions* with 0.7108.

Table 7 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Political

Incentives/elements	Better access to finance	Efficiency improvement	Improvement productivity	Soil health financial measures
1.Green bonds	0.4737	0.4737	0.2431	0.4737
2.Local funds	0.0526	0.0526	0.0462	0.0526
3.Conservation concessions	0.4737	0.4737	0.7108	0.4737

Source: Own calculations

Regarding the *Social* control criteria in *Benefits* the highest importance is the same for each element. For *Informational campaigns*, the highest influence

is observed over the incentive Conservation concessions, scoring 0.7660. *Knowledge hubs* element also prioritizes the incentive Conservation concessions with a score of 0.7511.

Table 8 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Social

Incentives/elements	Informational campaigns	Knowledge hubs
1.Green bonds	0.1915	0.2053
2.Local funds	0.0425	0.0436
3.Conservation concessions	0.7660	0.7511

Source: Own calculations

The analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits, Technological* control criteria. The importance of *Knowledge of latest technologies* element is highest for the incentive Green bonds with 0.4579. The incentive Conservation concessions have highest score according *Immediately available* element with score 0.4579.

Table 9 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Technological

Incentives/elements	Knowledge of latest technologies	Immediately available
1.Green bonds	0.4579	0.4161
2.Local funds	0.1260	0.1260
3.Conservation concessions	0.4161	0.4579

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic* control criteria, *Cost saving* cluster the *Initial costs* element have highest influence over incentive *Local funds*, scoring 0.6223. Similarly, for *Long term return*, *Conservation concessions* exhibits the highest importance, scoring 0.7903. Lastly, *Sustainable crop production* sees its highest priority in Incentives *Green bonds and Conservation concessions*, with a score of 0.4737.

Table 10 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Initial costs	Long term return	Sustainable crop production
1.Green bonds	0.2460	0.1377	0.4737
2.Local funds	0.6223	0.0720	0.0526
3.Conservation concessions	0.1307	0.7903	0.4737

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages*, *Food demand* element has the highest influence over *Green bonds and Conservation concessions* with a result of 0.4737. The same incentives are prioritized by element *Long term results in food security* with 0.4737.

Table 11 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Food demand	Long term results in food security
1.Green bonds	0.4737	0.4737
2.Local funds	0.0526	0.0526
3.Conservation concessions	0.4737	0.4737

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Opportunities*, *Fertilization* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.7785 over the incentive *Conservation concessions*. The same result is achieved by *Soil remediation and Sustainable soil management*.

Table 12 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Technological

Incentives/elements	Fertilization	Soil remediation	Sustainable soil management
1.Green bonds	0.1799	0.1799	0.1799
2.Local funds	0.0416	0.0416	0.0416
3.Conservation concessions	0.7785	0.7785	0.7785

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Social* control criteria in *Opportunities*, the highest priorities of the elements is over *Conservation concessions*. *Biodiversity preservation* most significantly impacts the incentive *Conservation concessions*, with a score of 0.7240. *Climate change, Regulation of the water and Soil quality* has highest influence on *Conservation concessions*, with same score of 0.7331.

Table 13 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Social

Incentives/elements	Biodiversity preservation	Climate change	Regulation of water cycle	Soil quality
1.Green bonds	0.2281	0.2220	0.2220	0.2220
2.Local funds	0.0479	0.0448	0.0448	0.0448
3.Conservation concessions	0.7240	0.7331	0.7331	0.7331

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Costs*, *Better product quality* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.4844 over the incentive *Green bonds*. The element *Decreasing variable costs* prioritizes *Green bonds* with a score of 0.4991. *Gross margin increasing* moderately influences *Green bonds* schemes with a score of 0.4434. Finally, *Higher retail price* influences equally all incentives.

Table 14 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1.Green bonds	0.4844	0.4991	0.4434	0.3333
2.Local funds	0.0924	0.1048	0.1692	0.3333
3.Conservation concessions	0.4232	0.3961	0.3874	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Costs*, the element *Costs for information campaigns* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.7331 over the incentive *Conservation concessions*. The element *Developing nature-positive production* has high importance over the same incentive with a score of 0.7331. *Increased expenditure for marketing* gives equal score to all incentives.

Table 15 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Costs for information campaigns	Developing nature-positive production	Increased expenditure for marketing
1.Green bonds	0.2220	0.2220	0.3333
2.Local funds	0.0448	0.0448	0.3333
3.Conservation concessions	0.7331	0.7331	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Costs* the *Cover crop* element influences in highest degree the incentive *Conservation concessions* with a score of 0.7785. The incentive is also highly influenced by *Increasing short-term investments* with a score of 0.7917 and *Crop rotation* with a score of 0.7331. The element *Precision agriculture* influences both *Green bonds* and *Conservation concessions* with a score of 0.4737.

Table 16 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Technological

Incentives/elements	Cover crops	Crop rotation	Increasing short-term investments	Precision agriculture
1.Green bonds	0.1799	0.2220	0.1599	0.4737
2.Local funds	0.0416	0.0448	0.0484	0.0526
3.Conservation concessions	0.7785	0.7331	0.7917	0.4737

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* the element *Increasing expenditures for soil health operations* prioritizes both incentives *Green bonds* and *Conservation concessions* with a score of 0.4737. The element *Increasing initial costs* influences *Local funds* incentive with a score of 0.4901. The last element *Increasing variable costs* confirms the importance of the *Local funds* incentive with a score of 0.8182.

Table 17 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations	Increasing initial costs	Increasing variable costs
1.Green bonds	0.4737	0.0592	0.0909
2.Local funds	0.0526	0.4901	0.8182
3.Conservation concessions	0.4737	0.4507	0.0909

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* the element *Access to finance* influences the incentive *Green bonds* with a score of 0.7493. The highest importance of the element *Barriers to change practices for health practices* is over the incentives *Green bonds* and *Conservation concessions* with 0.4737. The elements *Perceived risk* and *Initial costs* prioritizes the incentive *Local funds* with a score respectively 0.8182 and 0.4791.

Table 18 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Access to finance	Barriers to change practices for health practices	Initial costs	Perceived risk
1.Green bonds	0.7493	0.4737	0.0626	0.0909
2.Local funds	0.0524	0.0526	0.4791	0.8182
3.Conservation concessions	0.1982	0.4737	0.4582	0.0909

Source: Own calculations

During the analysis of *Political control* criteria in *Risks* it is estimated that all elements *Decreasing liquidity*, *Income decrease* and *Increasing the long term assets* have the same influence of 0.3333 to all the incentives.

Table 19 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Political

Incentives/elements	Decreasing liquidity	Income decrease	Increasing the long term assets
1.Green bonds	0.3333	0.3333	0.3333

2.Local funds	0.3333	0.3333	0.3333
3.Conservation concessions	0.3333	0.3333	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

Phase 2: Influence of control criteria on the new incentives

The influence of the clusters in Economic control criteria is estimated relatively by comparing them. Their weights of Market linkages and Cost savings under *Benefits* are assigned a weight of 0.2000 for *Market linkages* and 0.8000 for *Cost saving*. *Opportunities* receive same weights Costs are weighted at 0.8571 for *Market linkages* and 0.1429 for *Cost saving*. Risks hold a weight of 0.2000 for *Market linkages* and 0.8000 for *Cost saving*.

Table 20 Relative weights of the clusters

Control criteria	Clusters	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risks
Economic	Market linkages	0.2000	0.2000	0.8571	0.2000
	Cost saving	0.8000	0.8000	0.1429	0.8000

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Benefits* the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Green bonds* which is assigned weight of 0.3743. The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is *Conservation concessions*, which is assigned a high score of 0.5330. The highest priority under the *Social* control criteria is *Conservation concessions*, with a score of 0.7585. The highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria are both *Green bonds* and *Conservation concessions*, with a moderate weight of 0.4370.

Table 21 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under benefits

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political	Social	Technological
1.Green bonds	0.3743	0.4160	0.1984	0.4370
2.Local funds	0.3324	0.0510	0.0431	0.1260
3.Conservation concessions	0.2934	0.5330	0.7585	0.4370

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Opportunities*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Conservation concessions*, which is assigned a weight of 0.4666. The highest priority under the *Social* control criteria is again *Conservation concessions*, with a weight of 0.7309. Lastly, the highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is also *Conservation concessions*, with a weight of 0.7785.

Table 22 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under opportunities

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Social	Technological
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1.Green bonds	0.3236	0.2235	0.1799
2.Local funds	0.2097	0.0456	0.0416
3.Conservation concessions	0.4666	0.7309	0.7785

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Costs*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Conservation concessions*, which is assigned a weight of 0.5692. The highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is *Conservation concessions*, with a weight of 0.6943.

Table 23 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under costs

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Technological
1.Green bonds	0.2850	0.2589
2.Local funds	0.1458	0.0469
3.Conservation concessions	0.5692	0.6943

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Risks*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Local funds*, which is assigned a weight of 0.4330. The priority under the *Political* control criteria is equal for all incentives.

Table 24 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under risks

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political
1.Green bonds	0.2352	0.3333
2.Local funds	0.4330	0.3333
3.Conservation concessions	0.3318	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

Phase 3: Determining the control criteria weights and their influence on new incentives

Next table represents the relative weights of control criteria, where the *Social* considerations hold the highest priority across *Benefits* and *Opportunities*, *Economic* – across *Costs* and *Risks*.

Table 25 Relative weights of the control criteria

Control criteria	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
Economic	0.0833	0.1673	0.8889	0.8750
Technological	0.0833	0.0457	0.1111	-
Social	0.7500	0.7870	-	-
Political	0.0833	-	-	0.1250

Source: Own calculations

Overall priorities represents the priorities under *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs* and *Risks* after considering the relative weights of the control criteria. *Benefits*,

Opportunities, Costs prioritize the incentive *Conservation concessions* with ratings between 0.5808 and 0.6693. *Risk* prioritizes the incentive *Local funds* with 0.4174.

Table 26 Overall priorities

Incentives/blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
1.Green bonds	0.2745	0.2458	0.2826	0.2505
2.Local funds	0.0954	0.0848	0.1366	0.4174
3.Conservation concessions	0.6301	0.6693	0.5808	0.3320

Source: Own calculations

Phase 4: Strategic criteria weighting and final result

The next step is to estimate the Strategic criteria influence over the four categories. This table presents a qualitative assessment of the three different strategic criteria – *Climate change action, Environmental care, To preserve landscapes and biodiversity* over the categories *Benefits, Opportunities, Costs, and Risks*.

Table 27 Defining rating scale for strategic criteria

Blocks/strategic criteria	Climate change action	Environmental care	Preserve landscapes and biodiversity
Benefits	Excellent	Above Average	Average
Opportunities	Above Average	Above Average	Above Average
Costs	Average	Below Average	Below Average
Risks	Below Average	Below Average	Average

Source: Own calculations

Based on the qualitative assessment the relative weights of the four blocks of the model are derived. *Benefits* seems to have highest priority, followed by *Opportunities, Costs* and *Risks*.

Table 28 Ratings for strategic criteria and BOCR priorities

	TOTALS	PRIORITIES	Climate change action	Environmental care	Preserve landscapes and biodiversity
1.Benefits	0.8713	0.4478	1.0000	0.6643	0.3061
2.Opportunities	0.6643	0.3414	0.6643	0.6643	0.6643
3.Costs	0.2612	0.1342	0.3061	0.1263	0.1263
4.Risks	0.1488	0.0765	0.1263	0.1263	0.3061

Source: Own calculations

The Overall outcome table presents priorities assigned to three different incentives. *Conservation concessions* stand out with a significantly higher

priority score of 0.7385, suggesting a strong emphasis on this incentive. *Green bonds* also hold some importance but to a lesser extent, with a priority score of 0.2593. Conversely, *Local funds* rank lowest in priority, with a minimal score of 0.0022, indicating relatively less significance compared to the other incentives.

Table 29 Overall outcome of BOCR

Incentives	Priorities
1.Green bonds	0.2593
2.Local funds	0.0022
3.Conservation concessions	0.7385

Source: Own calculations

3.2 Spain: Organic wine in Rueda, Spain

The second case study in Spain is a *value-chain related contract solution*, where only grapes produced ecologically are bought by the winery Herederos del Marqués de Riscal, S.A (from now on, Riscal), to produce two selected varieties: MARQUÉS DE RISCAL ORGANIC and MARQUÉS DE RISCAL SAUVIGNON BLANC ORGANIC. In the Rueda case study, grape producers are not associated, however, they are integrated into the value chain by complying to the winery standards and have periodic controls on quality and residues, and have a strict protocol of organic production of high standards. From the point of view of the promoted business models in WP 2 this model is Value chain.

The new incentives are:

1. Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods;
2. Payment in order to implement cover crops.

Phase 1: Evaluation of the influence of the elements on the new incentives

The analysis begins with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Cost saving*. According to the stakeholders ratings the importance of *Better product production*, *Decreasing variable cost* and *Increasing gross margin* is very high for the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with score of 0.8000. The priority of *Higher retail prices* varies for the incentive *Payment in order to implement cover crops* is 0.8750.

Table 30 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8000	0.8000	0.8000	0.8750

2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.2000	0.2000	0.2000	0.1250
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Source: Own calculations

The analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Market linkages*. For the elements *GAPs* and *Producing Safe Food*, the highest influence is observed in the context of the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, scoring 0.8571. Similarly, for the elements *GMPs* (Good Manufacturing Practices) and *Long Chain*, the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, gets score of 0.8000.

Table 31 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	GAPs	GMPs	Long chain	Producing safe food
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8571	0.8000	0.8000	0.8571
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.1430	0.2000	0.2000	0.1430

Source: Own calculations

For the control cluster *Political* in *Benefits* the influence of the elements over the incentives is in the table below. For the elements *Better access to finance* and *Efficiency improvement* the highest influence is observed in the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with score respectively 0.8750 and 0.7500. The elements *Improvement productivity* and *Soil health financial measures* prioritize the incentive *Payment in order to implement cover crops* with respectively 0.7500 and 0.8333.

Table 32 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Political

Incentives/elements	Better access to finance	Efficiency improvement	Improvement productivity	Soil health financial measures
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8750	0.7500	0.2500	0.1667
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.1250	0.2500	0.7500	0.8333

Source: Own calculations

Regarding the *Social* control criteria in *Benefits* the highest importance for *Informational campaigns* is observed over the incentive *Payment to adopt*

and maintain organic production practices and methods, scoring 0.8750. Knowledge hubs element prioritizes both incentives equally.

Table 33 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Social

Incentives/elements	Informational campaigns	Knowledge hubs
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8750	0.5000
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.1250	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

The analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits, Technological* control criteria. The importance of *Knowledge of latest technologies* element is highest for the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with 0.8000. Both incentives *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* and *Payment in order to implement cover crops* have equal score according *Immediately available* element with 0.5000.

Table 34 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Technological

Incentives/elements	Knowledge of latest technologies	Immediately available
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8000	0.5000
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.2000	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic* control criteria, *cost saving* cluster the *Initial costs* element have highest influence over incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, scoring 0.8750. *Long term return* exhibits the highest importance for both incentives, scoring 0.5000. The same is for element *Sustainable crop production* that prioritize equally both incentives.

Table 35 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Initial costs	Long term return	Sustainable crop production
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8750	0.5000	0.5000
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.1250	0.5000	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages, Food demand* element has the highest influence over *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with a result of 0.8750. The element *Long term results in food security* has equal importance on both incentives.

Table 36 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Food demand	Long term results in food security
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8750	0.5000
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.1250	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Opportunities, Fertilization* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.8333 over the incentive *Payment in order to implement cover crops*. The same incentive is prioritized by *Soil remediation* with 0.7500. *Sustainable soil management* also shows notable influence with a score of 0.8750 over the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*.

Table 37 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Technological

Incentives/elements	Fertilization	Soil remediation	Sustainable soil management
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.1667	0.2500	0.8750
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.8333	0.7500	0.1250

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Social* control criteria in *Opportunities*, the highest priorities of the elements is over different incentives. *Biodiversity preservation* most significantly impacts the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a score of 0.8571. *Climate change* influences both incentives equally. *Regulation of the water cycle* sees its greatest influence over *Payment in order to implement cover crops*, with score of 0.8571. Finally, *Soil quality* has highest influence on *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a score of 0.8750.

Table 38 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Social

Incentives/elements	Biodiversity preservation	Climate change	Regulation of water cycle	Soil quality
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8571	0.5000	0.1429	0.8750
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.1429	0.5000	0.8571	0.1250

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Costs*, *Better product quality* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.8750 over the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*. The elements *Decreasing variable costs* and *Gross margin increasing* prioritize both incentives. Finally, *Higher retail price* influences the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with a score of 0.8000.

Table 39 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8750	0.5000	0.5000	0.8000
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.1250	0.5000	0.5000	0.2000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Costs*, the element *Costs for information campaigns* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.8000 over the incentive *Payment in order to implement cover crops*. The element *Developing nature-positive production* has high importance over the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with a score of 0.8571. The element *Increased expenditure for marketing* influences the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with a score of 0.8333.

Table 40 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Costs for information campaigns	Developing nature-positive production	Increased expenditure for marketing
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic	0.2000	0.8571	0.8333

production practices and methods			
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.8000	0.1429	0.1667

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Costs* the *Cover crops* element influences in highest degree the incentive *Payment in order to implement cover crops* with a score of 0.8571. The elements *Crop rotation* and *Precision agriculture* equally influence both incentives. *Increasing short-term investments* element prioritizes *Payment in order to implement cover crops* with a score of 0.8000.

Table 41 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Technological

Incentives/elements	Cover crops	Crop rotation	Increasing short-term investments	Precision agriculture
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.1429	0.5000	0.8000	0.5000
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.8571	0.5000	0.2000	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* all elements - *Increasing expenditures for soil health operations*, *Increasing initial costs* and *Increasing variable costs* prioritizes both incentives equally.

Table 42 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations	Increasing initial costs	Increasing variable costs
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* the element *Access to finance* influences the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with a score of 0.8750. The elements *Barriers to change practices for health practices*, *Perceived risk*

and *Initial costs* prioritizes the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with a score 0.8000.

Table 43 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Access to finance	Barriers to change practices for health practices	Initial costs	Perceived risk
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8750	0.8000	0.8000	0.8000
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.1250	0.2000	0.2000	0.2000

Source: Own calculations

During the analysis of *Political control* criteria in *Risks* it is estimated that the element *Decreasing liquidity* has equal influence over both incentives. The highest importance of the element *Income decrease* is over the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with a score of 0.8000. The element *Increasing the long term assets* has the same influence of 0.8000 to *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*.

Table 44 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Political

Incentives/elements	Decreasing liquidity	Income decrease	Increasing the long term assets
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.5000	0.8000	0.8000
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.5000	0.2000	0.2000

Source: Own calculations

Phase 2: Influence of control criteria on the new incentives

The influence of the clusters in Economic control criteria is estimated relatively by comparing them. Their weights of *Market linkages* and *Cost savings* under *Benefits* are assigned a weight of 0.8000 for *Market linkages* and 0.2000 for *Cost saving*. *Opportunities* receive 0,8571 for *Market linkages* and 0.1429 for *Cost saving*. For *Costs* and *Risks* blocks the results are the same with 0.8333 for *Market linkages* and 0.1666 for *Cost saving*.

Table 45 Relative weights of the clusters

Control criteria	Clusters	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risks

Economic	Market linkages	0.8000	0.8571	0.8333	0.8333
	Cost saving	0.2000	0.1429	0.1666	0.1666

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Benefits* the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* which is assigned a significant weight of 0.8266. The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, which is assigned a score of 0.5104. The highest priority under the *Social* control criteria is *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a score of 0.6875. The highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a weight of 0.6500.

Table 46 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under benefits

Incentives/Control criteria	Economic	Political	Social	Technological
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8266	0.5104	0.6875	0.6500
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.1734	0.4896	0.3125	0.3500

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Opportunities*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, which is assigned a weight of 0.6786. The highest priority under the *Social* control criteria is again *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a weight of 0.5938. Lastly, the highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is for *Payment in order to implement cover crops*, with a weight of 0.5694.

Table 47 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under opportunities

Incentives/Control criteria	Economic	Social	Technological
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.6786	0.5938	0.4306
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.3214	0.4063	0.5694

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Costs*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, which is assigned a weight of 0.6366. The

highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is *Payment in order to implement cover crops*, with a weight of 0.5893.

Table 48 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under costs

Incentives/Control criteria	Economic	Technological
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.6366	0.4107
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.3634	0.5893

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Risks*, the highest priority under the both control criteria is *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with weights respectively of 0.7656 and 0.7000.

Table 49 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under risks

Incentives/Control criteria	Economic	Political
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.7656	0.7000
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.2344	0.3000

Source: Own calculations

Phase 3: Determining the control criteria weights and their influence on new incentives

In the table below are the relative weights of control criteria, where *Economic* considerations hold the highest priority across *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs* and *Risks*, emphasizing its overarching importance.

Table 50 Relative weights of the control criteria

Control criteria/Blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
Economic	0.5379	0.4126	0.8571	0.8750
Technological	0.3139	0.2599	0.1429	
Social	0.0993	0.3275		
Political	0.0490			0.1250

Source: Own calculations

In the table below are the priorities under *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs* and *Risks* after considering the relative weights of the control criteria. All four categories prioritize the incentive *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*. *Benefits* influence is with rating 0.7278. Additionally, *Opportunities* contribute with a bit less – 0.5796. *Costs* also play a significant role, representing 0.6021 of the influence. *Risks* contributes 0.7568 to the overall influence.

Table 51 Overall priorities

Incentives/Blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.7278	0.5796	0.6021	0.7568
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.2722	0.4204	0.3879	0.2432

Source: Own calculations

Phase 4: Strategic criteria weighting and final result

The next step is to estimate the Strategic criteria influence over the four categories. This table presents a qualitative assessment of the three different strategic criteria – *Environmental care*, *To protect food and health quality* and *Fostering knowledge and innovation* over the categories Benefits, Opportunities, Costs, and Risks.

Table 52 Defining rating scale for strategic criteria

Blocks/Strategic criteria	Environmental care	To protect food and health quality	Fostering knowledge and innovation
Benefits	Above Average	Above Average	Above Average
Opportunities	Excellent	Above Average	Above Average
Costs	Average	Average	Above Average
Risks	Average	Above Average	Average

Source: Own calculations

Based on the qualitative assessment the relative weights of the four blocks of the model are derived. *Opportunities* seems to have highest priority, followed by *Benefits*, *Costs* and *Risks*.

Table 53 Ratings for strategic criteria and BOCR priorities

Blocks/Strategic criteria	TOTALS	PRIORITIES	Environmental care	To protect food and health quality	Fostering knowledge and innovation
Benefits	0.6643	0.2909	0.6643	0.6643	0.6643
Opportunities	0.9050	0.3964	1.0000	0.6643	0.6643
Costs	0.3296	0.1444	0.3061	0.3061	0.6643
Risks	0.3839	0.1681	0.3061	0.6643	0.3061

Source: Own calculations

The Overall outcome table presents priorities assigned to the two different incentives. *Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* stand out with a higher priority score of 0.6045, suggesting a

strong emphasis on this incentive. *Payment in order to implement cover crops* also hold some importance but to a lesser extent, with a priority score of 0.3954.

Table 54 Overall outcome of BOCR

Incentives	Priorities
1.Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.6045
2.Payment in order to implement cover crops	0.3954

Source: Own calculations

3.3 Bulgaria: Integrated production in the vineyards with vinery and rural tourism

The Bulgaria case study manages the viticultural potential of the country and exercises control over the rights for planting new vineyards, replanting and eradication of vineyards. The effective functioning of the system in recent years leads to the improvement and stabilization of the sector as a whole, increasing the quality and competitiveness of Bulgarian wines, both on the domestic and foreign markets. The aim of the Program for local traditional and regional traditional products for the period 2021-2023 is to value the potential of local traditional and regional traditional products in the wine sector and strengthen their relationship with communities in order to develop the local economy and agricultural sector. Local traditional and regional traditional products give Bulgarian citizens and guests of the country a variety of tastes, quality, touch with culture and traditions and life of the local economy and communities. From the point of view of the promoted business models in WP 2 this model is Value chain.

The new incentives are:

1. Raising awareness of regional products;
2. Encouraging the association of producers;
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes.

Phase 1: Evaluation of the influence of the elements on the new incentives

The analysis begins with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Cost saving*. The incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* was prioritized by the elements *Better product quality*, *Decreasing variable costs*, *Gross margin increasing*, *Higher retail price* with high influence (from 0.4000 to 0.6833).

Table 55 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.1168	0.2000	0.1047	0.0719
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.1998	0.4000	0.2582	0.2789
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.6833	0.4000	0.6369	0.6491

Source: Own calculations

The analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Market linkages*. For the element *GAPs*, the highest influence is observed in the context of the incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, scoring 0.5469. Similarly, for the element *GMPs* (Good Manufacturing Practices), the incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* exhibits the highest priority, scoring 0.7007. *Long Chain* also sees its highest importance in *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, with a score of 0.6927. Finally, *Producing Safe Food* demonstrates the highest influence once again in *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, scoring 0.7016.

Table 56 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Market linkages

	GAPs	GMPs	Long chain	Producing safe food
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.1085	0.0971	0.0872	0.0726
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.3445	0.2021	0.2199	0.2258
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.5469	0.7007	0.6927	0.7016

Source: Own calculations

For the control cluster *Political* in *Benefits* the influence of the elements over the incentives is in the table below. For the elements *Better access to finance*, *Efficiency improvement*, *Improvement productivity* the highest influence is consistently observed in the incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*. Specifically, weights of 0.5499 for *Better access to finance*, 0.6250 for

Efficiency improvement, 0.6337 for *Improvement productivity*. The element *Soil health financial measures* prioritizes the incentive *Encouraging the association of producers* with 0.4599.

Table 57 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Political

	Better access to finance	Efficiency improvement	Improvement productivity	Soil health financial measures
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.2098	0.1365	0.1743	0.2211
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.2402	0.2384	0.1919	0.4599
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.5499	0.6250	0.6337	0.3189

Source: Own calculations

Regarding the *Social control* criteria in *Benefits* the highest importance is the same for each element. For *Informational campaigns*, the highest influence is observed over the incentive *Raising awareness of regional products*, scoring 0.5936. *Knowledge hubs* element prioritizes the incentive *Raising awareness of regional products* with a score of 0.4125.

Table 58 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Social

	Informational campaigns	Knowledge hubs
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.5936	0.4125
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.2493	0.3274
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.1570	0.2599

Source: Own calculations

The analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits, Technological control* criteria. The importance of *Knowledge of latest technologies* element is highest for the incentive *Encouraging the association of producers* with 0.4125. Both incentives *Raising awareness of regional products* and *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* have highest score according *Immediately available* element with score 0.4285.

Table 59 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Technological

	Knowledge of latest technologies	Immediately available
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.2599	0.4285
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.4125	0.1428
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.3274	0.4285

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic* control criteria, *cost saving* cluster the *Initial costs* element have highest influence over incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, scoring 0.4933. Similarly, for *Long term return*, *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* exhibits the highest importance, scoring 0.5469. Lastly, *Sustainable crop production* also sees its highest priority in *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, with a score of 0.4742.

Table 60 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Cost saving

	Initial costs	Long term return	Sustainable crop production
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.3108	0.1085	0.1493
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.1958	0.3445	0.3763
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.4933	0.5469	0.4742

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages, Food demand* element has the highest influence over *Raising awareness of regional products* with a result of 0.4933. The element *Long term results in food security* has highest importance on *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* with 0.6000.

Table 61 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages

	Food demand	Long term results in food security
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.4933	0.2000
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.1958	0.2000

3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.3108	0.6000
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Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Opportunities*, *Fertilization* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.6250 over the incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*. The result is followed closely by *Soil remediation* with 0.6223, indicating their significant impact on incentivizing assistance to manufacturers. *Sustainable soil management* also shows notable influence with a score of 0.497724.

Table 62 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Technological

	Fertilization	Soil remediation	Sustainable soil management
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.1365	0.1306	0.2174
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.2384	0.2469	0.2848
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.6250	0.6223	0.4977

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Social* control criteria in *Opportunities*, the highest priorities of the elements is over different incentives. *Biodiversity preservation* most significantly impacts the incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, with a score of 0.5. *Climate change* notably influences the incentives *Raising awareness of regional products* and *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, both scoring 0.4. *Regulation of the water cycle* sees its greatest influence over *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, with score of 0.5. Finally, *Soil quality* has highest influence on *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, with a score of 0.6666.

Table 63 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Social

	Biodiversity preservation	Climate change	Regulation of water cycle	Soil quality
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.5000	0.4000	0.2500	0.1111

2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.2500	0.2000	0.2500	0.2222
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.2500	0.4000	0.5000	0.6666

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic control* criteria in *Costs*, *Better product quality* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.5815 over the incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*. The element *Decreasing variable costs* prioritizes *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* with a score of 0.6433. *Gross margin increasing* moderately influences *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* with a score of 0.4836. Finally, *Higher retail price* influences equally both incentives *Raising awareness of regional products* and *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* with a score of 0.4.

Table 64 Influence of elements on the incentives under *Costs*, *Economic*, *Cost saving*

	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.1094	0.1013	0.1676	0.4000
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.3089	0.2553	0.3487	0.2000
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.5815	0.6433	0.4836	0.4000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic control* criteria in *Costs*, the incentive *Costs for information campaigns* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.4066 over the incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*. The element *Developing nature-positive production* has high importance over the incentive with a score of 0.5841 and *Increased expenditure for marketing* with a score of 0.4638. The incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* is influenced to the highest degree.

Table 65 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Market linkages

	Costs for information campaigns	Developing nature-positive production	Increased expenditure for marketing
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.3695	0.2318	0.2809
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.2238	0.1840	0.2552
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.4066	0.5841	0.4638

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Costs* the *Cover crop* element influences in highest degree the incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* with a score of 0.6300. The incentive is also highly influenced by *Increasing short-term investments* with a score of 0.5472, *Crop rotation* with a score of 0.4933 and *Precision agriculture* with a score of 0.6144.

Table 66 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Technological

	Cover crops	Crop rotation	Increasing short-term investments	Precision agriculture
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.2184	0.1958	0.1897	0.1172
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.1514	0.3108	0.2630	0.2683
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.6300	0.4933	0.5472	0.6144

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* the element *Increasing expenditures for soil health operations* prioritizes the incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* with a score of 0.5278. The element *Increasing initial costs* influences the same incentive with a score of 0.6483. The last element *Increasing variable costs* confirms the importance of the same incentive with a score of 0.4638.

Table 67 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Cost saving

	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations	Increasing initial costs	Increasing variable costs
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.1396	0.2296	0.2552
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.3325	0.1220	0.2809
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.5278	0.6483	0.4638

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic control* criteria in *Risks* the element *Access to finance* influences the incentive *Encouraging the association of producers* with a score of 0.4125. The highest importance of the element *Barriers to change practices for health practices* is over the incentive *Relation with tourism* with 0.4066. The elements *Perceived risk* and *Initial costs* prioritizes the incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* with a score respectively 0.5936 and 0.4638.

Table 68 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Market linkages

	Access to finance	Barriers to change practices for health practices	Initial costs	Perceived risk
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.2599	0.2238	0.2809	0.1570
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.4125	0.4066	0.2552	0.2493
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.3274	0.3695	0.4638	0.5936

Source: Own calculations

During the analysis of *Political control* criteria in *Risks* it as estimated that the element *Decreasing liquidity* has strongest influence over *Encouraging the association of producers* incentive with a score of 0.4836. The highest importance of the element *Income decrease* is over the incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* with a score of 0.4434. The element *Increasing the long term assets* has the same moderate influence of 0.3333 to all the incentives.

Table 69 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Political

	Decreasing liquidity	Income decrease	Increasing the long term assets
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.1676	0.1692	0.3333
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.4836	0.3873	0.3333
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.3487	0.4434	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

Phase 2: Influence of control criteria on the new incentives

The influence of the separate clusters is estimated relatively by comparing them in the control criteria. That means that if there is one cluster in the control criteria the weight of the cluster is 1. If there are more than one clusters, they are compared and weights are derived. All economics clusters have two clusters: Market linkages and Cost savings. Their weights are shown in table... *Benefits* are assigned a weight of 0.5 for both *Market linkages* and *Cost saving*. *Opportunities* receive a weight of 0.3333 for *Market linkages* and 0.6667 for *Cost saving*. *Costs* are weighted at 0.8 for *Market linkages* and 0.2 for *Cost saving*. *Risks* hold a weight of 0.75 for *Market linkages* and 0.25 for *Cost saving*. These numbers suggest that in both clusters, *Market linkages* is relatively more significant, while *Costs saving* are given moderate importance.

Table 70 Relative weights of the clusters

		Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risks
Economic	Market linkages	0.5	0.3333	0.8	0.75
	Cost saving	0.5	0.6667	0.2	0.25

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Benefits* the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes* which is assigned a significant weight of 0.6264. The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, which is assigned a high score of 0.5318. The highest priority under the *Social* control criteria is *Raising awareness of regional products*, with a score of 0.5031. The highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, with a moderate weight of 0.3780.

Table 71 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under Benefits

Incentive/Control criteria	Economic	Political	Social	Technological
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.1073	0.1854	0.5031	0.3442
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.26618	0.2826	0.2883	0.2777
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.6264	0.5318	0.2084	0.3780

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Opportunities*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, which is assigned a weight of 0.4718. The highest priority under the *Social* control criteria is again *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, with a weight of 0.4541. Lastly, the highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is also *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, with a weight of 0.5816.

Table 72 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under opportunities

Incentive/Control criteria	Economic	Social	Technological
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.2943	0.3152	0.1615
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.2337	0.2305	0.2567
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.4718	0.4541	0.5816

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Costs*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, which is assigned a weight of 0.5186. The highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, with a weight of 0.5712.

Table 73 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under costs

Incentive/Control criteria	Economic	Technological
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.2145	0.1802
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.2668	0.2484
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.5186	0.5712

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Risks*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*, which is assigned a weight of 0.5196. The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is *Encouraging the association of producers*, with a weight of 0.4014.

Table 74 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under risks

Incentive/Control criteria	Economic	Political
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.2137	0.2233
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.2666	0.4014
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.5196	0.3751

Source: Own calculations

Phase 3: Determining the control criteria weights and their influence on new incentives

The next step in the analysis represents the relative weights of control criteria, where *Economic* considerations hold the highest priority across *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs* and *Risks*, emphasizing its overarching importance. Technological factors have moderate weights, particularly in *Opportunities*, reflecting the recognition of technological advancements in driving growth opportunities. While *Social* factors play a minor role, they still contribute to both *Benefits* and *Opportunities*. *Political* considerations are prominent in addressing *Risks*, indicating a focus on regulatory and governance aspects to manage potential threats.

Table 75 Relative weights of the control criteria

	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risks
Economic	0.4553	0.4806	0.6667	0.6667
Technological	0.3355	0.4054	0.3333	-
Social	0.1281	0.1140	-	-

Political	0.0811	-	-	0.3333
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Source: Own calculations

The table below represents the priorities under *Benefits, Opportunities, Costs* and *Risks* after considering the relative weights of the control criteria. All four categories prioritize the incentive *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*. *Benefits* influence is with rating 45.8%. Additionally, *Opportunities* contribute with a bit more - 50.9% of the incentive's influence. *Costs* also play a significant role, representing 53.5% of the influence. While *Risks*, though slightly less impactful, contribute 46.3% to the overall influence.

Table 76 Overall priorities for Benefits, Opportunities, Costs and Risks

	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risks
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.2670	0.2500	0.2040	0.2180
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.2750	0.2420	0.2610	0.3200
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.4580	0.5090	0.5350	0.4630

Source: Own calculations

Phase 4: Strategic criteria weighting and final result

The next step is to estimate the Strategic criteria influence over the four categories. The estimation is subjective and is based on a focus group of experts from NBU. The estimation is made on 5 degree scale. This table presents a qualitative assessment of the three different strategic criteria – *Environmental care, To preserve landscapes and biodiversity* and *To protect food and health quality* over the categories *Benefits, Opportunities, Costs*, and *Risks*.

Table 77 Defining rating scale for strategic criteria

	Environmental care	To preserve lands~	To protect food a~
1.Benefits	Below average	Poor	Above average
2.Opportunities	Above average	Excellent	Average
3.Costs	Average	Below average	Average
4.Risks	Below average	Poor	Below average

Source: Own calculations

Based on the qualitative assessment the relative weights of the four blocks of the model are derived. *Opportunities* seems to have highest priority, followed by *Benefits, Costs* and *Risks*.

Table 78 Table ratings for strategic criteria and BOCR priorities

	TOTALS	Priorities	Environmental care	To preserve lands~	To protect food a~
1.Benefits	0.4249	0.3193	0.1263	0.0647	0.6643
2.Opportunities	0.5076	0.3815	0.6643	1.000	0.3061
3.Costs	0.2804	0.2107	0.3061	0.1263	0.3061
4.Risks	0.1175	0.0883	0.1263	0.0647	0.1263

Source: Own calculations

Overall income from BOCR analysis presents final priorities assigned to the three incentives. *Strengthening the control capacity for compliance with product quality and characteristics* is noted with a priority value of 0.2932, indicating a moderate focus on ensuring adherence to quality standards and specifications. *Encouraging the association of producers* holds a priority value of 0.2409, suggesting a mild emphasis on enhancing relationships within the tourism sector to promote growth and development. However, the highest priority value of 0.4658 is assigned to *Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes*.

Table 79 Overall Outcome of BOCR

Name	Priorities
1. Raising awareness of regional products	0.2932
2. Encouraging the association of producers	0.2409
3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	0.4658

Source: Own calculations

3.4 Italy: District of the Sands

The coastal area of the Emilia-Romagna Region is an area with a strong agricultural vocation with high-quality horticultural production. However, soil health faces strong pressures due to the high share of sand components and salinisation, subsidence and loss of organic matter and contamination. Therefore, the project will investigate the possibility to introduce carbon farming that can enhance organic matter. Due to the substantial extent of diffusion sandy soil in the area (six municipalities involved), we will investigate the possibility to develop a Biodistrict to develop new business models aiming at adding value to the soil conservation management with food production through certification and production standards. From the point of view of the promoted business models in WP 2 this model is Value chain.

The new incentives are:

1. Carbon Credits;
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes;
3. Collective action.

Phase 1: Evaluation of the influence of the elements on the new incentives

The analysis starts with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Cost saving*. According to the stakeholders' ratings, the importance of *Better product production* is high for the incentive *Collective action* with result of 0.6666. The importance of the element *Decreasing variable cost* to the incentives *Collective action* is with score 0.7007. Furthermore, in the case of the element *Increasing gross margin* holds the highest priority over *Agri-environmental climatic schemes*, with a score of 0.4869. The influence of *Higher retail prices* varies significantly across different incentives, with the highest over the incentive *Agri-environmental climatic schemes* and *Collective action*, with a score of 0.4615.

Table 80 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1. Carbon Credits	0.1667	0.0972	0.0778	0.0770
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.1667	0.2021	0.4869	0.4615
3. Collective action	0.6666	0.7007	0.4353	0.4615

Source: Own calculations

In the table below the analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Market linkages*. For the element *GAPs*, the highest influence is observed in the context of the incentive *Collective action*, scoring 0.5470. For the element *GMPs* (Good Manufacturing Practices), all three incentives receive the equal score 0.3333. *Long Chain* also sees its highest importance in *Carbon Credits*, with a score of 0.8600. Finally, *Producing Safe Food* demonstrates the highest influence once again in *Collective action*, scoring 0.7248. This consistent trend underscores the significant impact of *Collective action* on marketing linkages.

Table 81 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	GAPs	GMPs	Long chain	Producing safe food
1. Carbon Credits	0.1085	0.3333	0.8600	0.1248
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.3445	0.3333	0.4995	0.1504
3. Collective action	0.5470	0.3333	0.4145	0.7248

Source: Own calculations

For the control cluster *Political* in *Benefits* the influence of the elements over the incentives is in table below. For the elements *Better access to finance* prioritize the incentive *Carbon Credit*. The elements: *Efficiency improvement* and *Improvement productivity* the highest influence is consistently observed in the incentive *Agri-environmental climatic schemes*. Specifically, weights of 0.4067 for *Efficiency improvement* and 0.6908 for *Improvement productivity*. The element *Soil health financial measures* prioritize the incentive *Collective action* with 0.6355.

Table 82 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Political

Incentives/elements	Better access to finance	Efficiency improvement	Improvement productivity	Soil health financial measures
1. Carbon Credits	0.6908	0.2238	0.1488	0.0929
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.1603	0.4067	0.6908	0.2716
3. Collective action	0.1488	0.3695	0.1603	0.6355

Source: Own calculations

Regarding the *Social* control criteria in *Benefits* the highest importance is the same for each element. For *Informational campaigns*, the highest influence is observed over the incentive *Collective action*, scoring 0.7855. *Knowledge hubs* element prioritizes the incentive *Collective action* with a score of 0.6098.

Table 83 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Social

Incentives/elements	Informational campaigns	Knowledge hubs
1. Carbon Credits	0.0852	0.1655
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.1293	0.2245
3. Collective action	0.7855	0.6098

Source: Own calculations

The analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits, Technological* control criteria. The importance of *Knowledge of latest technologies* element is highest for the incentive *Collective action* with 0.6175. The incentive *Carbon Credits* has highest score according *Immediately available* element with score 0.7554.

Table 84 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Technological

Incentives/elements	Knowledge of latest technologies	Immediately available
1. Carbon Credits	0.0856	0.7554
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.2969	0.0669

3. Collective action	0.6175	0.1777
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Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities*, *Economic* control criteria, *cost saving* cluster the *Initial costs* element have highest influence over incentive *Agri-environmental climatic schemes*, scoring 0.6516. For *Long term return*, *Carbon Credits* exhibits the highest importance, scoring 0.4126. Lastly, *Sustainable crop production* also sees its highest priority in *Collective action*, with a score of 0.7259.

Table 85 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Initial costs	Long term return	Sustainable crop production
1. Carbon Credits	0.1781	0.4126	0.1020
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.6516	0.2599	0.1721
3. Collective action	0.1703	0.3275	0.7259

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities*, *Economic*, *Market linkages*, *Food demand* element has the highest influence over *Carbon Credits* with a result of 0.7007. The element *Long term results in food security* has equal importance over all three incentives with score 0.3333.

Table 86 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Food demand	Long term results in food security
1. Carbon Credits	0.7007	0.3333
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.2021	0.3333
3. Collective action	0.0972	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Opportunities*, all of three elements *Fertilization*, *Soil remediation* and *Sustainable soil management* demonstrates the influence with a scores respectively of 0.7641, 0.7731 and 0.7223. These numbers underscore the crucial role that collective actions, and highlight the importance of considering factors like fertilization, soil remediation, and sustainable soil management in such initiatives.

Table 87 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Technological

Incentives/elements	Fertilization	Soil remediation	Sustainable soil management
1. Carbon Credits	0.1209	0.1392	0.0727
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.1149	0.0877	0.2050
3. Collective action	0.7641	0.7731	0.7223

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Social control* criteria in *Opportunities*, the highest priorities of the elements are over one incentive *Collective action*. *Biodiversity preservation*, *Climate change*, *Regulation of the water cycle* and *Soil quality* have significantly impacts the incentive *Collective action*, with a score of 0.7641, 0.7732, 0.7893 and 0.7223 respectively. These highest numbers in each column signify the varied impacts of different elements on different environmental factors, emphasizing the importance of tailored approaches *collective action* to address specific challenges.

Table 88 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Social

Incentives/elements	Biodiversity preservation	Climate change	Regulation of water cycle	Soil quality
1. Carbon Credits	0.1210	0.1391	0.0684	0.0727
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.1149	0.0877	0.1423	0.2050
3. Collective action	0.7641	0.7732	0.7893	0.7223

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic control* criteria in *Costs*, *Better product quality* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.6666 over the incentive *Collective action*. The element *Decreasing variable costs* prioritizes *Agri-environmental climatic schemes* with a score of 0.7010. *Gross margin increasing* moderately influences *Agri-environmental climatic schemes* and *Collective action* with the same score of 0.4286. Finally, *Higher retail price* influences incentive *Agri-environmental climatic* with a score of 0.5876. These numbers underscore the significance of *Agri-environmental climatic schemes* in reducing costs, highlighting their role in improving business outcomes.

Table 89 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1. Carbon Credits	0.1667	0.1062	0.1429	0.0890
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.1667	0.7010	0.4286	0.5876
3. Collective action	0.6666	0.1928	0.4286	0.3234

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic control* criteria in *Costs*, the incentive *Costs for information campaigns* demonstrates the equal influence on all incentives with a score of 0.3333. The element *Developing nature-positive production* has high importance over the incentive *Collective action*

with a score of 0.6519 and element *Increased expenditure* for *Agri-environmental climatic schemes* with a score of 0.4239. The incentive *Collective action* is influenced to the highest degree.

Table 90 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Costs for information campaigns	Developing nature-positive production	Increased expenditure for marketing
1. Carbon Credits	0.3333	0.1130	0.3935
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.3333	0.2351	0.4239
3. Collective action	0.3333	0.6519	0.1826

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Costs* the *Cover crop* element influences in highest degree the incentive *Carbon Credits* with a score of 0.4126. The incentive *Agri-environmental climatic schemes* is highly influenced by *Increasing short-term investments* with a score of 0.7418 and *Crop rotation* with a score of 0.5842. The incentive *Collective action* is influenced by the element *Precision agriculture* with a score of 0.5198. These numbers underscore the significance of *Agri-environmental climatic schemes* in promoting crop rotation and increasing short term investment in soil health.

Table 91 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Technological

Incentives/elements	Cover crops	Crop rotation	Increasing short term investments	Precision agriculture
1. Carbon Credits	0.4126	0.1350	0.0752	0.0856
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.2599	0.5842	0.7418	0.3946
3. Collective action	0.3275	0.2808	0.1830	0.5198

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* the element *Increasing expenditures for soil health operations* prioritizes the incentive *Collective action* with a score of 0.7418. The element *Increasing initial costs* influences the incentive *Agri-environmental climatic schemes* with a score of 0.7074. The last element *Increasing variable costs* confirms the importance of the all incentives with a score of 0.3333.

Table 92 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations	Increasing initial costs	Increasing variable costs

1. Carbon Credits	0.0752	0.1226	0.3333
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.1830	0.7074	0.3333
3. Collective action	0.7418	0.1700	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic control* criteria in *Risks* the element *Access to finance* influences the incentive *Carbon Credits* with a score of 0.7538. The highest importance of the rest of the elements is over the incentive *Agri-environmental climatic schemes* with 0.7418, 0.6301 and 0.4721 respectively.

Table 93 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Access to finance	Barriers to change practices for health practices	Initial costs	Perceived risk
1. Carbon Credits	0.7538	0.0752	0.1085	0.0836
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.0827	0.7418	0.6301	0.4721
3. Collective action	0.1635	0.1830	0.2614	0.4443

Source: Own calculations

During the analysis of *Political control* criteria in *Risks* it is estimated that the element *Decreasing liquidity* has medium influence over all of three incentives with a score 0.3333. The highest importance of the element *Income decrease* is over the incentive *Carbon Credits* with a score of 0.6. The element *Increasing the long term assets* has the same moderate influence of 0.5145 to the incentive *Collective action*.

Table 94 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Political

Incentives/elements	Decreasing liquidity	Income decrease	Increasing the long term assets
1. Carbon Credits	0.3333	0.6000	0.0975
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.3333	0.2000	0.3880
3. Collective action	0.3333	0.2000	0.5145

Source: Own calculations

Phase 2: Influence of control criteria on the new incentives

The influence of the separate clusters is estimated relatively by comparing them in the control criteria. That means that if there is one cluster in the control criteria the weight of the cluster is 1. If there are more than one clusters, they are compared and weights are derived. All economics clusters have two clusters: *Market linkages* and *Cost savings*. Their weights are shown in the table below. *Benefits* are assigned a weight of 0.6666 for *Market linkages* and 0.3333 for *Cost saving*. *Opportunities* receive a weight of 0.2500 for *Market linkages* and 0.7500 for *Cost saving*. *Costs* are weighted at 0.2500 for *Market linkages* and 0.7500 for *Cost saving*. *Risks* hold a weight for both *Market linkages* and *Cost saving* with 0.5000.

Table 95 Relative weights of the clusters

Control criteria	Clusters	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risks
Economic	Market linkages	0.6666	0.2500	0.2500	0.5000
	Cost saving	0.3333	0.7500	0.7500	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Benefits* the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Collective action* which is assigned a significant weight of 0.5252. The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is *Collective action*, which is assigned a high score of 0.3285. The highest priority under the *Social* control criteria is *Collective action*, with a score of 0.69676. The highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is *Carbon Credits*, with a moderate weight of 0.4205. These results reflect a strong importance of the *Economic*, *Political* and *Social* factors over the on collective action in soil health.

Table 96 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under benefits

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political	Social	Technological
1. Carbon Credits	0.1437	0.2891	0.1254	0.4205
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.3311	0.2824	0.1770	0.1819
3. Collective action	0.5252	0.3285	0.6976	0.3976

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Opportunities*, the highest priority under the all *Economic*, *Social* and *Technological* control criteria's is *Collective action*. These results indicate a strong emphasis on *Collective actions* in the direction to improve soil health.

Table 97 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under opportunities

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Social	Technological
1. Carbon Credits	0.3024	0.1003	0.1643

2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.3378	0.1375	0.2527
3. Collective action	0.3597	0.7622	0.5829

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Costs*, the highest priority under the *Economic* and *Technological* control criteria's is *Agri-environmental climatic schemes*. These results suggest a significant emphasis on supporting manufacturers eligible for European Agri-environmental climatic schemes, particularly in economic and technological considerations, indicating the importance of investment in quality assurance and compliance measures within these domains.

Table 98 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under costs

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Technological
1. Carbon Credits	0.1646	0.1771
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.4369	0.4951
3. Collective action	0.3995	0.3278

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Risks*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Agri-environmental climatic schemes*, which is assigned a weight of 0.4448. The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is *Collective action*, with a weight of 0.3493.

Table 99 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under risks

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political
1. Carbon Credits	0.2162	0.3436
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.4448	0.3071
3. Collective action	0.3390	0.3493

Source: Own calculations

Phase 3: Determining the control criteria weights and their influence on new incentives

In the table below are the relative weights of control criteria, where *Economic* considerations hold the highest priority for *Costs*. *Technological* factors have moderate weights, particularly in *Benefits*, reflecting the recognition of technological advancements in driving growth opportunities. While *Social* factors play an important role, they still contribute to the *Opportunities*. *Political* considerations are prominent in addressing *Risks*, indicating a focus on regulatory and governance aspects to manage potential threats.

Table 100 Relative weights of the control criteria

Control criteria/blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
Economic	0.2508	0.1634	0.8750	0.2000
Technological	0.2947	0.2970	0.1250	
Social	0.2629	0.5396		

Political	0.1917			0.8000
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Source: Own calculations

The table below represents the priorities under *Benefits, Opportunities, Costs* and *Risks* after considering the relative weights of the control criteria. The most of the main blocks categories prioritize the incentive *Collective action*. *Benefits* influence is with rating 0.4654. Additionally, *Opportunities* contribute with a bit more 0.5983 of the incentive's influence and *Risk* with 0.3476. *Costs* play a significant role on the other incentive *Agri-environmental climatic schemes*, representing 0.4425 of the influence.

Table 101 Overall priorities

Incentives/blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
1. Carbon Credits	0.2701	0.1748	0.1660	0.3227
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.2645	0.2270	0.4425	0.3297
3. Collective action	0.4654	0.5983	0.3915	0.3476

Source: Own calculations

Phase 4: Strategic criteria weighting and final result

The next step is to estimate the Strategic criteria influence over the four categories. The estimation is subjective and is based on a focus group of experts from NBU. The estimation is made on 5 degree scale. This table below presents a qualitative assessment of the three different strategic criteria – *Environmental care, To preserve landscapes and biodiversity* and *To protect food and health quality* over the categories *Benefits, Opportunities, Costs*, and *Risks*. Each criterion is evaluated based on its performance relative to others. For instance, in terms of *Benefits*, *Environmental Care* is rated as Below Average, while *Opportunities* in *To preserve landscapes and biodiversity* are deemed Excellent.

Table 102 Defining rating scale for strategic criteria

Blocks/strategic criteria	Fair income	Food chain	Innovation
Benefits	Excellent	Above Average	Excellent
Opportunities	Above Average	Above Average	Excellent
Costs	Average	Average	Below Average
Risks	Above Average	Average	Below Average

Source: Own calculations

In the table below we can see the summarized relative weights of the strategic criteria and in column Totals are the final weights.

Table 103 Ratings for strategic criteria and BOCR priorities

Blocks/strategic criteria	TOTALS	PRIORITIES	Fair income	Food chain	Innovation
1.Benefits	0.8474	0.3709	1.0000	0.6643	1.0000
2.Opportunities	0.6948	0.3041	0.6643	0.6643	1.0000
3.Costs	0.2898	0.1268	0.3061	0.3061	0.1263
4.Risks	0.4526	0.1981	0.6643	0.3061	0.1263

Source: Own calculations

The data in the table below presents priorities assigned to three different incentives. *Carbon Credits* is noted with a priority value of 0.1633, indicating a minor focus on ensuring adherence to Carbon Credits in the case study. *Agri-environmental climatic schemes* hold a priority value of 0.0257, suggesting a small emphasis on Agri-environmental climatic schemes as an incentive for soil health. However, the highest priority value of 0.8110 is assigned to *Collective action*, reflecting a strategic focus to enhance product quality, market access, and competitiveness.

Table 104 Overall outcome of BOCR

Incentives	Priorities
1. Carbon Credits	0.1633
2. Agri-environmental climatic schemes	0.0257
3. Collective action	0.8110

Source: Own calculations

3.5 Italy: A model for multifunctional I and sustainable local development of marginal areas

Hilly areas of the Tuscany Region are considered marginal due to their conventional extensive agriculture and limited agricultural value. These areas face various environmental and socio-economic constraints that negatively impact crop productivity and environmental quality, resulting in low farmer incomes. The prevailing cropping systems in these areas are winter cereal-based, leading to soil degradation and a decline in ecosystem services. Issues such as soil erosion, nutrient leaching, and reduction of carbon content in soils are of significant concern. This case study aims to learn from the project's experiences by assessing the effectiveness of actions taken to improve soil fertility and health, increase productivity, enhance resilience, and valorise the landscape. The focus will be on exploring the development of business models that add value to agronomic management aimed at conserving soil health through innovative crop products, certification, and production standards. From the point of view of the promoted business models in WP 2 this model is Payments for ES.

The new incentives are:

1. ECO-SCHEME 5 (Italy)– Specific measures for pollinators;
2. Private soil health labels;

3. Italian fund for sustainable tourism 2023-25 (Fondo per il turismo sostenibile).

Phase 1: Evaluation of the influence of the elements on the new incentives

The analysis I begins with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Cost saving*. According to the stakeholder's ratings the importance of *Better product production* is high for the incentive *Private soil health labels* with result of 0,5498. The importance of the element *Decreasing variable cost* is higher for the incentive *ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators*. The third incentive for *Italian sustainable tourism* presents higher values under the *Gross margin increasing element* with 0,6250. The influence of *Higher retail prices* varies significantly across different incentives, with the highest over the incentive *Private soil health labels*, with a score of 0,6348.

Table 105 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.3681	0.4126	0.1365	0.0780
2.Private soil health labels	0.5498	0.3275	0.2385	0.6348
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.0821	0.2599	0.6250	0.2872

Source: Own calculations

In the table below the analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Market linkages*. For the element *GAPs*, the highest influence is observed in the context of the incentive *ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators*, scoring 0,5472. The same incentive presents higher score for the element *GMPs* (Good Manufacturing Practices) of 0,6301. The third incentive *Italian fund for sustainable tourism* presents higher scores for both elements *Long Chain* and *Producing Safe Food*, with score of 0,4934 and 0,5936 respectively. On the other hand, the incentive *Private soil health labels* produce lower scores for each of the elements in this cluster.

Table 106 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	GAPs	GMPs	Long chain	Producing safe food
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.5472	0.6301	0.3108	0.1571
2.Private soil health labels	0.1897	0.1515	0.1958	0.2493

3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.2631	0.2184	0.4934	0.5936
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Source: Own calculations

For the control cluster *Political* in *Benefits* the influence of the elements over the incentives is in the table below. For all elements except *Better access to finance*, the incentive ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators presents the higher scores. The scores are the same for both *Efficiency improvement* and *Improvement productivity* (0,5842), with slightly higher score of 0,6250 for the element *Soil health financial measures*. This underscores a strong emphasis on the role of measures to support pollinators. The incentive *Private soil health labels* have a higher score for the element *Better access to finance* which underlines the importance of financial resources in this regard. Regarding the political cluster in benefits, the incentive *Italian fund for sustainable tourism* is represented with low scores.

Table 107 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Political

Incentives/elements	Better access to finance	Efficiency improvement	Improvement productivity	Soil health financial measures
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.3275	0.5842	0.5842	0.6250
2.Private soil health labels	0.4126	0.1350	0.1350	0.2385
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.2599	0.2808	0.2808	0.1365

Source: Own calculations

Regarding the *Social* control criteria in *Benefits* the highest importance for the element *Informational campaigns* is slightly higher for the incentive *Italian fund for sustainable tourism* (0,3793), where for the element *Knowledge hubs* the incentive for pollinators measures presents the higher score of 0,4742. However, it is worth mentioning that the incentive for sustainable tourism has a very close score for both of the elements in this cluster.

Table 108 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Social

Incentives/elements	Informational campaigns	Knowledge hubs
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.3313	0.4742
2.Private soil health labels	0.2894	0.1494
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.3793	0.3764

Source: Own calculations

In the table below the analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits, Technological* control criteria. Both of the elements here represent substantial score for the first incentive *Specific measures for pollinators* (0,6908 for each). Apparently, the knowledge of latest technologist together with ensuring that resources are immediately available are an important technological element for this incentive.

Table 109 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Technological

Incentives/elements	Knowledge of latest technologies	Immediately available
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.6908	0.6908
2.Private soil health labels	0.1603	0.1603
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.1488	0.1488

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic* control criteria, *cost saving* cluster the *Initial costs* element have highest influence over incentive *Specific measures for pollinators* with scoring of 0,7007. On the other hand, the importance of *Italian fund for sustainable tourism* is substantial for both of the elements *Long - term return* and *Sustainable crop production* with close scores of 0,6782 and 0,6000 respectively.

Table 110 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Initial costs	Long term return	Sustainable crop production
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.7007	0.1794	0.2000
2.Private soil health labels	0.0972	0.1424	0.2000
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.2021	0.6782	0.6000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages*, both *Food demand* and *Long term results in food security* elements have the highest influence over the incentive *Private soil health labels*, which underlines the potential of such incentives.

Table 111 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Food demand	Long term results in food security
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1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.2000	0.1350
2.Private soil health labels	0.6000	0.5842
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.2000	0.2808

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Opportunities*, *Fertilization* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0,4934 over the incentive *Private soil health labels*. However, *Soil remediation* and *Sustainable soil management* appear to have notable influence on the incentive *Specific measures for pollinators* with a score of 0,6000 and 0,7007 respectively.

Table 112 Influence of elements on the incentives under *Opportunities*, *Technological*

Incentives/elements	Fertilization	Soil remediation	Sustainable soil management
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.1958	0.6000	0.7007
2.Private soil health labels	0.4934	0.2000	0.2021
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.3108	0.2000	0.0972

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Social* control criteria in *Opportunities*, the element *Biodiversity preservation* most significantly impacts the incentive *Specific measures for pollinators*, with a score of 0,6483. The elements *Regulation of the water cycle* and *Soil quality influence the incentive for with very close scores of 0,5278 and 0,5076*. However, *Climate change* appears to have the same influence over all of the incentives of 0,3333.

Table 113 Influence of elements on the incentives under *Opportunities*, *Social*

Incentives/elements	Biodiversity preservation	Climate change	Regulation of water cycle	Soil quality
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.6483	0.3333	0.3325	0.3791
2.Private soil health labels	0.2297	0.3333	0.5278	0.5076
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.1220	0.3333	0.1397	0.1133

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Costs*, the elements vary among the different incentives. The incentive *Specific*

measures for pollinators shows importance to both elements of Better product quality with score of 0,5769 and Decreasing variable costs with score of 0,4126. Gross margin increasing influences Italian fund for sustainable tourism with a score of 0,6250. Finally, Higher retail price influences the incentive for private soil health labels. Raising awareness of regional products and Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes with a score of 0.4. These numbers underscore the significance of pollinators programs in enhancing product quality and reducing costs.

Table 114 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.5769	0.4126	0.1365	0.0780
2.Private soil health labels	0.3420	0.3275	0.2385	0.6348
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.0811	0.2599	0.6250	0.2872

Source: Own calculations

Regarding Market linkages cluster in Economic control criteria in Costs, the elements Costs for information campaigns and Increased expenditure for marketing present similar results across the incentives. Private soil health labels and Italian fund for sustainable tourism incentives have moderate scores of 0,444 for these two elements. A substantial influence has the element of Developing nature-positive production regarding the incentive Specific measures for pollinators (0,6817).

Table 115 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Costs for information campaigns	Developing nature-positive production	Increased expenditure for marketing
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.1111	0.6817	0.1111
2.Private soil health labels	0.4444	0.2363	0.4444
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.4444	0.0819	0.4444

Source: Own calculations

When considering Technological control criteria in Costs the incentive for Private soil health labels shows the highest scores in relation with Crop rotation (0,6492), Increasing short-term investments (0,4991) and Precision agriculture (0,7143). In the case with soil health labels, precision agriculture as a technological option represents the highest score which underlies its major

influence on incentives like this. On the other hand, the element *Cover crops* influences in highest degree the incentive *Specific measures for pollinators* with score of 0,6519.

Table 116 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Technological

Incentives/elements	Cover crops	Crop rotation	Increasing short-term investments	Precision agriculture
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.6519	0.2738	0.1048	0.1429
2.Private soil health labels	0.2351	0.6492	0.4991	0.7143
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.1130	0.0770	0.3961	0.1429

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* the elements *Increasing expenditures for soil health operations* and *Increasing initial costs* prioritize the incentive *Private soil health labels* (with close scores of 0,6738 and 0,6348). The last element *Increasing variable costs* influences the incentive *Italian fund for sustainable tourism* with score of 0,4126.

Table 117 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations	Increasing initial costs	Increasing variable costs
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.1007	0.0780	0.2599
2.Private soil health labels	0.6738	0.6348	0.3275
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.2255	0.2587	0.4126

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* the element *Access to finance* influences in the same way two of the incentives: *Private soil health labels* and *Italian fund for sustainable tourism*. The highest importance of the element *Barriers to change practices for health practices* is over the incentive *Italian fund for sustainable tourism* with slightly higher score of 0,4126. We observe substantial importance of the incentive for *Private soil health labels* regarding the element for *Initial costs* (0,6250), and the incentive of *Specific measures for pollinators* for *Perceived risk* (0,6908).

Table 118 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Access to finance	Barriers to change practices for health practices	Initial costs	Perceived risk
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.1429	0.3275	0.1365	0.6908
2.Private soil health labels	0.4286	0.2599	0.6250	0.1488
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.4286	0.4126	0.2385	0.1603

Source: Own calculations

During the analysis of *Political control* criteria in *Risks* we found that the incentive for Private soil health labels has the largest importance for all of the elements in this cluster: *Decreasing liquidity* (0,6370), *Income decrease* (0,6370), and *Increasing the long term assets* (0,5936). These results show the significance of incentives like this on the business outcomes and the need to overcome such risks.

Table 119 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Political

Incentives/elements	Decreasing liquidity	Income decrease	Increasing the long term assets
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.1047	0.1047	0.1571
2.Private soil health labels	0.6370	0.6370	0.5936
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.2583	0.2583	0.2493

Source: Own calculations

Phase 2: Influence of control criteria on the new incentives

The influence of the separate clusters is estimated relatively by comparing them in the control criteria. That means that if there is one cluster in the control criteria the weight of the cluster is 1. If there are more than one clusters, they are compared and weights are derived. All economics clusters have two clusters: Market linkages and Cost savings. Their weights are shown in the table below. *Benefits* are assigned a weight of 0.6666 for *Market linkages* and 0.3333 for *Cost saving*. *Opportunities* receive a weight of 0.1000 for *Market linkages* and 0.9000 for *Cost saving*. *Costs* are weighted at 0.7500 for *Market linkages* and 0.2500 for *Cost saving*. *Risks* hold a weight of 0.50 for both *Market linkages* and *Cost saving*. These numbers suggest that the cluster *Market linkages* is relatively more significant for *Benefits* (0.6666)

and Costs (0.7500), while *Costs saving* are more significant regarding Opportunities (0.90). Both clusters appear to have the same weight regarding Risks (0.5).

Table 120 Relative weights of the clusters

Control criteria	Clusters	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risks
Economic	Market linkages	0.6666	0.1000	0.7500	0.5000
	Cost saving	0.3333	0.9000	0.2500	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Benefits* the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Italian fund for sustainable tourism* (0.3659), which is just slightly higher when the incentive *Specific measures for pollinators* (0.3571). The incentive *Specific measures for pollinators* has the highest priority under the other three control criteria: *Political* (0.5302), *Social* (0.4028), *Technological* (0.6908), which highlights the importance of such incentives.

Table 121 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under benefits

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political	Social	Technological
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.3571	0.5302	0.4028	0.6908
2.Private soil health labels	0.2769	0.2302	0.2194	0.1603
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.3659	0.2395	0.3778	0.1488

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Opportunities*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Italian fund for sustainable tourism* (0.4681). The highest priority under the *Social* and *Technological* control criteria is for *Specific measures for pollinators* with scores of 0.4233 and 0,4988 respectively.

Table 122 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under opportunities

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Social	Technological
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.3408	0.4233	0,4988
2.Private soil health labels	0.1911	0.3996	0,2985
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.4681	0.1771	0,2027

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Costs*, the highest priority under the *Economic* and *Technological* control criteria is *Private soil health labels*. However, it should be noted that regarding the *Economic* control criteria the result is just very slightly higher (0,3777), compared to the other two incentives.

Table 123 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under costs

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Technological
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.3012	0.2933
2.Private soil health labels	0.3777	0.5244
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.3210	0.1822

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Risks*, the highest priority under the *Economic* and *Political* control criteria is *Private soil health labels* (0,5569 and 0,6225). These results suggest above average concern for political risks associated with supporting private soil health labels.

Table 124 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under risks

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.1225	0.1222
2.Private soil health labels	0.5569	0.6225
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.3206	0.2553

Source: Own calculations

Phase 3: Determining the control criteria weights and their influence on new incentives

The table below represents the relative weights of control criteria, where *Economic* considerations hold the highest priority across *Costs* (0.8) and *Risk* (0.5), emphasizing its overarching importance. *Technological* factors have moderate weights, particularly in *Opportunities* (0.3275) reflecting the recognition of technological advancements in driving growth opportunities. While *Social* factors play a moderate role in *Benefits* (0.3769). And finally, *Political* considerations are average in addressing *Risks* (0,5000), indicating a focus on regulatory and governance aspects to manage potential threats.

Table 125 Relative weights of the control criteria

Control criteria/blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
Economic	0.1728	0.4126	0.8000	0.5000
Technological	0.0734	0.3275	0.2000	
Social	0.3769	0.2599	-	-
Political	0.3769	-	-	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

The table below represents the priorities under *Benefits, Opportunities, Costs* and *Risks* after considering the relative weights of the control criteria. As so far the analysis showed, the Benefits and Opportunities categories prioritize with moderate influence the incentive *Specific measures for pollinators*, while Costs and Risks – the incentive for *Private soil health labels*.

Table 126 Overall priorities

Incentives/blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.4476	0.4125	0.3000	0.1223
2.Private soil health labels	0.2322	0.2833	0.4002	0.5878
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.3202	0.3042	0.2998	0.2897

Source: Own calculations

Phase 4: Strategic criteria weighting and final result

The next step is to estimate the Strategic criteria influence over the four categories. The estimation is subjective and is based on a focus group of experts from NBU. The estimation is made on 5-degree scale. This table presents a qualitative assessment of the three different strategic criteria – *Environmental care, To preserve landscapes and biodiversity* and *To protect food and health quality* over the categories *Benefits, Opportunities, Costs*, and *Risks*. Each criterion is evaluated based on its performance relative to others. Here, the Benefit category shows Above average assessments for all of the three strategic criteria. *Environmental care* shows poor assessments regarding both Costs and Risks.

Table 127 Defining rating scale for strategic criteria

Blocks/strategic criteria	Environmental care	To preserve landscapes and biodiversity	Vibrant rural areas
Benefits	Above Average	Above Average	Above Average
Opportunities	Average	Average	Below Average
Costs	Poor	Below Average	Below Average
Risks	Poor	Poor	Average

Source: Own calculations

Table 128 Ratings for strategic criteria and BOCR priorities

Blocks/strategic criteria	TOTALS	PRIORITIES	Environmental care	To preserve landscapes and biodiversity	Vibrant rural areas
1.Benefits	0.6643	0.5720	0.6643	0.6643	0.6643
2.Opportunities	0.2462	0.2120	0.3061	0.3061	0.1263

3.Costs	0.1058	0.0911	0.0647	0.1263	0.1263
4.Risks	0.1452	0.1250	0.0647	0.0647	0.3061

Source: Own calculations

The data in the table below presents priorities assigned to three different incentives. The highest priority is given to the incentive *Specific measures for pollinators* (0,5149), followed by *Italian fund for sustainable tourism* (0,3231). Minor emphasis is put on Private soil health labels (0,1620). These assessments show a strategic focus on pollinators measures, a moderate focus on ensuring sustainable tourism and a minor emphasis on soil health labels.

Table 129 Overall outcome of BOCR

Incentives	Priorities
1.ECO-SCHEME 5 – Specific measures for pollinators	0.5149
2.Private soil health labels	0.1620
3.Italian fund for sustainable tourism	0.3231

Source: Own calculations

3.6 Italy: CiRAA LTEs on conventional and organic agriculture

The case study focuses on a series of long term experiments (LTEs) carried out at large plots/field scale at the Centre for Agri-environmental Research "Enrico Avanzi" of the University of Pisa. Two field experiments are focusing on the application of conservation agriculture techniques (i.e. reduced or no tillage, cover crops), whereas the third one dealt with organic vs conventional farming systems. The oldest field experiment started in 1986 and is comparing on around 2 ha continuous no-till vs annual mouldboard ploughing 30 cm depth on durum wheat and pigeon bean crops. Effects on soil fertility (SOC, C stock, bulk density, total N, available P, pH) are regularly assessed at different depths (0-10, 10-30, 30-60 cm), besides with crop yield and nutrient uptake. The second LTE is comparing on 4 ha since 1993 the combination of 2 tillage levels (reduced tillage vs annual ploughing 30 cm depth), 4 N fertilization levels and 4 cover crop species (control, hairy vetch, radish, a mixture of the two) on a 4-yr arable crop rotation including durum wheat, sunflower and grain sorghum. Soil fertility issues, crop yield, weed abundance and composition are regularly assessed. In the third LTE, being carried out on 23 ha since 2001, an organic and a conventional management system are being compared on a 4-yr (conventional system: durum wheat-chickpea-common wheat and grain sorghum) or 8-yr (organic system: common wheat-grain millet-grain sorghum chickpea- hemmer wheat-alfalfa) arable crop rotation. Soil fertility, crop yield and rheological quality, weed abundance and composition, energy use efficiency, economic balance, are regularly assessed, thanks to the standard field plot size. From the point of view of the promoted business models in WP 2 this model is Value chain.

The new incentives are:

1. Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods;
2. Reduced soils processing techniques;
3. Cover crops.

Phase 1: Evaluation of the influence of the elements on the new incentives

The analysis start with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Cost saving*. According to the stakeholder's ratings, the importance of *Better product production* is high for the incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with result of 0.8000. The importance of the element *Decreasing variable cost* to the incentives *Reduced soils processing techniques* is with scoring 0,6264. Furthermore, in the case of the element *Increasing gross margin* holds the highest priority over *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a score of 0,4286. The influence of *Higher retail prices* varies significantly across different incentives, with the highest over the incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a score of 0,7375.

Table 130 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8000	0.3012	0.4286	0.7375
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.1000	0.6264	0.4286	0.1773
3.Cover crops	0.1000	0.1429	0.3325	0.0852

Source: Own calculations

In the table below the analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Market linkages*. For the element *GAPs*, the highest influence is observed in the context of the incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, scoring 0,4934. Differently, for the element *GMPs* (Good Manufacturing Practices), the incentive *Reduced soils processing techniques* exhibits the highest priority, scoring 0,4286. *Long Chain* also sees its highest importance in *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a score of 0.8000. Finally, *Producing Safe Food* demonstrates the highest influence once again in *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic*

production practices and methods, scoring 0.5936. This consistent trend underscores the significant impact of assistance provided under Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods.

Table 131 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	GAPs	GMPs	Long chain	Producing safe food
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.4934	0.1429	0.8000	0.5936
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.3108	0.4286	0.1000	0.1571
3.Cover crops	0.1958	0.4286	0.1000	0.2493

Source: Own calculations

For the control cluster *Political* in *Benefits* the influence of the elements over the incentives is in the table below. For the elements *Better access to finance*, the influence observed in the incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* is 0.5499. For the *Efficiency improvement*, the highest score is 0.7500 for incentive *Reduced soils processing techniques* for *Improvement productivity*. The element *Improvement productivity* impose the incentive *Cover crops*. The element *Soil health financial measures* prioritize the incentive *Cover crops* with 0.5499. This underscores a strong emphasis on supporting manufacturers within the framework of *Cover crops* to improve access to productivity, and soil health financial measures (political benefits).

Table 132 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Political

Incentives/elements	Better access to finance	Efficiency improvement	Improvement productivity	Soil health financial measures
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.5499	0.1250	0.0902	0.2402
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.2402	0.7500	0.2449	0.2098
3.Cover crops	0.2098	0.1250	0.6648	0.5499

Source: Own calculations

Regarding the *Social* control criteria in *Benefits* the highest importance is the same for each element. For *Informational campaigns*, the highest influence is observed over the incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, scoring 0.8182. *Knowledge hubs* element prioritizes the incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with a score of 0.4868.

Table 133 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Social

Incentives/elements	Informational campaigns	Knowledge hubs
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8182	0.4868
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.0909	0.1417
3.Cover crops	0.0909	0.3715

Source: Own calculations

In the table below the analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits, Technological* control criteria. The importance of *Knowledge of latest technologies* element and *Immediately available* is highest for the incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* and *Cover crops* with 0.4000. This highlights a strong emphasis on *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* and *Cover crops* in terms of leveraging knowledge of latest technologies and ensuring resources are immediately available.

Table 134 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Technological

Incentives/elements	Knowledge of latest technologies	Immediately available
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.4000	0.4000
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.2000	0.2000
3.Cover crops	0.4000	0.4000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic* control criteria, *Cost saving* cluster the *Initial costs* element have highest influence over incentive *Cover crops*, scoring 0.4655. Similarly, for *Long term return*, *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* the highest importance, scoring 0.7778. Lastly, *Sustainable crop production* also sees its highest priority in *Reduced soils processing techniques*, with a score of 0.5171. In this cluster the importance of *all three incentives* are substantial across all elements. This underscores a strong commitment to supporting manufacturers within the framework of European quality schemes.

Table 135 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Initial costs	Long term return	Sustainable crop production
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.4330	0.7778	0.1243
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.1005	0.1111	0.5171
3.Cover crops	0.4665	0.1111	0.3586

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages, Food demand* element has the highest influence over *Cover crops* a result of 0.5368. The element *Long term results in food security* has highest importance on *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with 0.5171.

Table 136 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Food demand	Long term results in food security
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.0989	0.5171
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.3643	0.1243
3.Cover crops	0.5368	0.3586

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Opportunities, Fertilization* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.6833 over the incentive *Reduced soils processing techniques*. The result is followed closely by *Soil remediation* with 0.5714 on *Cover crops* incentive. *Sustainable soil management* also shows notable influence, albeit slightly strong, with a score of 0.6817. These numbers underscore the crucial role that assistance programs play in supporting *Cover crops*, and highlight the importance of considering factors like soil remediation, and sustainable soil management in such initiatives.

Table 137 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Technological

Incentives/elements	Fertilization	Soil remediation	Sustainable soil management
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.1168	0.2857	0.2363

2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.6833	0.1429	0.0819
3.Cover crops	0.1998	0.5714	0.6817

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Social control* criteria in Opportunities, the highest priorities of the elements are over different incentives. *Biodiversity preservation* most significantly impacts the incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a score of 0.6955. *Climate change* notably influence the incentives *Cover crops* with a score 0,5499. *Regulation of the water cycle* sees its greatest influence over *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with score of 0.6586. Finally, *Soil quality* has highest influence on *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a score of 0.5278. These highest numbers in each three elements signify the varied impacts on different environmental factors, emphasizing the importance of *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*.

Table 138 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Social

Incentives/elements	Biodiversity preservation	Climate change	Regulation of water cycle	Soil quality
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.6955	0.2098	0.6586	0.5278
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.0754	0.2402	0.0786	0.1396
3.Cover crops	0.2290	0.5499	0.2628	0.3325

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic control* criteria in Costs, *Better product quality* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.8000 over the incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*. The element *Decreasing variable costs* prioritizes *Reduced soils processing techniques* with a score of 0.6264. *Gross margin increasing* moderately influences *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with a score of 0.4286. Finally, *Higher retail price* influences incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with a score of 0.7375. These numbers underscore the significance of assistance program for *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* in enhancing product quality, increasing gross margin and higher retail price.

Table 139 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.8000	0.3012	0.4286	0.7375
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.1000	0.6264	0.4286	0.1773
3.Cover crops	0.1000	0.0724	0.1429	0.0852

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Costs*, the incentive *Costs for information campaigns* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.4706 over the incentive *Reduced soils processing techniques*. The element *Developing nature-positive production* has high importance over the same incentive with a score of 0.4434 and the last element *Increased expenditure for marketing* with a score of 0.4706. The incentive *Reduced soils processing techniques* is influenced to the highest degree from all of research elements in this cluster.

Table 140 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Costs for information campaigns	Developing nature-positive production	Increased expenditure for marketing
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.0588	0.1692	0.0588
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.4706	0.4434	0.4706
3.Cover crops	0.4706	0.3874	0.4706

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Costs* the *Cover crop* element influences in highest degree the incentive *Cover crops* with a score of 0.7007. The incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* is also highly influenced by *Increasing short-term investments* with a score of 0.4600 and *Crop rotation* with a score of 0.7697. The incentive *Reduced soils processing techniques* is influenced strongly by *Precision agriculture* with a score of 0.5584.

Table 141 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Technological

Incentives/elements	Cover crops	Crop rotation	Increasing short-term investments	Precision agriculture
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.2021	0.7697	0.4600	0.3196
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.0972	0.0634	0.3189	0.5584
3.Cover crops	0.7007	0.1669	0.2211	0.1220

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic control* criteria in *Risks* the element *Increasing expenditures for soil health operations* prioritizes the incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with a score of 0.6370. The element *Increasing initial costs* influences the incentive *Reduced soils processing techniques* with a score of 0.6250. The last element *Increasing variable costs* shows the strong importance of the incentive *Cover crops* with a score of 0.7375.

Table 142 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations	Increasing initial costs	Increasing variable costs
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.6370	0.1365	0.1773
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.1047	0.6250	0.0852
3.Cover crops	0.2583	0.2385	0.7375

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic control* criteria in *Risks* the element *Access to finance* influences the incentive *Cover crops* with a score of 0.4286. The highest importance of the element *Barriers to change practices for health practices* is over the incentive *Cover crops* with 0.4126. The elements *Perceived risk* influence on incentive *Reduced soils processing techniques* with a score with 0,6250. The last element *Initial costs* prioritizes the incentive *Reduced soils processing techniques* with a score respectively 0.6250. These numbers underscore the significance of assistance programs in *Cover crops*.

Table 143 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Access to finance	Barriers to change practices for health practices	Initial costs	Perceived risk
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.1429	0.3275	0.1365	0.6908
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.4286	0.2599	0.6250	0.1488
3.Cover crops	0.4286	0.4126	0.2385	0.1603

Source: Own calculations

During the analysis of *Political control* criteria in *Risks* it is estimated that the element *Decreasing liquidity* has strongest influence over *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with a score of 0.6870. The highest importance of the element *Income decrease* and *Increasing the long term assets* is over the incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* with a score of 0.6870 and 0,7612. These insights highlight the strong impacts of *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* on business outcomes, emphasizing the need for tailored strategies to address specific challenges and risks.

Table 144 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Political

Incentives/elements	Decreasing liquidity	Income decrease	Increasing the long term assets
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.6870	0.6870	0.7612
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.1865	0.1865	0.0726
3.Cover crops	0.1265	0.1265	0.1662

Source: Own calculations

Phase 2: Influence of control criteria on the new incentives

The influence of the separate clusters is estimated relatively by comparing them in the control criteria. That means that if there is one cluster in the control criteria the weight of the cluster is 1. If there are more than one clusters, they are compared and weights are derived. All economics clusters have two clusters: Market linkages and Cost savings. Their weights are shown in the

table below. *Benefits* are assigned a weight of 0.6666 for both *Market linkages* and 0,3333 for *Cost saving*. *Opportunities* receive a weight of 0.5 for *Market linkages* and for *Cost saving*. *Costs* are weighted at 0.3333 for *Market linkages* and 0.6666 for *Cost saving*. *Risks* hold a weight of 0.3333 for *Market linkages* and 0.6666 for *Cost saving*. These numbers suggest that in both clusters (*Benefits* and *Opportunities*), *Market linkages* is relatively more significant, while *Costs saving* are given moderate importance.

Table 145 Relative weights of the clusters

Incentives/elements	Clusters	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risks
Economic	Market linkages	0.6666	0.5000	0.3333	0.3333
	Cost saving	0.3333	0.5000	0.6666	0.6666

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Benefits* the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* which is assigned a significant weight of 0.5272. The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is *Cover crops*, which is assigned a high score of 0.3874. The highest priority under the *Social* control criteria is *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a score of 0.6525. The highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a moderate weight of 0,4000. These results reflect a strong importance of the *Economic*, *Social* and *Technological* factors over the *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*.

Table 146 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under benefits

Incentives/elements	Economic	Political	Social	Technological
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.5272	0.2513	0.6525	0.4000
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.2771	0.3612	0.1163	0.2000
3.Cover crops	0.1957	0.3874	0.2312	0.4000

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Opportunities*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Cover crops*, which is assigned a weight of 0.3799. The highest priority under the *Social* control criteria is *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a weight of 0,5230. Lastly, the highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is again on *Cover crops* with a weight of 0.4843. These results

indicate a strong emphasis on *Cover crops* across Economic and Technological criteria.

Table 147 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under opportunities

Incentives/elements	Economic	Social	Technological
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.3765	0.5230	0.2130
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.2436	0.1335	0.3027
3.Cover crops	0.3799	0.3436	0.4843

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Costs*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control and *Technological* criteria's is *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, which is assigned a weight of 0.4097 and 0,4378. These results suggest a significant emphasis on *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*.

Table 148 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under costs

Incentives/elements	Economic	Technological
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.4097	0.4378
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.3759	0.2595
3.Cover crops	0.2144	0.3027

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Risks*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Cover crops*, which is assigned a weight of 0.3776. The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*, with a weight of 0.7117.

Table 149 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under risks

Incentives/elements	Economic	Political
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.3194	0.7117
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.3030	0.1485
3.Cover crops	0.3776	0.1398

Source: Own calculations

Phase 3: Determining the control criteria weights and their influence on new incentives

The table below represents the relative weights of control criteria, where *Economic* considerations hold the highest priority across *Costs* and *Risks*, emphasizing its overarching importance. Technological factors have moderate weights, particularly in *Opportunities*, reflecting the recognition of technological advancements in driving growth opportunities. While *Social* factors play a minor role. *Political* considerations are prominent in addressing *Benefits*, indicating a focus on regulatory and governance aspects to manage potential threats.

Table 150 Relative weights of the control criteria

Incentives/elements	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
Economic	0.2061	0.3695	0.6667	0.5000
Technological	0.0684	0.4067	0.3333	-
Social	0.2922	0.2238	-	-
Political	0.4334		-	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

This part of the analysis represents the priorities under *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs* and *Risks* after considering the relative weights of the control criteria. All of main blocks except *Opportunities* prioritize the incentive *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods*.

Table 151 Overall priorities

Incentives/blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.3984	0.3432	0.4187	0.4554
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.2813	0.2447	0.3388	0.2494
3.Cover crops	0.3203	0.4121	0.2425	0.2952

Source: Own calculations

Phase 4: Strategic criteria weighting and final result

The next step is to estimate the Strategic criteria influence over the four categories. This table presents a qualitative assessment of the three different strategic criteria – Environmental care, To protect food and health quality, Fostering knowledge and innovation over the categories *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs*, and *Risks*.

Table 152 Defining rating scale for strategic criteria

Blocks/strategic criteria	Environmental care	To protect food and health quality	Fostering knowledge

			and innovation
Benefits	Average	Average	Excellent
Opportunities	Above Average	Above Average	Above Average
Costs	Above Average	Excellent	Average
Risks	Average	Average	Below Average

Source: Own calculations

Based on the qualitative assessment the relative weights of the four blocks of the model are derived. *Opportunities* seems to have highest priority, followed by *Costs*, *Benefits* and *Risks*.

Table 153 Ratings for strategic criteria and BOCR priorities

Blocks/strategic criteria	TOTALS	PRIORITIES	Environmental care	To protect food and health quality	Fostering knowledge and innovation
1.Benefits	0.5374	0.2553	0.3061	0.3061	1.0000
2.Opportunities	0.6643	0.3156	0.6643	0.6643	0.6643
3.Costs	0.6568	0.3120	0.6643	1.0000	0.3061
4.Risks	0.2461	0.1169	0.3061	0.3061	0.1263

Source: Own calculations

The data in the table below presents priorities assigned to three different incentives. *Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods* is noted with a priority value of 0.1459, indicating a minor focus on ensuring adherence to organic production in the case study. *Reduced soils processing techniques* holds a priority value of 0.0532, suggesting a small emphasis on soil processing techniques. However, the highest priority value of 0.8007 is assigned to *Cover crops*, reflecting a strategic focus on this incentive.

Table 154 Overall outcome of BOCR

Incentives	Priorities
1.Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	0.1459
2.Reduced soils processing techniques	0.0532
3.Cover crops	0.8007

Source: Own calculations

3.7 Latvia: Crop production and animal farming

In this particular case study of Latvia, the main objective is to evaluate the potential of implementing agro-forestry practices to bolster soil health in

otherwise degraded farmland. There are three incentives which will be assessed. Incentive 1 is for Private investments from companies that would both benefit the farmer (improved soil health and profitability via agroforestry) and give positive image to the company that has given the investment. (corresponding to 1.12 Corporate social responsibility). Incentive 2 is for Establishing a marketing label/quality scheme, which would allow to sell both farming and forestry production under "Agroforestry" label, if these particular degraded areas are re-vitalised with principles mentioned in case study and certified accordingly. (corresponding to 1.8 Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards). Incentive 3 is for Establishing an eco-scheme under CAP strategic plan of Latvia, where there would be an incentivizing payment for every hectare of degraded land managed under Agroforestry practices. (corresponding to 2.4 Direct Payment for Ecosystem Services). From the point of view of the promoted business models in WP 2 this model is Payments for ES.

The new incentives are:

1. Private investments;
2. Establishing 'Agroforestry' label;
3. Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices.

Phase 1: Evaluation of the influence of the elements on the new incentives

The analysis starts with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Cost saving*. The first incentive for private investments has substantial influence on both *Decreasing variable cost* (0.5736) and *Gross margin increasing* (0.6301). According to the stakeholder's ratings the importance of *Better product production* is the same and moderate for all of the incentives. The importance of the element Higher retail price to the incentives Establishing 'Agroforestry' label is substantial with scoring of 0.7778

Table 155 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1.Private investments	0.3333	0.5736	0.6301	0.1111
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.3333	0.0650	0.2184	0.7778
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.3333	0.3614	0.1515	0.1111

Source: Own calculations

In the table below the analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Market linkages*. Here, the second incentive for Establishing

'Agroforestry' label has major influence on the element *Long Chain* (0.6666) *Producing Safe Food* (0.6000). Two of the elements in this cluster represent close influences on the other two incentives. For the element *GAPs*, moderate influence is observed for both incentives Private investments and Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices with the same score of 0.4546. Similar results are shown for the element *GMPs*, with the same score of 0.4286.

Table 156 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	GAPs	GMPs	Long chain	Producing safe food
1.Private investments	0.4546	0.4286	0.1667	0.2000
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.0909	0.1429	0.6666	0.6000
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.4546	0.4286	0.1667	0.2000

Source: Own calculations

For the control cluster *Political* in *Benefits* the influence of the elements over the incentives is in the table below. The incentive for private investments shows the highest scores in all elements in this cluster, except for the element *Soil health financial measures*, where the score is the same for the third incentive for Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices. This result shows the importance of enhancing private investments to benefit farmers' soil health performance.

Table 157 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Political

Incentives/elements	Better access to finance	Efficiency improvement	Improvement productivity	Soil health financial measures
1.Private investments	0.5769	0.6144	0.5769	0.4615
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.0811	0.1172	0.0811	0.0769
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.3420	0.2684	0.3420	0.4615

Source: Own calculations

Regarding the *Social* control criteria in *Benefits* the highest importance for the element *Informational campaigns* is for the second incentive - Establishing 'Agroforestry' label with score of 0.6875. As for the *Knowledge hubs* element the importance is the same for both Private investments and Establishing 'Agroforestry' label (0.4444).

Table 158 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Social

Incentives/elements	Informational campaigns	Knowledge hubs
1.Private investments	0.2623	0.4444
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.6875	0.4444
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.0501	0.1111

Source: Own calculations

The analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits, Technological* control criteria. The importance of *Knowledge of latest technologies* element is the same for all of the incentives. For the other element *Immediately available* the importance is the same for the both Private investments and "Agroforestry" label with moderate score of 0.4000.

Table 159 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Technological

Incentives/elements	Knowledge of latest technologies	Immediately available
1.Private investments	0.3333	0.4000
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.3333	0.4000
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.3333	0.2000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic* control criteria, *cost saving* cluster the *Initial costs* element have highest influence over incentive Private investments, scoring 0.6483, which appears to be very logical results. On the other hand, the *Long term return* influences the incentive for "Agroforestry" label with moderate scoring of 0.5000. The last element *Sustainable crop production* sees the same priority under all of the three incentives.

Table 160 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Initial costs	Long term return	Sustainable crop production
1.Private investments	0.6483	0.2500	0.3333
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.2297	0.5000	0.3333
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.1220	0.3333	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages*, the incentive for Private investments presents high importance for both of the elements in this

cluster - *Food demand* element with the moderate score of 0.4600, *Long term results* with substantial score of 0.6370.

Table 161 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Food demand	Long term results in food security
1.Private investments	0.4600	0.6370
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.2211	0.1047
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.3189	0.2583

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Opportunities*, *Fertilization* demonstrates moderate influence for both incentives Private investments and Agroforestry practices (both with scoring of 0.4286). On the other hand, *Sustainable soil management* shows the same results under the three incentives. *Soil remediation* element shows the most substantial influence on Private investments with score of 0.6267. These results show the importance of private investments in considering factors like fertilization and soil remediation as technological options.

Table 162 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Technological

Incentives/elements	Fertilization	Soil remediation	Sustainable soil management
1.Private investments	0.4286	0.6267	0.3333
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.1429	0.0936	0.3333
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.4286	0.2797	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Social* control criteria in *Opportunities*, the highest priorities of the elements are over the first incentive for Private investments. The most substantial score is for the element *Climate change* and *Soil quality* with score of 0.6250 and 0.7074 respectively. *Regulation of water cycle* shows influence also on the third incentive for Agroforestry practices with the same moderate results of 0.4000. These substantial results emphasize the importance of private investments for potential impacts on elements like climate r and water regulation, soil and biodiversity preservation.

Table 163 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Social

Incentives/elements	Biodiversity preservation	Climate change	Regulation of water cycle	Soil quality
1.Private investments	0.5584	0.6250	0.4000	0.7074

2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.1220	0.1365	0.2000	0.1700
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.3196	0.2385	0.4000	0.1226

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic control* criteria in *Costs*, *Better product quality* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.5584 over the incentive *Private investments*. For this incentive there is a substantial result for *Decreasing variable costs* with score of 0.6442. *Gross margin increasing* and *Higher retail price* substantially influences the incentive for 'Agroforestry' label with scores of 0.7143 and 0.7838 respectively.

Table 164 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1.Private investments	0.5584	0.6442	0.1429	0.1349
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.1220	0.0852	0.7143	0.7838
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.3196	0.2706	0.1429	0.0813

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic control* criteria in *Costs*, the incentive 'Agroforestry' label demonstrates the highest importance regarding the elements *Costs for information campaigns* (0.8000) and *Increased expenditure for marketing* (0.8182). This results underscore the significance of informational campaigns and marketing strategies for the success of incentives like this. *Developing nature-positive production* has the same importance for all of the three incentives.

Table 165 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Costs for information campaigns	Developing nature-positive production	Increased expenditure for marketing
1.Private investments	0.1000	0.3333	0.0909
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.8000	0.3333	0.8182
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.1000	0.3333	0.0909

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Costs* the *Cover crop* element influences in highest degree the incentive Private investments a score of 0.5396. The incentive is also moderately influenced by *Increasing short-term investments* with a score of 0.4286. The same score of this element is also for the second incentive for “Agroforestry” label. *Precision agriculture* elements has the same results over all of the incentives.

Table 166 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Technological

Incentives/elements	Cover crops	Crop rotation	Increasing short-term investments	Precision agriculture
1.Private investments	0.5396	0.3333	0.4286	0.3333
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.1634	0.3333	0.4286	0.3333
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.2970	0.3333	0.1429	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* the element *Increasing expenditures for soil health operations* prioritizes the incentive Private investments a score of 0.6667. The element *Increasing initial costs* influences both incentives for Private investments and 'Agroforestry' label with a score of 0.4286. The last element *Increasing variable costs* has the same results over all of the incentives.

Table 167 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations	Increasing initial costs	Increasing variable costs
1.Private investments	0.6667	0.4286	0.3333
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.1667	0.4286	0.3333
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.1667	0.1429	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic* control criteria the results vary across the three incentives. The element *Access to finance* influences with the highest score the incentive Agroforestry practices (0.6000). The highest importance of the element *Barriers to change practices for health practices* is over the incentive 'Agroforestry' label (0.6000). The element *Initial costs* prioritizes Private investments (0.5695), and finally *Perceived risk* shows average influence over 'Agroforestry' label incentive.

Table 168 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Access to finance	Barriers to change practices for health practices	Initial costs	Perceived risk
1.Private investments	0.2000	0.2000	0.5695	0.2500
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.2000	0.6000	0.3331	0.5000
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.6000	0.2000	0.0974	0.2500

Source: Own calculations

During the analysis of *Political control* criteria in *Risks* all of the three incentives presents with the same scores of 0.3333 for the elements *Decreasing liquidity* and *Income decrease*. The element *Increasing the long term assets* has the same moderate influence of 0.4444 for both incentives for Private investments and Agroforestry practices.

Table 169 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Political

Incentives/elements	Decreasing liquidity	Income decrease	Increasing the long term assets
1.Private investments	0.3333	0.3333	0.4444
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.3333	0.3333	0.1111
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.3333	0.3333	0.4444

Source: Own calculations

Phase 2: Influence of control criteria on the new incentives

The influence of the separate clusters is estimated relatively by comparing them in the control criteria. That means that if there is one cluster in the control criteria the weight of the cluster is 1. If there are more than one clusters, they are compared and weights are derived. All economics clusters have two clusters: Market linkages and Cost savings. Their weights are shown in table... *Benefits* are assigned a weight of 0.80 for both *Market linkages* and 0.20 for *Cost saving*. *Opportunities* receive a weight of 0.8571 for *Market linkages* and 0.1429 for *Cost saving*. *Costs* are weighted at 0.8 for *Market linkages* and 0.2 for *Cost saving*. *Risks* hold a weight of 0.8333 for *Market linkages* and 0.1667 for *Cost saving*. These numbers suggest that in both clusters, *Market linkages* is relatively more significant, while *Costs saving* are given moderate importance.

Table 170 Relative weights of the clusters

Control criteria	Clusters	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risks
Economic	Market linkages	0.8000	0.8571	0.8000	0.8333
	Cost saving	0.2000	0.1429	0.2000	0.1667

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Benefits* the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is 'Agroforestry' label with a moderate weight of 0,3698. The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is Private investments with average score of 0,5574. The highest priority under the *Social* control criteria is 'Agroforestry' label, with a score of 0,5660. Two of the incentives show the same moderate priority under the *Technological* control criteria.

Table 171 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under benefits

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political	Social	Technological
1.Private investments	0.3324	0.5574	0.3534	0.3667
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.3698	0.0891	0.5660	0.3667
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.2978	0.3535	0.0806	0.2667

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Opportunities*, the highest priority is for the incentive Private investments for all the control criteria. These results indicate a strong emphasis on such incentives across Economic, Social, and Technological criteria.

Table 172 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under opportunities

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Social	Technological
1.Private investments	0.5288	0.5727	0.4629
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.1903	0.1571	0.1899
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.2810	0.2702	0.3472

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Costs*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is 'Agroforestry' label, with a substantial weight of 0,6057. The highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is Private investments with moderate score of 0,4087. These results suggest a

significant emphasis on agroforestry labels with regard to the economic considerations.

Table 173 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under costs

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Technological
1.Private investments	0.2138	0.4087
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.6057	0.3147
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.1805	0.2766

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Risks*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is 'Agroforestry' label with weight of 0,3918, slightly higher than the one for Private investments. The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is the same for both Private investments and Agroforestry practices (0,3704).

Table 174 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under risks

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political
1.Private investments	0.3334	0.3704
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.3918	0.2593
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.2748	0.3704

Source: Own calculations

Phase 3: Determining the control criteria weights and their influence on new incentives

The table below represents the relative weights of control criteria, where *Economic* considerations hold the highest priority across *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs* and *Risks*, emphasizing its overarching importance. The *Social* factors play a moderate role with score of 0.4444 for *Opportunities*.

Table 175 Relative weights of the control criteria

Incentives/control criteria	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
Economic	0.4621	0.4444	0.8000	0.8333
Technological	0.1026	0.1111	0.2000	-
Social	0.3008	0.4444	-	-
Political	0.1344	-	-	0.1667

Source: Own calculations

In the table below are the priorities under *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs* and *Risks* after considering the relative weights of the control criteria. Three of the categories prioritize the incentive 'Agroforestry' label, where *Benefits* influence is with score of 0,3853, *Costs* - 0,5270, and *Risks* - 0,3687. *Opportunities* contribute with a highest score for the incentive for Private

investments with score of 0,5386. It should be noted that for both *Benefits* and *Risks*, the incentive for Private investments has very close moderate results of 0,3650 and 0,3400 respectively.

Table 176 Overall priorities

Incentives/control criteria	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
1.Private investments	0.3650	0.5386	0.2665	0.3400
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.3853	0.1764	0.5270	0.3687
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.2497	0.2850	0.2065	0.2915

Source: Own calculations

Phase 4: Strategic criteria weighting and final result

The next step is to estimate the Strategic criteria influence over the four categories. The estimation is subjective and is based on a focus group of experts from NBU. The estimation is made on 5-degree scale. This table presents a qualitative assessment of the three different strategic criteria – *To ensure a fair income for farmers*, *Environmental care* and *To preserve landscapes and biodiversity* over the categories *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs*, and *Risks*. Each criterion is evaluated based on its performance relative to others. In this case, in terms of *Benefits* all of the three strategic goals is rated with Above average score.

Table 177 Defining rating scale for strategic criteria

Blocks/strategic criteria	To ensure a fair income for farmers	Environmental care	To preserve landscapes and biodiversity
Benefits	Above Average	Above Average	Above Average
Opportunities	Average	Average	Below Average
Costs	Poor	Below Average	Below Average
Risks	Poor	Poor	Average

Source: Own calculations

Table 178 ratings for strategic criteria and BOCR priorities

Blocks/strategic criteria	TOTALS	PRIORITIES	To ensure a fair income	Environmental care	To preserve landscapes and biodiversity

			for farmers		
1.Benefits	0.6643	0.5720	0.6643	0.6643	0.6643
2.Opportunities	0.2462	0.2120	0.3061	0.3061	0.1263
3.Costs	0.1058	0.0911	0.0647	0.1263	0.1263
4.Risks	0.1452	0.1250	0.0647	0.0647	0.3061

Source: Own calculations

The data in the table below presents priorities assigned to three different incentives. Private investments have the highest priority of 0,4407, which prioritises the role of private investments among other options. Establishing 'Agroforestry' label is on the second place with score of 0,3034. Lastly, Agroforestry practices is noted with a priority value of 0.2932, indicating a moderate focus. This prioritization underscores a diversified approach that balances efforts towards private schemes, agroforestry labels and practices.

Table 179 Overall outcome of BOCR

Incentives	Priorities
1.Private investments	0.4407
2.Establishing 'Agroforestry' label	0.3034
3.Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices	0.2559

Source: Own calculations

3.8 Latvia: Forest management

Case study: Digital showcase, Latvia

This case study examines three incentives under the business model for creation of online map where fields with reduced soil tillage would be displayed publicly. The first incentive is for carbon credit certification schemes which incentivise farmers to collect and sell carbon credit as a part of reduced tillage and other soil-friendly practices. The second incentive is for quality schemes / private labelling where farmers' participation in quality scheme allows them to label their products if production methods are certified to be higher than baseline. This would lead to higher premium in supply chain. And finally, the third incentive is for financing from municipalities in a form of tax discounts if particular fields are farmed with soil-friendly practices. From the point of view of the promoted business models in WP 2 this model is Payments for ES.

The new incentives are:

1. Carbon credit schemes;
2. Private labelling;
3. Municipal tax discounts.

Phase 1: Evaluation of the influence of the elements on the new incentives

The analysis starts with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Cost saving* in the table below. According to the stakeholder's ratings the importance of *Better*

product production is high for the incentive *Private labelling* with result of 0.5782. The importance of the element *Decreasing variable cost* to the incentive *Carbon credit schemes* has a scoring of 0.4844. The influence of *Higher retail prices* receives a significant score of 0.8182 for the *Private labelling* incentive, where for the other two incentives the importance is minor. As for the element *Gross margin increasing* the score for all three incentives is moderate (0.3333).

Table 180 Influence of elements on the incentive under Benefits, Economic, Cost saving s

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.2627	0.4844	0.3333	0.0909
2. Private labelling	0.5782	0.0924	0.3333	0.8182
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.1591	0.4232	0.3333	0.0909

Source: Own calculations

In the table below the analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Market linkages*. For the element *GAPs*, the highest influence is observed in the context of the incentive *Municipal tax discounts*, scoring 0.5000. The other three elements show moderate to high score for the incentive *Private labelling*. Here, the element *Long Chain* has a significant score of 0.6667. The incentive for *Carbon credit schemes* presents moderately high score only for the element *GMPs* (Good Manufacturing Practices) - 0.4286. This consistent trend underscores the significant impact of private labelling across various elements of food production.

Table 181 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	GAPs	GMPs	Long chain	Producing safe food
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.2500	0.4286	0.1666	0.2500
2. Private labelling	0.2500	0.4286	0.6667	0.5000
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.5000	0.1429	0.1666	0.2500

Source: Own calculations

For the control cluster *Political* in *Benefits* the influence of the elements over the incentives in the table below, the incentive for *Carbon credit schemes* has the highest score for all of the elements in this cluster. The incentive for *Municipal tax discounts* presents moderate score of 0.4286 for the element *Soil health financial measures*. Here, the results put an emphasis on supporting carbon credit schemes in relation to better financial outcomes and productivity.

Table 182 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Political

Incentives/elements	Better access to finance	Efficiency improvement	Improvement productivity	Soil health financial measures
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.6833	0.7142	0.6000	0.4286
2. Private labelling	0.1169	0.1429	0.2000	0.1428
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.1998	0.1429	0.2000	0.4286

Source: Own calculations

Regarding the *Social* control criteria in *Benefits* the highest importance for the element *Informational campaigns* is for the *Private labelling* incentive of 0.6548. For *Informational campaigns*, the highest influence is observed over the incentive *Municipal tax discounts*, scoring 0.5000.

Table 183 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Social

Incentives/elements	Informational campaigns	Knowledge hubs
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.0953	0.2500
2. Private labelling	0.6548	0.2500
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.2499	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

In the table below we observe significant importance of the incentive for *Municipal tax discounts* with regards to the element *Immediately available* (0.6734). However, regarding the element *Knowledge of latest technologies* all three incentives scores the same (0.3333).

Table 184 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Technological

Incentives/elements	Knowledge of latest technologies	Immediately available
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.3333	0.2515
2. Private labelling	0.3333	0.0751
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.3333	0.6734

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities*, *Economic* control criteria, *cost saving* cluster the *Initial costs* element have highest influence over incentive *Private labelling*, scoring 0.6000. For the other two elements, all three incentives score the same results, where the highest score is for the incentives *Carbon credit schemes* (0.4286) and *Municipal tax discounts* (0.4286). This result suggests, that while long-term return and sustainable crop production is of higher relevance for carbon credit incentives and tax discounts, the initial costs are more significant in relation with private labelling incentives.

Table 185 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Initial costs	Long term return	Sustainable crop production
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.2000	0.4286	0.4286
2. Private labelling	0.6000	0.1429	0.1429
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.2000	0.4286	0.4286

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages, Food demand* element has the same moderate influence over both incentives *Private labelling* and *Municipal tax discounts* (0.4000). The element *Long term results in food security* has highest importance on *Private labelling* with 0.6000.

Table 186 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Food demand	Long term results in food security
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.2000	0.2000
2. Private labelling	0.4000	0.6000
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.4000	0.2000

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological control* criteria in *Opportunities*, the element *Soil remediation* has a significant score for the incentive *Carbon credit schemes*. The other two elements – *Fertilization* and *Sustainable soil management* demonstrate the same influence of 0.3333 for all of the three incentives. This result shows that with regards to the technological criteria soil remediation is the element that has the highest influence, especially in the case with incentive that target carbon farming.

Table 187 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Technological

Incentives/elements	Fertilization	Soil remediation	Sustainable soil management
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.3333	0.6000	0.3333
2. Private labelling	0.3333	0.2000	0.3333
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.3333	0.2000	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Social control* criteria in *Opportunities*, the results show similar scoring for almost all of the elements in this cluster for all three incentives. *Climate change, Regulation of the water cycle* and *Soil quality* have moderate impact on the incentives *Carbon credit schemes* and *Municipal tax*

discounts, where for the incentive *Private labelling* the impact is minor. However, *Biodiversity preservation* most significantly impacts the incentive *Carbon credit schemes* with score of 0.6483.

Table 188 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Social

Incentives/elements	Biodiversity preservation	Climate change	Regulation of water cycle	Soil quality
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.6483	0.4000	0.4444	0.4000
2. Private labelling	0.2297	0.2000	0.1111	0.2000
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.1220	0.4000	0.4444	0.4000

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic control criteria in Costs*, the elements vary for all of the incentives. The incentive *Carbon credit schemes* has a highest score for the element *Better product quality* (0.6666) and moderate score for the element *Gross margin increasing* (0.4579). The element *Decreasing variable costs* prioritizes *Municipal tax discounts* with a score of 0.4579. Finally, *Higher retail price* presents the most significant influence on the incentive *Private labelling* with score of 0.8000, which is a logical result regarding this incentive.

Table 189 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.6666	0.4161	0.4579	0.1000
2. Private labelling	0.1667	0.1260	0.1260	0.8000
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.1667	0.4579	0.4161	0.1000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic control criteria in Costs*, the elements *Costs for information campaigns* as well as *Increased expenditure for marketing* demonstrate the highest influence with a score of 0.6910 over the incentive *Private labelling*. The element *Developing nature-positive production* presents equal score for all of the incentives (0.3333). These numbers underscore the significance of private labels for investing in informational and marketing campaigns.

Table 190 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Costs for information campaigns	Developing nature-positive production	Increased expenditure for marketing
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.0914	0.3333	0.0914

2.Private labelling	0.6910	0.3333	0.6910
3.Municipal tax discounts	0.2176	0.3333	0.2176

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Costs*, the elements *Cover crop* and *Precision agriculture* influences in highest degree the incentive *Carbon credit schemes* with a score of 0.6370 and 0.6000 respectively, which show their relevance for the functioning of such schemes. Regarding the element *Increasing short-term investments* the highest score is for the incentive *Private labelling* (0.6667). The *Crop rotation* element has equal influence on all of the three incentives (0.3333).

Table 191 Influence of elements on the incentives under *Costs, Technological*

Incentives/elements	Cover crops	Crop rotation	Increasing short-term investments	Precision agriculture
1.Carbon credit schemes	0.6370	0.3333	0.1666	0.6000
2.Private labelling	0.1047	0.3333	0.6667	0.2000
3.Municipal tax discounts	0.2583	0.3333	0.1666	0.2000

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks*, the element *Increasing expenditures for soil health operations* prioritizes the incentive *Private labelling* with a score of 0.5278. The elements *Increasing initial costs* and *Increasing variable costs* present equal influence on both incentives *Carbon credit schemes* and *Private labelling* (0.4444).

Table 192 Influence of elements on the incentives under *Risks, Economic, Cost saving*

Incentives/elements	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations	Increasing initial costs	Increasing variable costs
1.Carbon credit schemes	0.2627	0.4444	0.4444
2.Private labelling	0.5782	0.4444	0.4444
3.Municipal tax discounts	0.1591	0.1111	0.1111

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* the element *Access to finance* influences the incentive *Municipal tax discounts* with a score of 0.6817. The highest influence of the element *Initial costs* is for *Carbon credit schemes* and *Private labelling* (0.4444 for both). The element *Perceived risk* prioritizes the incentive *Private labelling* with a score 0.6571. *Barriers to change practices for health practices* presents equal influence on all of the three incentives.

Table 193 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/elements	Access to finance	Barriers to change practices for health practices	Initial costs	Perceived risk
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.2363	0.3333	0.4444	0.1466
2. Private labelling	0.0819	0.3333	0.4444	0.6571
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.6817	0.3333	0.1111	0.1963

Source: Own calculations

During the analysis of *Political control* criteria in *Risks* it is estimated that the element *Decreasing liquidity* has strongest influence over *Carbon credit schemes* incentive with a score of 0.7672. The highest importance of the element *Income decrease* is observed over two of the incentives – *Private labelling* and *Municipal tax discounts* (0.4444). *Increasing the long term assets for health practices* presents equal influence on all of the three incentives.

Table 194 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Political

Incentives/elements	Decreasing liquidity	Income decrease	Increasing the long term assets
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.7672	0.2000	0.3333
2. Private labelling	0.0806	0.4000	0.3333
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.1522	0.4000	0.3333

Source: Own calculations

Phase 2: Influence of control criteria on the new incentives

The influence of the separate clusters is estimated relatively by comparing them in the control criteria. That means that if there is one cluster in the control criteria the weight of the cluster is 1. If there are more than one clusters, they are compared and weights are derived. All economics clusters have two clusters: *Market linkages* and *Cost savings*. Their weights are shown in the table below. *Benefits* are assigned a weight of 0.8889 for *Market linkages* and 0.1111 for *Cost saving*. *Opportunities* receive a weight of 0.8333 for *Market linkages* and 0.1666 for *Cost saving*. *Costs* are weighted at 0.8 for *Market linkages* and 0.2 for *Cost saving*. *Risks* hold a weight of 0.8571 for *Market linkages* and 0.1429 for *Cost saving*. These numbers suggest that in both clusters, *Market linkages* is relatively more significant, while *Costs saving* are given moderate importance.

Table 195 relative weights of the clusters

Control criteria	Clusters	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risks
Economic	Market linkages	0.8889	0.8333	0.8000	0.8571
	Cost saving	0.1111	0.1666	0.2000	0.1429

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Benefits* the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Private labelling* which is assigned a moderate weight of 0,4607. The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is *Carbon credit schemes* with score of 0,6065. The highest priority under the *Social* control criteria is *Private labelling*, with a score of 0,4524. The highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is *Municipal tax discounts*, with a moderate weight of 0,5034. These results reflect that economic and social factors have strong importance for private labels, where political is of more importance for developing carbon farming. On the other hand, technological factors affect to greater extent incentives like tax discounts.

Table 196 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under benefits

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political	Social	Technological
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.2759	0.6065	0.1727	0.2924
2. Private labelling	0.4607	0.1506	0.4524	0.2042
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.2634	0.2428	0.3749	0.5034

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Opportunities*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Private labelling*, which is assigned a weight of 0,4659. Regarding the incentive *Carbon credit schemes* the highest priority is for the *Social* and *Technological* control criteria, with weight of 0,4732 and 0,4222 respectively.

Table 197 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under opportunities

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Social	Technological
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.2254	0.4732	0.4222
2. Private labelling	0.4659	0.1852	0.2889
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.3087	0.3416	0.2889

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Costs*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Private labelling*, with weight of 0. 0,5183. The highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is *Carbon credit schemes*, with a weight of 0,4342.

Table 198 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under costs

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Technological
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.2197	0.4342
2. Private labelling	0.5183	0.3262
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.2620	0.2396

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Risks*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria there is a very small difference among the three incentives. Still, the highest priority is on the incentive Private labelling (0,3949). The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is *Carbon credit schemes*, with a weight of 0,4335. These results suggest average concern for risks associated carbon credits and private labels within economic and political consideration.

Table 199 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under risks

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.3036	0.4335
2. Private labelling	0.3949	0.2713
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.3015	0.2952

Source: Own calculations

Phase 3: Determining the control criteria weights and their influence on new incentives

The table below represents the relative weights of control criteria, where *Economic* considerations hold the highest priority across *Costs* and *Risks*, emphasizing its overarching importance. Technological factors have moderate weights in *Benefits*, where the *Social* factors play a significant role in *Opportunities*.

Table 200 Relative weights of the control criteria

Control criteria/blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
Economic	0.0385	0.0754	0.8000	0.8333
Technological	0.4456	0.2291	0.2000	0.1667
Social	0.3177	0.6955	-	-
Political	0.1982	-	-	-

Source: Own calculations

In the table below are presented the priorities under *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs* and *Risks* after considering the relative weights of the control criteria. *Benefits* influence is with score of with 0,4056 for the incentive *Municipal tax discounts*. *Opportunities* contribute with a bit more - 0,4420 regarding the incentive for *Carbon credit schemes*. *Costs* and *Risks* play moderate role for the incentive *Private labelling* with score of 0,4742 and 0,3758 respectively.

Table 201 Overall priorities

Incentives/blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.3010	0.4420	0.2690	0.3236
2. Private labelling	0.2934	0.2320	0.4742	0.3758
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.4056	0.3260	0.2568	0.3006

Source: Own calculations

Phase 4: Strategic criteria weighting and final result

The next step is to estimate the Strategic criteria influence over the four categories. The estimation is subjective and is based on a focus group of experts from NBU. The estimation is made on 5-degree scale. This table presents a qualitative assessment of the three different strategic criteria – *Environmental care*, *To preserve landscapes and biodiversity* and *To protect food and health quality* over the categories *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs*, and *Risks*. Each criterion is evaluated based on its performance relative to others. For instance, in terms of *Benefits*, the strategic goals *To ensure a fair income for farmers*, *To improve the position of farmers in the food chain*, and *Environmental Care* are rated as Above Average.

Table 202 Defining rating scale for strategic criteria

Blocks/strategic criteria	To ensure a fair income for farmers	To improve the position of farmers in the food chain	Environmental care
Benefits	Above Average	Above Average	Above Average
Opportunities	Average	Average	Below Average
Costs	Poor	Below Average	Below Average
Risks	Poor	Poor	Average

Source: Own calculations

The table below summarizes the relative weights of the strategic criteria and in column Totals are the final weights.

Table 203 ratings for strategic criteria and BOCR priorities

Blocks/strategic criteria	TOTALS	PRIORITIES	To ensure a fair income for farmers	To improve the position of farmers in the food chain	Environmental care
1. Benefits	0.6643	0.5720	0.6643	0.6643	0.6643
2. Opportunities	0.2462	0.2120	0.3061	0.3061	0.1263
3. Costs	0.1058	0.0911	0.0647	0.1263	0.1263
4. Risks	0.1452	0.1250	0.0647	0.0647	0.3061

Source: Own calculations

The data in the table below presents priorities assigned to three different incentives. *Carbon credit schemes* is noted with a priority value of 0,3585. *Private labelling* holds a priority value of 0,2150. The highest priority is for the incentive *Municipal tax discounts* - 0,4265.

Table 204 Overall outcome of BOCR

Incentives	Priorities
1. Carbon credit schemes	0.3585
2. Private labelling	0.2150
3. Municipal tax discounts	0.4265

Source: Own calculations

3.9 Germany: CO₂-Land

“CO₂-Land” is a newly established carbon farming initiative in south-western Germany offering carbon credit certificates enabled by carbon sequestration on partner farms. The case study will focus on learning from experiences in the initiative by exploring success factors to foster similar projects across Europe, facilitating potential upscaling of the concept. It will also investigate the acceptance of the concept among farmers and society as a precondition for upscaling, along with ways to increase its acceptance. From the point of view of the promoted business models in WP 2 this model is Carbon markets.

The new incentives are:

1. Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most;
2. Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant;
3. Impact Funds for consultation.

Phase 1: Evaluation of the influence of the elements on the new incentives

The analysis starts with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Cost saving*. According to the stakeholders' ratings the importance of *Better product production* is high for the incentive *Impact Funds for consultation* with result of 0.4934. The importance of the element *Decreasing variable cost* to the incentives *Impact Funds for consultation* is similar with scoring 0.4444. Furthermore, in the case of the element *Increasing gross margin* holds the highest priority over *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant*, with a score of 0.5278. The influence of *Higher retail prices* varies significantly across different incentives, with the highest over the incentive *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant*, with a score of 0.4126.

Table 205 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/elements	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1. Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.1958	0.4444	0.1397	0.2599
2. Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.3108	0.1111	0.5278	0.4126
3. Impact Funds for consultation	0.4934	0.4444	0.3325	0.3275

Source: Own calculations

In the table below the analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Market linkages*. For the element *GAPs*, the highest influence is observed in the context of the incentive *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most*, scoring 0.4126. For the element *GMPs* (Good Manufacturing Practices), the incentive *Impact Funds for consultation* exhibits the highest priority, scoring 0.6337. *Long Chain* also sees its highest importance in *Impact Funds for consultation*, with a score of 0.4836. Finally, *Producing Safe Food* demonstrates the highest influence once again in *Impact Funds for consultation*, scoring 0.4286. This consistent trend underscores the significant impact of assistance provided under Impact Funds for consultation.

Table 206 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/control criteria	GAPs	GMPs	Long chain	Producing safe food
1. Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.4126	0.1744	0.1677	0.1429
2. Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.3275	0.1919	0.3487	0.4286
3. Impact Funds for consultation	0.2599	0.6337	0.4836	0.4286

Source: Own calculations

For the control cluster *Political* in *Benefits* the influence of the elements over the incentives is in the table below. For the elements *Better access to finance* and *Soil health financial* measures the highest influence is consistently observed in the incentive *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most*. The element *Efficiency improvement* prioritizes the incentive *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant* with 0.7143. The element *Improvement productivity* impose on incentive *Impact Funds for consultation* with weights of 0.6046.

Table 207 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Political

Incentives/control criteria	Better access to finance	Efficiency improvement	Improvement productivity	Soil health financial measures
1.Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.4742	0.1429	0.1048	0.4934
2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.1494	0.7143	0.2906	0.1958
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.3764	0.1429	0.6046	0.3108

Source: Own calculations

Regarding the *Social* control criteria in *Benefits* the highest importance is the same for each element. For *Informational campaigns*, the highest influence is observed over the incentive *Impact Funds for consultation*, scoring 0.6586. *Knowledge hubs* element prioritizes the incentive *Impact Funds for consultation* with a score of 0.7089.

Table 208 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Social

Incentives/control criteria	Informational campaigns	Knowledge hubs
1.Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.1562	0.1786
2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.1852	0.1125
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.6586	0.7089

Source: Own calculations

In the table below the analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits, Technological* control criteria. The importance of *Knowledge of latest technologies* element is highest for the incentive *Impact Funds for consultation* with 0.5936. Both incentives *Impact Funds for consultation* and *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most* have highest score according *Immediately available* element with score 0.4000.

Table 209 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Technological

Incentives/control criteria	Knowledge of latest technologies	Immediately available

1.Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.2493	0.4000
2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.1571	0.2000
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.5936	0.4000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic* control criteria, *cost saving* cluster the *Initial costs* element have highest influence over incentive *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant*, scoring 0.4434. The other two elements *Long term return* and *Sustainable crop production* exhibit the highest importance, scoring respectively 0.4126 and 0.4934 for incentive *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most*.

Table 210 Influence of elements on the incentives under *Opportunities, Economic, Cost saving*

Incentives/control criteria	Initial costs	Long term return	Sustainable crop production
1.Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.3874	0.4126	0.4934
2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.4434	0.2599	0.3108
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.1692	0.3275	0.1958

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages, Food demand* element has the highest influence over *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most* with a result of 0.4434. The element *Long term results in food security* has highest importance on *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant* with 0.4434.

Table 211 Influence of elements on the incentives under *Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages*

Incentives/control criteria	Food demand	Long term results in food security
1.Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.4434	0.3874
2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.3874	0.4434

3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.1692	0.1692
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Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Opportunities*, *Fertilization* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.5584 over the incentive *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant*. The element *Soil remediation* with 0.5750, indicating their significant impact on *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most*. *Sustainable soil management* also shows notable influence, albeit slightly lower, with a score of 0.4934, suggesting its importance in the context of the same incentive.

Table 212 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Technological

Incentives/control criteria	Fertilization	Soil remediation	Sustainable soil management
1.Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.3196	0.5750	0.4934
2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.5584	0.3043	0.3108
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.1220	0.1207	0.1958

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Social* control criteria in *Opportunities*, the highest priorities of the elements are over different incentives. *Biodiversity preservation* most significantly impacts the incentive *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most*, with a score of 0.6571. *Climate change* notably influences on the same incentive with score 0.4742. The element *Regulation of the water cycle* sees its greatest influence over *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant*, with score of 0.4665. Finally, *Soil quality* has highest influence on *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most*, with a score of 0.4067. These highest numbers in each column signify the varied impacts of different elements on different environmental factors, emphasizing the importance of tailored approaches to address specific challenges.

Table 213 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Social

Incentives/contr ol criteria	Biodiversity preservation	Climate change	Regulation of water cycle	Soil quality
1.Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without	0.6571	0.4742	0.4330	0.4067

vegetation during the most				
2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.1963	0.3764	0.4665	0.3695
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.1466	0.1494	0.1005	0.2238

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Costs*, *Better product quality* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.4126 over the incentive *Impact Funds for consultation*. The other three elements prioritize *Impact Funds for consultation* with a score of 0.4067, 0.4934 and 0.5000. These numbers underscore the significance of assistance programs for *Impact Funds for consultation*.

Table 214 Influence of elements on the incentives under *Costs*, *Economic*, *Cost saving*

Incentives/control criteria	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1.Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.3275	0.3695	0.3108	0.2500
2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.2599	0.2238	0.1958	0.2500
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.4126	0.4067	0.4934	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Costs*, the incentive *Impact Funds for consultation* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.6667 from the element *Costs for information campaigns*. The element *Developing nature-positive production* has high importance over the incentive *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most* with a score of 0.4934 and *Increased expenditure for marketing on Impact Funds for consultation* with a score of 0.5000. The incentive *Impact Funds for consultation* is influenced to the highest degree.

Table 215 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/control criteria	Costs for information campaigns	Developing nature-positive production	Increased expenditure for marketing
1. Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.1667	0.4934	0.2500
2. Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.1667	0.3108	0.2500
3. Impact Funds for consultation	0.6667	0.1958	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Costs* the *Cover crop* element influences in highest degree the incentive *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most* with a score of 0.7504. The second incentive *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant* is also highly influenced by *Increasing short-term investments* with a score of 0.5499 and *Precision agriculture* with a score of 0.5842. The last incentive *Impact Funds for consultation* and impose by *Crop rotation* with a score of 0.6092. These numbers underscore the significance of assistance programs in *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant*, such as *Increasing short term investments*.

Table 216 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Technological

Incentives/control criteria	Cover crops	Crop rotation	Increasing short term investments	Precision agriculture
1. Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.7504	0.3112	0.2402	0.1350
2. Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.0782	0.0795	0.5499	0.5842
3. Impact Funds for consultation	0.1713	0.6092	0.2098	0.2808

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* the element *Increasing expenditures for soil health operations* prioritizes the incentive *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing*

media and plant with a score of 0.5714. The element *Increasing initial costs* influences the same incentive with a score of 0.4934. The last element *Increasing variable costs* confirms the importance of the same incentive with a score of 0.5396. These numbers underscore the significance of assistance programs in *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant*.

Table 217 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/control criteria	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations	Increasing initial costs	Increasing variable costs
1. Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.1429	0.3108	0.2970
2. Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant	0.5714	0.4934	0.5396
3. Impact Funds for consultation	0.2857	0.1958	0.1634

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* the element *Access to finance* influences the incentive *Impact Funds for consultation* with a score of 0.5000. The highest importance of the element *Barriers to change practices for health practices* is over the incentive *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most* with 0.4000 and *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most* with 0.4000. The elements *Perceived risk* and *Initial costs* prioritizes the incentive *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant* with a score respectively 0.6098 and 0.5278. These numbers underscore the significance of assistance programs in mitigating perceived risks, barriers to change practices and addressing initial costs, and the importance of *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant*.

Table 218 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/control criteria	Access to finance	Barriers to change practices for health practices	Initial costs	Perceived risk
1. Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.2500	0.4000	0.3325	0.1655

2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant	0.2500	0.4000	0.5278	0.6098
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.5000	0.2000	0.1396	0.2247

Source: Own calculations

During the analysis of *Political control* criteria in *Risks* it is estimated that the element *Decreasing liquidity* has strongest influence over *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant* incentive with a score of 0.6908. The highest importance of the element *Income decrease* is over the incentive *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant* with a score of 0.6144. The element *Increasing the long term assets* has the same moderate influence of 0.4126 to the same incentive. These insights highlight the strong impacts of *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant* on business outcomes, emphasizing the need for tailored strategies to address specific challenges and risks.

Table 219 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Political

Incentives/control criteria	Decreasing liquidity	Income decrease	Increasing the long term assets
1.Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.1603	0.2684	0.3275
2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant	0.6908	0.6144	0.4126
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.1488	0.1172	0.2599

Source: Own calculations

Phase 2: Influence of control criteria on the new incentives

The influence of the separate clusters is estimated relatively by comparing them in the control criteria. That means that if there is one cluster in the control criteria the weight of the cluster is 1. If there are more than one clusters, they are compared and weights are derived. All economics clusters have two clusters: Market linkages and Cost savings. Their weights are shown in table... *Benefits* are assigned a weight of 0.5 for both *Market linkages* and *Cost saving*. *Opportunities* receive a weight of 0.5 for *Market linkages* and 0.5 for *Cost saving*. *Costs* are weighted at 0.3333 for *Market linkages* and 0.6667 for *Cost saving*. *Risks* hold a weight of 0.25 for *Market linkages* and 0.75 for *Cost saving*. These numbers suggest that in both clusters, *Market linkages* is relatively more moderate, while *Costs saving* are given significant importance.

Table 220 relative weights of the clusters

Control criteria	Clusters	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risks
Economic	Market linkages	0.5000	0.5000	0.3333	0.2500
	Cost saving	0.5000	0.5000	0.6667	0.7500

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Benefits* the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Impact Funds for consultation* which is assigned a significant weight of 0.4255. All the rest control criteria have highest priority for the same incentive *Impact Funds for consultation*. These results reflect a strong importance of the *Economic*, *Political* and *Technological* factors over the on supporting products eligible of *Impact Funds for consultation*.

Table 221 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under benefits

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political	Social	Technological
1. Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.2422	0.3038	0.1674	0.3247
2. Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.3324	0.3375	0.1488	0.1785
3. Impact Funds for consultation	0.4255	0.3587	0.6838	0.4968

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Opportunities*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most*, which is assigned a weight of 0.4233. The highest priority under the *Social* and *Technological* control criteria is again *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most*, with a weights respectively of 0.4928 and 0.4627. These results indicate a strong emphasis on *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most* across *Economic*, *Social*, and *Technological* criteria.

Table 222 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under opportunities

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Social	Technological
1. Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.4233	0.4928	0.4627

2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.3767	0.3522	0.3912
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.2000	0.1551	0.1462

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Costs*, the highest priority under the *Impact Funds for consultation*, which is assigned a weight of 0.4535. The highest priority under the *Technological control criteria* is *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most*, with a weight of 0.3592.

Table 223 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under costs

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Technological
1.Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.3107	0.3592
2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.2358	0.3230
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.4535	0.3178

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Risks*, the highest priority under the *Economic and Political control criteria* is *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant*, which is respectively weight of 0.5128 and 0.5726. These results suggest average concern for risks associated with *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant* within economic and political considerations.

Table 224 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under risks

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political
1.Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.2594	0.2521
2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.5128	0.5726
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.2278	0.1753

Source: Own calculations

Phase 3: Determining the control criteria weights and their influence on new incentives

The table below represents the relative weights of control criteria, where *Economic* considerations hold the highest priority across *Benefits*, *Costs* and *Risks*. *Technological* criteria have highest priority in *Opportunities*.

Table 225 Relative weights of the control criteria

Control criteria/blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
Economic	0.2994	0.3487	0.7500	0.8000
Technological	0.2530	0.4836	0.2500	-
Social	0.2087	0.1677	-	-
Political	0.2389	-	-	0.2000

Source: Own calculations

In the table below are presented the priorities under *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs* and *Risks* after considering the relative weights of the control criteria. All four categories prioritize different incentives. The incentive *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most* has influence of *Opportunities* with score 0.4526. *Benefits* influence on *Impact Funds for consultation* with rating 0.4578. *Costs* also play a significant role on *Impact Funds for consultation*, representing 0.5238 of the influence. While *Risks*, though slightly less impactful, contribute 0.5238 to the overall influence on *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant*.

Table 226 Overall priorities

Incentives/blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
1.Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.2698	0.4526	0.3251	0.2581
2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.2724	0.3798	0.2616	0.5238
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.4578	0.1676	0.4133	0.2182

Source: Own calculations

Phase 4: Strategic criteria weighting and final result

The next step is to estimate the Strategic criteria influence over the four categories. The estimation is subjective and is based on a focus group of experts from NBU. The estimation is made on 5-degree scale. This table presents a qualitative assessment of the three different strategic criteria – *Environmental care*, *To preserve landscapes and biodiversity* and *To protect food and health quality* over the categories *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs*, and *Risks*. Each criterion is evaluated based on its performance relative to others. For instance, in terms of *Benefits*, *Environmental Care* is rated as *Below Average*, while *Opportunities* in *To preserve landscapes and biodiversity* are deemed *Excellent*.

Table 227 Defining rating scale for strategic criteria

Blocks/strategic criteria	Climate change	Environmental care	Fostering knowledge	To ensure fair
Benefits	Above average	Above average	Above average	Above average
Opportunities	Excellent	Above average	Above average	Above average
Costs	Average	Average	Average	Average
Risks	Below average	Average	Average	Average

Source: Own calculations

In the table below we can observe the summarized relative weights of the strategic criteria and in column Totals are the final weights.

Table 228 ratings for strategic criteria and BOCR priorities

Blocks/strategic criteria	1.Benefits	2.Opportunities	3.Costs	4.Risks
TOTALS	0.6643	0.7111	0.3061	0.2810
PRIORITIES	0.3384	0.3623	0.1559	0.1432
Climate change	0.6643	1.0000	0.3061	0.1263
Environmental care	0.6643	0.6643	0.3061	0.3061
Fostering knowledge	0.6643	0.6643	0.3061	0.3061
To ensure fair	0.6643	0.6643	0.3061	0.3061

Source: Own calculations

The data in the table below presents priorities assigned to three different incentives. *Impact Funds for consultation* is noted with a priority value of 0.2906. *Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant* holds a priority value of 0.2959. However, the highest priority value of 0.4134 is assigned to *Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most*. This prioritization underscores a diversified approach that balances efforts towards application of fertilizers and consultations compare with the stress on minimum ground cover to avoid soil without vegetation.

Table 229 Overall outcome of BOCR

Incentives	Priorities
1.Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most	0.4134
2.Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. soil additives. growing media and plant	0.2959
3.Impact Funds for consultation	0.2906

Source: Own calculations

3.10 Estonia: Crop production

ETKI is a state research and development institute in the area of governance of the Estonian Ministry of Rural Affairs. Among others, ETKI researches impact of catch crops, tillage technologies and fertilizing on soil physical, chemical and biological properties. The crop production technologies and machinery use are analyzed to assess their impact on the environment and farms economy. ETKI cooperates with other organizations, which are developing digital maps on the basis of soil properties. These tools help to choose crops on fields, show fields soil texture, carbon stock, moisture level or erosion level. The usability of these digital maps to develop new business models aiming at adding value to soil conservation should be investigated. From the point of view of the promoted business models in WP 2 this model is Value chain.

The new incentives are:

1. Marketing labels;
2. Voluntary farm set-asides;

Phase 1: Evaluation of the influence of the elements on the new incentives

The analysis will begin with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Cost saving*. According to the stakeholders' ratings the importance of *Better product production* is very high for the incentive *Marketing labels* with result of 0.9. The importance of the element *Decreasing variable cost* to the incentives *Voluntary farm set-asides* is scoring 0.8750. Furthermore, in the case of the element *Increasing gross margin* and *Higher retail prices* holds the highest priority over *Marketing labels*, with a score respectively of 0.75 and 0.9.

Table 230 Influence of elements on the incentives under *Benefits, Economic, Cost saving*

Incentives/elements	Code	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1.Marketing labels		0.9000	0.1250	0.7500	0.9000
2.Voluntary farm set-asides		0.1000	0.8750	0.2500	0.1111

Source: Own calculations

In the table below, the analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits*, control criteria *Economic*, cluster *Market linkages*. For the element *GAPs* and *Long chain*, the highest influence is observed in the context of the incentive *Marketing labels* and *Marketing labels*, scoring with the same result 0.5. Similarly, for the element *GMPs* (*Good Manufacturing Practices*) and *Producing Safe Food*, the incentive *Marketing labels* exhibits the highest priority, scoring 0.8750 and 0.75 respectively. This consistent trend underscores the significant impact of *Marketing labels*.

Table 231 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/control criteria	GAPs	GMPs	Long chain	Producing safe food
1.Marketing labels	0.5000	0.8750	0.5000	0.7500
2.Voluntary farm set-asides	0.5000	0.1250	0.5000	0.2500

Source: Own calculations

For the control cluster *Political* in *Benefits* the influence of the elements over the incentives is in the table below. For the elements *Better access to finance*, *Efficiency improvement* and *Soil health financial measures* the highest influence is consistently observed in the incentive *Marketing labels*. Specifically, weights of 0.9 for *Better access to finance*, 0.5 for *Efficiency improvement*, 0.75 for *Soil health financial measures*. The element *Improvement productivity* prioritizes the incentive *Voluntary farm set-asides* with 0.75. For this incentive *Efficiency improvement* also impose with 0.5.

Table 232 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Political

Incentives/control criteria	Better access to finance	Efficiency improvement	Improvement productivity	Soil health financial measures
1.Marketing labels	0.9000	0.5000	0.2500	0.7500
2.Voluntary farm set-asides	0.1111	0.5000	0.7500	0.2500

Source: Own calculations

Regarding the *Social* control criteria in *Benefits* the highest importance is the same for each element. For *Informational campaign* and *Knowledge hubs* have the highest over the incentive *Marketing labels*, scoring 0.8333.

Table 233 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Social

Incentives/control criteria	Informational campaigns	Knowledge hubs
1.Marketing labels	0.8333	0.8333
2.Voluntary farm set-asides	0.1700	0.1700

Source: Own calculations

In the table below the analysis continues with description of the influence of the elements over the incentives for the *Benefits, Technological* control criteria. The importance of *Knowledge of latest technologies* element is highest for the incentive *Voluntary farm set-asides* with 0.9. *Both* incentives *Marketing labels* and *Voluntary farm set-asides* schemes have highest score according *Immediately available* element with score 0.5.

Table 234 Influence of elements on the incentives under Benefits, Technological

Incentives/control criteria	Knowledge of latest technologies	Immediately available
1. Marketing labels	0.1000	0.5000
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.9000	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities*, *Economic* control criteria, *cost saving* cluster the *Initial costs* and *Sustainable crop production* elements have equal influence over two incentives *Marketing labels* and *Voluntary farm set-asides* schemes, scoring 0.5. Similarly, for *Long term return*, *Marketing labels* exhibits the highest importance, scoring 0.75.

Table 235 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/control criteria	Initial costs	Long term return	Sustainable crop production
1. Marketing labels	0.5000	0.7500	0.5000
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.5000	0.2500	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Opportunities*, *Economic*, *Market linkages*, *Food demand* and *Long term results in food security* elements have the highest influence over *Marketing labels* with a result of 0.9.

Table 236 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/control criteria	Food demand	Long term results in food security
1. Marketing labels	0.9000	0.9000
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.1000	0.1000

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Opportunities*, *Fertilization*, *Soil remediation* and *Sustainable soil management* demonstrates the equal influence with a score of 0.5 over the two incentives *Marketing labels* and *Voluntary farm set-asides*.

Table 237 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Technological

Incentives/control criteria	Fertilization	Soil remediation	Sustainable soil management
1. Marketing labels	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Social control* criteria in *Opportunities*, the highest priorities of the elements are over different incentives. *Biodiversity preservation* and *Regulation of water cycle* have the most significantly impacts the incentive *Voluntary farm set-asides*, with a score of 0.8333. *Climate change* and *Soil quality* have equal influences on the incentives *Marketing labels* and *Voluntary farm set-asides*, both scoring 0.5. These highest numbers in each column signify the varied impacts of different elements on different environmental factors, emphasizing the importance of *Voluntary farm set-asides*.

Table 238 Influence of elements on the incentives under Opportunities, Social

Incentives/control criteria	Biodiversity preservation	Climate change	Regulation of water cycle	Soil quality
1. Marketing labels	0.1666	0.5000	0.1666	0.5000
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.8333	0.5000	0.8333	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic control* criteria in *Costs*, *Better product quality* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.8750 over the incentive *Marketing labels*. The element *Decreasing variable costs* prioritizes *Voluntary farm set-asides* with a score of 0.8750. *Gross margin increasing* moderately influences *Marketing labels* with a score of 0.8571. Finally, *Higher retail price* influences *Marketing labels* with a score of 0.9. These numbers underscore the significance of assistance programs in enhancing product quality and reducing costs, highlighting their role of marketing labels.

Table 239 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/control criteria	Better product quality	Decreasing variable costs	Gross margin increasing	Higher retail price
1. Marketing labels	0.8750	0.1250	0.8571	0.9000
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.1250	0.8750	0.1430	0.1000

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic control* criteria in *Costs*, the element *Costs for information campaigns* demonstrates the highest influence with a score of 0.8750 over the incentive *Marketing labels*. The elements *Developing nature-positive production* and *Increased expenditure*

for marketing have high importance over the incentive *Marketing labels* with a score of 0.9.

Table 240 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/control criteria	Costs for information campaigns	Developing nature-positive production	Increased expenditure for marketing
1. Marketing labels	0.8750	0.9000	0.9000
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.1250	0.1000	0.1000

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Technological* control criteria in *Costs* the *Cover crop* element influences in highest degree the incentive *Voluntary farm set-asides* with a score of 0.7500. The incentive is also highly influenced by *Increasing short-term investments* with a score of 0.5472 and *Crop rotation* with a score of 0.5. The element *Precision agriculture* and *Increasing short term investments* have influence on incentive *Marketing labels* with a score of 0.9 and 0.8 respectively.

Table 241 Influence of elements on the incentives under Costs, Technological

Incentives/control criteria	Cover crops	Crop rotation	Increasing short-term investments	Precision agriculture
1. Marketing labels	0.2500	0.5000	0.8000	0.9000
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.7500	0.5000	0.2000	0.1000

Source: Own calculations

When considering *Cost saving* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* the element *Increasing expenditures for soil health operations* prioritizes the incentive *Marketing labels* with a score of 0.8571. The elements *Increasing initial costs* and *Increasing variable costs* influence the same incentive with a score of 0.8571. These numbers underscore the significance of marketing labels in investing in soil health operations and coping with initial costs.

Table 242 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Cost saving

Incentives/control criteria	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations	Increasing initial costs	Increasing variable costs
1. Marketing labels	0.8571	0.8750	0.8571
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.1428	0.1250	0.1428

Source: Own calculations

Regarding *Market linkages* cluster in *Economic* control criteria in *Risks* the element *Access to finance* influences the incentive *Marketing labels* with a

score of 0.8571. The highest importance of the rest of the element is on the same incentive with 0.9. These numbers underscore the significance of marketing labels in mitigating perceived risks and addressing initial costs, and the importance of the tourism for the sector.

Table 243 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Economic, Market linkages

Incentives/control criteria	Access to finance	Barriers to change practices for health practices	Initial costs	Perceived risk
1.Marketing labels	0.8571	0.9000	0.9000	0.9000
2.Voluntary farm set-asides	0.1428	0.1000	0.1000	0.1000

Source: Own calculations

During the analysis of *Political control* criteria in *Risks* it as estimated that the element *Decreasing liquidity* has strongest influence over *Marketing labels* incentive with a score of 0.75. The highest importance of the element *Income decrease* is over the incentive *Voluntary farm set-asides* with a score of 0.75. The element *Increasing the long term assets* has the moderate influence of 0.8 to the *Marketing labels* incentive. These insights highlight the varied impacts of different factors on business outcomes, emphasizing the need for tailored strategies to address specific challenges and risks.

Table 244 Influence of elements on the incentives under Risks, Political

Incentives/control criteria	Decreasing liquidity	Income decrease	Increasing the long term assets
1.Marketing labels	0.7500	0.2500	0.8000
2.Voluntary farm set-asides	0.2500	0.7500	0.2000

Source: Own calculations

Phase 2: Influence of control criteria on the new incentives

The influence of the separate clusters is estimated relatively by comparing them in the control criteria. That means that if there is one cluster in the control criteria the weight of the cluster is 1. If there are more than one clusters, they are compared and weights are derived. All economics clusters have two clusters: Market linkages and Cost savings. Their weights are shown in table... *Benefits* are assigned a weight of 0.75 for *Market linkages* and 0.25 for *Cost saving*. *Opportunities* receive a weight of 0.9 for *Market linkages* and 0.1 for *Cost saving*. *Costs* are weighted at 0.1 for *Market linkages* and 0.9 for *Cost saving*. *Risks* hold the same weight of 0.5 for *Market linkages* and for *Cost saving*. These numbers suggest that in both clusters, *Market linkages* is relatively more significant for the first two clusters, while *Costs saving* are given moderate importance for the other two.

Table 245 relative weights of the clusters

Control criteria	Clusters	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risks
Economic	Market linkages	0.7500	0.9000	0.1000	0.5000
	Cost saving	0.2500	0.1000	0.9000	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Benefits* the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Marketing labels* which is assigned a significant weight of 0.6587. The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is *Marketing labels* which is assigned a high score of 0.5972. The highest priority under the *Social* control criteria is *Marketing labels*, with a score of 0.8333. The highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is *Voluntary farm set-asides*, with a moderate weight of 0.7. These results reflect a strong importance of the *Economic*, *Political* and *Technological* factors over the on supporting products eligible under marketing labels.

Table 246 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under benefits

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political	Social	Technological
1. Marketing labels	0.6587	0.5972	0.8333	0.3000
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.3413	0.4028	0.1667	0.7000

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Opportunities*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Marketing labels*, which is assigned a weight of 0.8683. The highest priority under the *Social* control criteria is again *Voluntary farm set-asides*, with a weight of 0.6667. Lastly, the equal priority under the *Technological* control criteria is for *Marketing labels* and *Voluntary farm set-asides*, with a weight of 0.5. These results indicate a strong emphasis on marketing labels across *Economic* and *Technological* criteria.

Table 247 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under opportunities

Control criteria	Economic	Social	Technological
1. Marketing labels	0.8683	0.3333	0.5000
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.1317	0.6667	0.5000

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Costs*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Marketing labels*, which is assigned a weight of 0.7067. The highest priority under the *Technological* control criteria is

Marketing labels, with a weight of 0.6097. These results suggest a significant emphasis on *Marketing labels*, particularly in economic and technological considerations, indicating the importance of investment in quality assurance and compliance measures within these domains.

Table 248 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under costs

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Technological
1. Marketing labels	0.7067	0.6097
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.2933	0.3903

Source: Own calculations

When summarizing the results for *Risks*, the highest priority under the *Economic* control criteria is *Marketing labels*, which is assigned a weight of 0.8720. The highest priority under the *Political* control criteria is *Marketing labels*, with a weight of 0.4. These results suggest average concern for risks associated with supporting manufacturers eligible for marketing labels within economic and political considerations.

Table 249 Influence of control criteria on the incentives under risks

Incentives/control criteria	Economic	Political
1. Marketing labels	0.8720	0.6000
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.1280	0.4000

Source: Own calculations

Phase 3: Determining the control criteria weights and their influence on new incentives

The table below represents the relative weights of control criteria, where *Social* considerations hold the highest priority across *Benefits*. *Technological* control criteria have highest priority in *Opportunities*. *Economic* and *Technological* control criteria are equally important in *Costs*. *Political* considerations are prominent in addressing *Risks*, indicating a focus on regulatory and governance aspects to manage potential threats.

Table 250 Relative weights of the control criteria

Control criteria/blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
Economic	0.0881	0.1095	0.5000	0.1429
Technological	0.1855	0.3090	0.5000	-
Social	0.3642	0.5816	-	-
Political	0.3621	-	-	0.8571

Source: Own calculations

The table below represents the priorities under *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs* and *Risks* after considering the relative weights of the control criteria. All four categories prioritize the incentive *Marketing labels*. *Benefits* influence is with rating 0,6199. Additionally, *Opportunities* contribute with 0,4388 of the incentive's influence. *Costs* also play a significant role, representing 0,6546 of the influence. The last block *Risks*, though slightly less impactful, compare

with Costs contribute 0.6280 to the overall influence, highlighting a pragmatic approach that acknowledges and manages potential drawbacks or challenges associated with the incentive.

Table 251 Overall priorities

Incentives/blocks	Benefits	Opportunities	Costs	Risk
1. Marketing labels	0.6199	0.4388	0.6546	0.6280
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.3801	0.5612	0.3454	0.3720

Source: Own calculations

Phase 4: Strategic criteria weighting and final result

The next step is to estimate the Strategic criteria influence over the four categories. The estimation is subjective and is based on a focus group of experts from NBU. The estimation is made on 5-degree scale. This table presents a qualitative assessment of the three different strategic criteria – *Environmental care*, *To preserve landscapes and biodiversity* and *To protect food and health quality* over the categories *Benefits*, *Opportunities*, *Costs*, and *Risks*. Each criterion is evaluated based on its performance relative to others. For instance, in terms of *Benefits*, *Environmental Care* is rated as *Below Average*, while *Opportunities* in *To preserve landscapes and biodiversity* are deemed *Excellent*.

Table 252 Defining rating scale for strategic criteria

Blocks/strategic criteria	Fostering knowledge	To improve the position of farmers in the food chain	To protect food and health quality
Benefits	Excellent	Above Average	Excellent
Opportunities	Excellent	Above Average	Above Average
Costs	Above Average	Above Average	Average
Risks	Average	Above Average	-

Source: Own calculations

The relative weights of the strategic criteria are shown in the table below, where in column Totals are the final weights.

Table 253 ratings for strategic criteria and BOCR priorities

Blocks/strategic criteria	TOTALS	PRIORITIES	Fostering knowledge	To improve the position of farmers in the food chain	To protect food and health quality
Benefits	0.8546	0.3609	1.0000	0.6643	1.0000

Opportunities	0.6981	0.2947	1.0000	0.6643	0.6643
Costs	0.4972	0.2100	0.6643	0.6643	0.3061
Risks	0.3184	0.1345	0.3061	0.6643	0.0000

Source: Own calculations

The data in the table below presents priorities assigned to two different incentives. *Marketing labels* is noted with a priority value of 0.4052, indicating a moderate focus on ensuring adherence to quality standards and specifications. *Voluntary farm set-asides* holds a higher priority value of 0.5948.

Table 254 Overall outcome of BOCR

Incentives	Priorities
1. Marketing labels	0.4052
2. Voluntary farm set-asides	0.5948

Source: Own calculations

4. Conclusions

Table 255 summarizes the new incentives examined. 28 new incentives were proposed within the case studies. According to the classification of incentives in D 3.1, 19 (68%) incentives are policy driven and 9 are voluntary.

Ten of the new incentives are in category 1.5 Subsidies. These incentives are: Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most sensitive periods; Agri-environmental climatic schemes; ECO-SCHEME 5 (Italy)– Specific measures for pollinators; Italian fund for sustainable tourism 2023-25; Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods – CSR Toscana 2023-2027; Reduced soils processing techniques (ACA3) – CSR Toscana 2023-2027; Cover crops (ACA6) - CSR Toscana 2023-2027; Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods; Payment in order to implement cover crops. From the point of view of the business model, these incentives are related with Revenue and costs and Key activities.

One new incentive is in category 1.1 Prohibition of use - DüV: Ordinance on the application of fertilizers. This incentive is also related with Revenues and costs and Key activities in the business model.

Two new incentives are in category 1.10 Impact funds: Impact Funds for consultation and Local funds. That incentive is related with Revenues and costs and Key resources in the business model.

One incentive is in category 1.9 Offsets: Carbon Credits. This incentive is also related with Revenues and costs and Key activities in the business model.

Two new incentives are in category 2.7 Others (incentives not included in previous categories): Raising awareness of regional products and Collective action / association. These incentives are related with Channels and Partnerships and Key resources from the business model.

Three new incentives are in category 2.6 Marketing labels (without certificates or standards): Private soil health labels; Encouraging the association of producers and Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes. These new incentives are related with Customer value proposition and Channels and partnerships blocks from the business model.

One new incentive is in category 1.12 Corporate social responsibility: Private investments from companies. That incentive is related with Customer value proposition and Channels and partnerships blocks from the business model.

Three new incentives are in category 1.8 Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards): Establishing a marketing label/quality scheme; Quality schemes / private labelling and Marketing labels. These new incentives are related with Customer value proposition and Channels and partnerships blocks from the business model.

One new incentive is in category 2.4 Direct Payment for Ecosystem Services: Agroforestry eco-scheme under CAP strategic plan. That incentive is related with Channels and partnerships and Revenue and cost blocks from the business model.

One new incentive is in the category 1.3 Taxes/charges: Carbon credit certification schemes. That incentive is related with Revenue and cost and Key resources blocks from the business model.

One new incentive is in the category 2.1: Green bonds. That incentive is related with Revenue and cost and Key resources blocks from the business model.

One new incentive is in category 2.2: Voluntary farm set-asides. That incentive is related with Key resources and Key activities blocks from the business model.

One new incentive is in category 2.3 Conservation concessions: Conservation concessions. That incentive is related with Key resources and Key activities blocks from the business model.

This analysis, on the one hand, makes it possible to assess the gaps. On the other hand, it gives an opportunity to evaluate the new incentives. A simplified analogical approach will be used as a basis for the development of the second tool from Digital tools for soil health business models as a part of the NOVASOIL digital tool box.

Table 255 Summary of the incentives influence over the business model blocks

New Incentives from case studies	Code	Case study BM	Customer value preposition	Channels and partnerships	Revenue and cost	Key resources	Key activities
GLÖZ 6 (CAP): Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most sensitive periods	1.5	DE: "CO2-Land"					
DüV: Ordinance on the application of fertilizers	1.1	DE: "CO2-Land"					
Impact Funds for consultation	1.10	DE: "CO2-Land"					
Carbon Credits	1.9	IT 1: Producers' association "sandy district"					
Agri-environmental climatic schemes	1.5	IT 1: Producers' association "sandy district"					
Collective action / association	2.7	IT 1: Producers' association "sandy district"					
ECO-SCHEME 5 (Italy)– Specific measures for pollinators	1.5	IT 2: multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas					
Private soil health labels	2.6	IT 2: multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas					
Italian fund for sustainable tourism 2023-25	1.5	IT 2: multifunctional and sustainable local development of marginal areas					
Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods – CSR Toscana 2023-2027	1.5	IT 3: CiRAA LTEs on conventional and organic agriculture					
Reduced soils processing techniques (ACA3) – CSR Toscana 2023-2027	1.5	IT 3: CiRAA LTEs on conventional and organic agriculture					
Cover crops (ACA6) - CSR Toscana 2023-2027	1.5	IT 3: CiRAA LTEs on conventional and organic agriculture					
Private investments from companies	1.12	LV 1: Crop production and animal farming - Alley cropping system					
Establishing a marketing label/quality scheme	1.8	LV 1: Crop production and animal farming - Alley cropping system					
Agroforestry eco-scheme under CAP strategic plan	2.4	LV 1: Crop production and animal farming - Alley cropping system					

New Incentives from case studies	Code	Case study BM	Customer value preposition	Channels and partnerships	Revenue and cost	Key resources	Key activities
Carbon credit certification schemes	1.3	LV 2: Crop production and animal farming – Digital showcase					
Quality schemes / private labeling	1.8	LV 2: Crop production and animal farming – Digital showcase					
Financing from municipalities in a form of tax discounts	1.3	LV 2: Crop production and animal farming – Digital showcase					
Green bonds	2.1	SP 1: Integrated Production, Periurban park					
Local funds	1.10	SP 1: Integrated Production, Periurban park					
Conservation concessions	2.3	SP 1: Periurban park					
Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods	1.5	SP 2: Organic wine production – value chain from grapes cultivation to marketing					
Payment in order to implement cover crops	1.5	SP 2: Organic wine production – value chain from grapes cultivation to marketing					
Marketing labels	1.8	EE: production of quality seeds					
Voluntary farm set-asides	2.2	EE: production of quality seeds					
Raising awareness of regional products	2.7	BC: Integrated production in the vineyards with vinery and rural tourism					
Encouraging the association of producers	2.6	BC: Integrated production in the vineyards with vinery and rural tourism					
Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes	2.6	BC: Integrated production in the vineyards with vinery and rural tourism					

Source: Own calculations

5. Annexes

5.1 Annex 1 – BOCR structure and results for Spain: Integrated production case study

BOCR	Control criteria	Clusters	Elements in cluster
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Alternatives	Green bonds		
	Local funds		
	Conservation concessions		
Benefits	Economic 0,0833	Market linkages 0.2000	Producing safe food, GAPs, GMPs, Long chain
		Cost saving 0.8000	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Political 0,0833	Innovative financing 1	Better access to finance, Soil health financial measures, Improvement productivity, Efficiency improvement
	Social 0.7500	Contribution across local and national communities 1	Informational campaigns, Knowledge hubs
	Technological 0,0833	Resources 1	Knowledge of latest technologies, Immediately available
Opportunities	Economic 0,1673	Market linkages 0.2000	Long term results in food security, Food demand
		Cost saving 0.8000	Long term return, Initial costs, Sustainable crop production
	Social 0,7870	Sustainable soil use 1	Climate change, Biodiversity preservation, Soil quality, Regulation of water cycle
	Technological 0,0457	Soil restoration 1	Fertilization, Soil remediation, Sustainable soil management
Costs	Economic 0,8889	Market linkages 0,8571	Developing nature- positive production,

			Costs for information campaigns,
		Cost saving 0,1429	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Technological 0,1111	Investments in better technologies for healthy soil 1	Precision agriculture, Cover crops, Crop rotation, Increasing short-term investments,
Risks	Economic 0,8750	Market linkages 0,2000	Barriers to change practices for health practices, Perceived risk, Access to finance, Initial costs
		Cost saving 0,8000	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations, Increasing variable costs, Increasing initial costs
	Political 0,1250	Innovative financing 1	Decreasing liquidity, Increasing the long term assets, Income decrease
Strategic criteria	Strategic criteria 1: climate change action Strategic criteria 2: environmental care Strategic criteria 3: to preserve landscapes and biodiversity.		

Source: Own calculations

5.2 Annex 2 – BOCR structure and results for Spain: Organic wine in Rueda

BOCR	Control criteria	Clusters	Elements in cluster
Alternatives	Payment to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods		
	Payment in order to implement cover crops		
Benefits	Economic 0,5379	Market linkages 0,8000	Producing safe food, GAPs, GMPs, Long chain

		Cost saving 0,2000	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Political 0,0490	Innovative financing 1	Better access to finance, Soil health financial measures, Improvement productivity, Efficiency improvement
	Social 0,0993	Contribution across local and national communities 1	Informational campaigns, Knowledge hubs
	Technological 0,3139	Resources 1	Knowledge of latest technologies, Immediately available
Opportunities	Economic 0,4126	Market linkages 0,8571	Long term results in food security, Food demand
		Cost saving 0,1429	Long term return, Initial costs, Sustainable crop production
	Social 0,3275	Sustainable soil use 1	Climate change, Biodiversity preservation, Soil quality, Regulation of water cycle
	Technological 0,2599	Soil restoration 1	Fertilization, Soil remediation, Sustainable soil management
Costs	Economic 0,8571	Market linkages 0,8333	Developing nature-positive production, Costs for information campaigns,
		Cost saving 0,1666	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality,

			Decreasing variable costs
	Technological 0,1429	Investments in better technologies for healthy soil 1	Precision agriculture, Cover crops, Crop rotation, Increasing short-term investments,
Risks	Economic 0,8750	Market linkages 0,8333	Barriers to change practices for health practices, Perceived risk, Access to finance, Initial costs
		Cost saving 0,1666	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations, Increasing variable costs, Increasing initial costs
	Political 0,1250	Innovative financing 1	Decreasing liquidity, Increasing the long term assets, Income decrease
Strategic criteria	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. SG5. Environmental care; 2. SG9. To protect food and health quality; 3. SG10. Fostering knowledge and innovation. 		

Source: Own calculations

5.3 Annex 2 – BOCR structure and results for Bulgaria: Integrated production in the vineyards with vinery and rural tourism

BOCR	Control criteria	Clusters	Elements in cluster
Alternatives	1. Raising awareness of regional products		
	2. Encouraging the association of producers		
	3. Assistance to manufacturers of products with potential for protection under European quality schemes		
Benefits	Economic 0.4553	Market linkages 0.5	Producing safe food, GAPs, GMPs, Long chain
		Cost saving 0.5	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs

	Technological 0.3355	Resources 1	Knowledge of latest technologies, Immediately available
	Social 0.1281	Contribution across local and national communities 1	Informational campaigns, Knowledge hubs
	Political 0.0811	Innovative financing 1	Better access to finance, Soil health financial measures, Improvement productivity, Efficiency improvement
Opportunities	Economic 0.4806	Market linkages 0.3333	Long term results in food security, Food demand
		Cost saving 0.6667	Long term return, Initial costs, Sustainable crop production
	Technological 0.4054	Soil restoration 1	Fertilization, Soil remediation, Sustainable soil management
	Social 0.1140	Sustainable soil use 1	Climate change, Biodiversity preservation, Soil quality, Regulation of water cycle
Costs	Economic 0.6667	Market linkages 0.8	Developing nature-positive production, Costs for information campaigns, Increased expenditure for marketing
		Cost saving 0.2	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Technological 0.3333	Investments in better technologies for healthy soil 1	Precision agriculture, Cover crops, Crop rotation, Increasing short-term investments,

Risks	Economic 0.6667	Market linkages 0.75	Barriers to change practices for health practices, Perceived risk, Access to finance, Initial costs
		Cost saving 0.25	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations, Increasing variable costs, Increasing initial costs
	Political 0.3333	Innovative financing 1	Decreasing liquidity, Increasing the long term assets, Income decrease
Strategic criteria	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Environmental care, 2. To preserve landscapes and biodiversity, 3. To protect food and health quality 		

Source: Own calculations

5.4 Annex 2 – BOCR structure and results for Italy: District of the Sands

BOCR	Control criteria	Clusters	Elements in cluster
Alternatives	Carbon Credits		
	Agri-environmental climatic schemes		
	Collective action / association		
Benefits	Economic 0.2508	Market linkages 0,6666	Producing safe food, GAPs, GMPs, Long chain
		Cost saving 0,3333	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Political 0.1917	Innovative financing 1	Better access to finance, Soil health financial measures, Improvement productivity, Efficiency improvement
	Social 0.2629	Contribution across local and national communities	Informational campaigns, Knowledge hubs

		1	
	Technological 0.2947	Resources 1	Knowledge of latest technologies, Immediately available
Opportunities	Economic 0.1634	Market linkages 0,2500	Long term results in food security, Food demand
		Cost saving 0,7500	Long term return, Initial costs, Sustainable crop production
	Social 0.5396	Sustainable soil use 1	Climate change, Biodiversity preservation, Soil quality, Regulation of water cycle
	Technological 0.2970	Soil restoration 1	Fertilization, Soil remediation, Sustainable soil management
Costs	Economic 0.8750	Market linkages 0,2500	Developing nature-positive production, Costs for information campaigns,
		Cost saving 0,7500	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Technological 0.1250	Investments in better technologies for healthy soil 1	Precision agriculture, Cover crops, Crop rotation, Increasing short-term investments,
Risks	Economic 0.2000	Market linkages 0,5000	Barriers to change practices for health practices, Perceived risk, Access to finance, Initial costs
		Cost saving 0,5000	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations, Increasing variable costs, Increasing initial costs
	Political 0.8000	Innovative financing	Decreasing liquidity,

		1	Increasing the long term assets, Income decrease
Strategic criteria	SC 1 fair income SC 3 food chain SC 10 innovation		

Source: Own calculations

5.5 Annex 2 – BOCR structure and results for Italy: A model for multifunctional I and sustainable local development of marginal areas

BOCR	Control criteria	Clusters	Elements in cluster
Alternatives	ECO-SCHEME 5 - Specific measures for pollinators;		
	Private soil health labels;		
	Italian fund for sustainable tourism		
Benefits	Economic 0.1728	Market linkages 0.6666–	Producing safe food, GAPs, GMPs, Long chain
		Cost saving 0.3333	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Political 0.3769	Innovative financing 1	Better access to finance, Soil health financial measures, Improvement productivity, Efficiency improvement
	Social 0.3769	Contribution across local and national communities 1	Informational campaigns, Knowledge hubs
	Technological 0.0734	Resources 1	Knowledge of latest technologies, Immediately available
Opportunities	Economic 0.4126	Market linkages 0.1000	Long term results in food security, Food demand
		Cost saving 0.9000	Long term return, Initial costs, Sustainable crop production

	Social 0.2599	Sustainable soil use 1	Climate change, Biodiversity preservation, Soil quality, Regulation of water cycle
	Technological 0.3275	Soil restoration 1	Fertilization, Soil remediation, Sustainable soil management
Costs	Economic 0.8000	Market linkages 0.7500	Developing nature- positive production, Costs for information campaigns,
		Cost saving 0.2500	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Technological 0.2000	Investments in better technologies for healthy soil 1	Precision agriculture, Cover crops, Crop rotation, Increasing short-term investments,
Risks	Economic 0.50000	Market linkages 0.5000	Barriers to change practices for health practices, Perceived risk, Access to finance, Initial costs
		Cost saving 0.5000	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations, Increasing variable costs, Increasing initial costs
	Political 0.50000	Innovative financing 1	Decreasing liquidity, Increasing the long term assets, Income decrease
Strategic criteria	6. To preserve landscapes and biodiversity 5. environmental care 8. Vibrant rural areas		

Source: Own calculations

5.6 Annex 2 – BOCR structure and results for Italy: CiRAA LTEs on conventional and organic agriculture

BOCR	Control criteria	Clusters	Elements in cluster
Alternatives	Payment in order to adopt and maintain organic production practices and methods		
	Reduced soils processing techniques		
	Cover crops		
Benefits	Economic 0,2061	Market linkages 0.6666	Producing safe food, GAPs, GMPs, Long chain
		Cost saving 0.3333	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Political 0,4334	Innovative financing 1	Better access to finance, Soil health financial measures, Improvement productivity, Efficiency improvement
	Social 0,2922	Contribution across local and national communities 1	Informational campaigns, Knowledge hubs
	Technological 0,0684	Resources 1	Knowledge of latest technologies, Immediately available
Opportunities	Economic 0,3695	Market linkages 0.5000	Long term results in food security, Food demand
		Cost saving 0.5000	Long term return, Initial costs, Sustainable crop production
	Social 0,2238	Sustainable soil use 1	Climate change, Biodiversity preservation, Soil quality, Regulation of water cycle
	Technological	Soil restoration	Fertilization,

	0,4067	1	Soil remediation, Sustainable soil management
Costs	Economic 0,6667	Market linkages 0,3333	Developing nature- positive production, Costs for information campaigns, Increased expenditure for marketing
		Cost saving 0,6666	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Technological 0,3333	Investments in better technologies for healthy soil 1	Precision agriculture, Cover crops, Crop rotation, Increasing short- term investments,
Risks	Economic 0.50000	Market linkages 0,3333	Barriers to change practices for health practices, Perceived risk, Access to finance, Initial costs
		Cost saving 0,6666	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations, Increasing variable costs, Increasing initial costs
	Political 0.50000	Innovative financing 1	Decreasing liquidity, Increasing the long term assets, Income decrease
Strategic criteria	SG5. Environmental care SG9. To protect food and health quality; SG10. Fostering knowledge and innovation.		

Source: Own calculations

5.7 Annex 2 – BOCR structure and results for Latvia: Crop production and animal farming

BOCR	Control criteria	Clusters	Elements in cluster
Alternatives	Private investments		
	Establishing a marketing 'Agroforestry' label		
	Establishing an eco-scheme: Agroforestry practices		
Benefits	Economic 0.4621	Market linkages 0.80	Producing safe food, GAPs, GMPs, Long chain
		Cost saving 0.20	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Political 0.1344	Innovative financing 1	Better access to finance, Soil health financial measures, Improvement productivity, Efficiency improvement
	Social 0.3008	Contribution across local and national communities 1	Informational campaigns, Knowledge hubs
	Technological 0.1026	Resources 1	Knowledge of latest technologies, Immediately available
Opportunities	Economic 0.4444	Market linkages 0.8571	Long term results in food security, Food demand
		Cost saving 0.1429	Long term return, Initial costs, Sustainable crop production
	Social 0.4444	Sustainable soil use 1	Climate change, Biodiversity preservation, Soil quality, Regulation of water cycle
	Technological 0.1111	Soil restoration 1	Fertilization, Soil remediation, Sustainable soil management

Costs	Economic 0.8000	Market linkages 0.80	Developing nature-positive production, Costs for information campaigns,
		Cost saving 0.20	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Technological 0.2000	Investments in better technologies for healthy soil 1	Precision agriculture, Cover crops, Crop rotation, Increasing short-term investments,
Risks	Economic 0.8333	Market linkages 0.8333	Barriers to change practices for health practices, Perceived risk, Access to finance, Initial costs
		Cost saving 0.1667	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations, Increasing variable costs, Increasing initial costs
	Political 0.1667	Innovative financing 1	Decreasing liquidity, Increasing the long term assets, Income decrease
Strategic criteria	1. to ensure a fair income for farmers; 5. environmental care; 6. to preserve landscapes and biodiversity		

Source: Own calculations

5.8 Annex 2 – BOCR structure and results for 3.8 Latvia: Forest management

BOCR	Control criteria	Clusters	Elements in cluster
Alternatives	1. Carbon credit schemes		
	2. Private labelling		
	3. Municipal tax discounts		

Benefits	Economic 0.0385	Market linkages 0.8889	Producing safe food, GAPs, GMPs, Long chain
		Cost saving 0.1111	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Political 0.1982	Innovative financing 1	Better access to finance, Soil health financial measures, Improvement productivity, Efficiency improvement
	Social 0.3177	Contribution across local and national communities 1	Informational campaigns, Knowledge hubs
	Technological 0.4456	Resources 1	Knowledge of latest technologies, Immediately available
Opportunities	Economic 0.0754	Market linkages 0.8333	Long term results in food security, Food demand
		Cost saving 0.1666	Long term return, Initial costs, Sustainable crop production
	Social 0.6955	Sustainable soil use 1	Climate change, Biodiversity preservation, Soil quality, Regulation of water cycle
	Technological 0.2291	Soil restoration 1	Fertilization, Soil remediation, Sustainable soil management
Costs	Economic 0.8000	Market linkages 0.8000	Developing nature-positive production, Costs for information campaigns,

		Cost saving 0.2000	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Technological 0.2000	Investments in better technologies for healthy soil 1	Precision agriculture, Cover crops, Crop rotation, Increasing short-term investments,
Risks	Economic 0.8333	Market linkages 0.8571	Barriers to change practices for health practices, Perceived risk, Access to finance, Initial costs
		Cost saving 0.1429	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations, Increasing variable costs, Increasing initial costs
	Political 0.1667	Innovative financing 1	Decreasing liquidity, Increasing the long term assets, Income decrease
Strategic criteria	1. to ensure a fair income for farmers; 3. to improve the position of farmers in the food chain; 5. environmental care;		

Source: Own calculations

5.9 Annex 2 – BOCR structure and results for Germany: CO₂-Land

BOCR	Control criteria	Clusters	Elements in cluster
Alternatives	GLÖZ 6 (CAP): Minimum ground cover to avoid soils without vegetation during the most		
	DüV: Ordinance on the application of fertilizers, soil additives, growing media and plant		
	Impact Funds for consultation		
Benefits	Economic 0.2994	Market linkages 0.5	Producing safe food,

			GAPs, GMPs, Long chain
		Cost saving 0.5	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Political 0.2389	Innovative financing 1	Better access to finance, Soil health financial measures, Improvement productivity, Efficiency improvement
	Social 0.2087	Contribution across local and national communities 1	Informational campaigns, Knowledge hubs
	Technological 0.2530	Resources 1	Knowledge of latest technologies, Immediately available
Opportunities	Economic 0.3487	Market linkages 0.5	Long term results in food security, Food demand
		Cost saving 0.5	Long term return, Initial costs, Sustainable crop production
	Social 0.1677	Sustainable soil use 1	Climate change, Biodiversity preservation, Soil quality, Regulation of water cycle
	Technological 0.4836	Soil restoration 1	Fertilization, Soil remediation, Sustainable soil management
Costs	Economic 0.7500	Market linkages 0.3333	Developing nature- positive production, Costs for information campaigns,

			Increased expenditure for marketing
		Cost saving 0.6667	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Technological 0.2500	Investments in better technologies for healthy soil 1	Precision agriculture, Cover crops, Crop rotation, Increasing short-term investments,
Risks	Economic 0.8000	Market linkages 0.25	Barriers to change practices for health practices, Perceived risk, Access to finance, Initial costs
		Cost saving 0.75	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations, Increasing variable costs, Increasing initial costs
	Political 0.2000	Innovative financing 1	Decreasing liquidity, Increasing the long term assets, Income decrease
Strategic criteria	4. Environmental care, 5. climate change action 6. to ensure a fair income for farmers 7. fostering knowledge and innovation		

Source: Own calculations

5.10 Annex 2 – BOCR structure and results for Estonia: Crop production

BOCR	Control criteria	Clusters	Elements in cluster
Alternatives	Marketing labels		
	Voluntary farm set-asides		

Benefits	Economic 0.0881	Market linkages 0.75	Producing safe food, GAPs, GMPs, Long chain
		Cost saving 0.25	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Political 0.3621	Innovative financing 1	Better access to finance, Soil health financial measures, Improvement productivity, Efficiency improvement
	Social 0.3642	Contribution across local and national communities 1	Informational campaigns, Knowledge hubs
	Technological 0.1855	Resources 1	Knowledge of latest technologies, Immediately available
Opportunities	Economic 0.109452	Market linkages 0.90	Long term results in food security, Food demand
		Cost saving 0.10	Long term return, Initial costs, Sustainable crop production
	Social 0.581552	Sustainable soil use 1	Climate change, Biodiversity preservation, Soil quality, Regulation of water cycle
	Technological 0.308996	Soil restoration 1	Fertilization, Soil remediation, Sustainable soil management
Costs	Economic 0.5	Market linkages 0.10	Developing nature-positive production,

			Costs for information campaigns, Increased expenditure for marketing
		Cost saving 0.90	Gross margin increasing, Higher retail price, Better product quality, Decreasing variable costs
	Technological 0.5	Investments in better technologies for healthy soil 1	Precision agriculture, Cover crops, Crop rotation, Increasing short-term investments,
Risks	Economic 0.142857	Market linkages 0.5	Barriers to change practices for health practices, Perceived risk, Access to finance, Initial costs
		Cost saving 0.5	Increasing expenditures for soil health operations, Increasing variable costs, Increasing initial costs
	Political 0.857143	Innovative financing 1	Decreasing liquidity, Increasing the long term assets, Income decrease
Strategic criteria	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Fostering knowledge and innovation 2. To improve the position of farmers in the food chain 3. To protect food and health quality 		

Source: Own calculations

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